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Modélisation hydrodynamique d'une rivière méso-tidale basée sur des mesures SWOT et in situ dans une région pauvre en données

Hydrodynamic modelling of a meso-tidal river using in-situ and SWOT measurements in a data-scarce region

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Hydrodynamic modelling of a meso-tidal river
based on in situ and SWOT measurements
in a data-scarce region

**Achieving a better understanding of the hydrological-to-ocean
continuum in the estuary of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam**

Francisco Rodrigues do Amaral

July 11th, 2024

To Clara and Atlas
and all my family

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Summary in English

Coastal environments have historically supported thriving societies due to their rich food resources, fertile soils, and strategic locations as transportation hubs, fostering urban development and economic growth. This trend continues today, with many of the world's most densely populated cities situated in Low-Elevation Coastal Zones (LECZs). Currently, approximately 896 million people, nearly 11% of the global population in 2020, reside in LECZs, and this number is projected to exceed one billion by 2050.

Coastal megacities face substantial risks from climate change due to their low elevation, climate-sensitive physical and ecological characteristics, and high societal exposure and vulnerability. Despite these risks, LECZs are poorly monitored globally, especially in under-developed and developing countries.

This thesis focuses on the poorly gauged LECZ of Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC) in South Vietnam. HCMC, a densely populated megacity, has urban center areas with up to 30,000 inhabitants per square kilometer. The city is traversed by the tidal Saigon River, which includes a network of about 800 km of watercourses and canals. With 90% of HCMC's urban area being impermeable, the hydrological cycle is significantly impacted, leading to frequent flooding from coastal, riverine, and rainfall runoff sources.

Achieving a sustainable future for HCMC relies on our ability to monitor both hydrological and oceanographic variables concurrently to better understand the physics of these systems. To enhance our understanding of this estuarine system, two key variables are of interest: river and coastal ocean water levels, and river discharge. These variables can be effectively monitored using a combination of in-situ and satellite measurements.

The general objective of this thesis is to achieve a better understanding of the hydrological-to-ocean continuum in the LECZ of Ho Chi Minh City. To do so we use a trinity of tools: in-situ measurements, remote sensing measurements and hydrodynamic modelling. In specific, we are interested in assessing the potential of the new Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite mission over this region.

Chapter 1 introduces the subject area of the thesis.

Chapter 2 assesses the impact of Typhoon Usagi, which made landfall in HCMC in 2018. The typhoon did not create a significant storm surge but

caused extreme rainfall, leading to significant inland water level surges. Prolonged flooding in the city, especially in Thao Dien, resulted from the combination of a high river spring tide and impervious, low-lying streets. Coastal tidal forcing was the main driver of river discharge during this event. A general insight into the the behaviour of the Saigon river was also found: seasonal coastal storm surges from East Asian summer monsoon wind patterns, rather than precipitation, were found to control river water levels.

Chapter 3 presents data from a two-month field campaign in HCMC, where high-resolution river water level and discharge measurements were obtained. This campaign was managed and supervised by me, with assistance from Mr. Tin Nguyen Trung of the Center for Asian Research on Water (CARE).

Chapter 4 details the implementation, calibration, and validation of a 1D hydrodynamic model of the Saigon and Dongnai rivers, addressing calibration challenges in this data-scarce region. The model, coupled with a modified Manning-Strickler (MS) law, was developed in collaboration with Dr. Benoit Camenen of INRAE. The best calibration strategy was found to involve directly measured water levels and indirectly measured discharge data, despite challenges from dynamic tidal conditions and lack of reliable upstream discharge data. Validation against independent measurements showed promising results, demonstrating the effectiveness of the modified MS equation in enhancing discharge estimates.

Chapter 5 provides a statistical study of the potential of SWOT satellite data to improve discharge estimations in the Saigon River, conducted before real SWOT data was available. A methodology using simulated SWOT products at a 200-meter node resolution showed improved discharge estimates by reducing mean relative RMSE and increasing R^2 between true and estimated discharge.

Chapter 6 explores the application of real SWOT data in one of the most challenging coastal environments this satellite mission could encounter: a data-scarce, tropical region characterized by flat topography, a heavily urbanized environment, and a river with a weak water surface slope that fluctuates daily around zero due to strong coastal tidal forcing. To do so, we compare SWOT's reach level products of river water level and slope against in-situ measurements. The results show that about 50% of SWOT's water level measurements were found to be valid compared to in-situ data, showing a good accuracy despite the challenges posed by this region. However, SWOT's slope measurements lack accuracy and are unreliable without prior validation against in-situ data. Despite these limitations, SWOT provides high-spatial resolution observations that can offer new insights into dynamic hydrological phenomena when combined with in-situ data and modeling efforts.

Chapter 7 concludes the thesis and offers perspectives for future work.

Résumé en Français

Les environnements côtiers ont historiquement soutenu des sociétés florissantes en raison de leurs riches ressources alimentaires, de leurs sols fertiles et de leurs emplacements stratégiques en tant que centres de transport, favorisant le développement urbain et la croissance économique. Cette tendance se poursuit aujourd'hui, avec de nombreuses villes parmi les plus densément peuplées au monde situées dans les Zones Côtières de Basse Altitude (LECZ). Actuellement, environ 896 millions de personnes, soit près de 11% de la population mondiale en 2020, résident dans les LECZ, et ce nombre devrait dépasser un milliard d'ici 2050.

Les mégapoles côtières font face à des risques importants liés au changement climatique en raison de leur faible altitude, de leurs caractéristiques physiques et écologiques sensibles au climat, ainsi que de leur forte exposition et vulnérabilité sociétale. Malgré ces risques, les LECZ sont globalement mal suivies, notamment dans les pays sous-développés et en développement.

Cette thèse concerne la LECZ de Ho Chi Minh-Ville (HCMV) dans le sud du Vietnam, une région peu dotée en données. HCMV, une mégapole densément peuplée, possède des zones urbaines avec jusqu'à 30 000 habitants par kilomètre carré. La ville est traversée par le fleuve Saïgon, qui inclut un réseau d'environ 800 km de cours d'eau et de canaux. Avec 90 % de la zone urbaine de HCMV étant imperméable, le cycle hydrologique est considérablement perturbé, entraînant des inondations fréquentes dues aux sources côtières, fluviales et de ruissellement pluvial.

Pour assurer un avenir durable à HCMV, il est crucial de mesurer simultanément les variables hydrologiques et océanographiques afin de mieux comprendre la physique de ces systèmes. Afin d'améliorer notre compréhension de ce système estuarien, deux variables clés sont d'intérêt : les niveaux d'eau des rivières et de l'océan côtier, ainsi que le débit des rivières. Ces variables peuvent être efficacement surveillées en combinant des mesures in-situ et des mesures par satellite.

L'objectif général de cette thèse est d'acquérir une meilleure compréhension du continuum hydrologique-océan dans la LECZ de Ho Chi Minh-Ville. Pour ce faire, nous utilisons trois outils : des mesures in-situ, des mesures par télédétection et une modélisation hydrodynamique. Plus précisément, nous

nous intéressons à évaluer le potentiel de la nouvelle mission spatiale Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) pour cette région.

Le Chapitre 1 introduit le domaine d'étude de la thèse.

Le Chapitre 2 évalue l'impact du Typhon Usagi, qui a atteint les côtes de HCMV en 2018. Le typhon n'a pas provoqué de surcôte significative mais a engendré des pluies extrêmes, entraînant des crues importantes. L'inondation prolongée dans la ville, en particulier à Thao Dien, a résulté de la combinaison d'une marée haute dans la rivière et des rues imperméables. La forçage des marées côtières a été le principal moteur du débit fluvial durant cet événement. Un aperçu général du comportement du fleuve Saïgon a également été trouvé : les surcôtes côtières saisonnières dues aux régimes de vent de la mousson d'été de l'Asie de l'Est, plutôt que les précipitations, contrôlent les niveaux d'eau du fleuve.

Le Chapitre 3 présente les données d'une campagne de terrain de deux mois à HCMV, où des mesures de haute résolution des niveaux d'eau des rivières et des débits ont été obtenues. Cette campagne a été gérée et supervisée par moi, avec l'assistance de M. Tin Nguyen Trung du Centre Asiatique de Recherche sur l'Eau (CARE).

Le Chapitre 4 détaille la mise en œuvre, l'étalonnage et la validation d'un modèle hydrodynamique 1D des rivières Saïgon et Dongnai, abordant les défis d'étalonnage dans cette région peu dotée en données. Le modèle, couplé avec une loi modifiée de Manning-Strickler (MS), a été développé en collaboration avec Dr. Benoit Camenen de l'INRAE. La meilleure stratégie d'étalonnage a été trouvée en combinant des niveaux d'eau mesurés directement et des données de débit mesurées indirectement, malgré les défis liés aux conditions dynamiques des marées et au manque de données fiables sur les débits amont. La validation contre des mesures indépendantes a montré des résultats prometteurs, démontrant l'efficacité de l'équation MS modifiée pour améliorer les estimations de débit.

Le Chapitre 5 fournit une étude statistique du potentiel des données du satellite SWOT pour améliorer les estimations de débit dans le fleuve Saïgon, réalisée avant la disponibilité des données réelles de SWOT. Une méthodologie utilisant des produits SWOT simulés à une résolution de nœud de 200 mètres a montré des améliorations dans les estimations de débit en réduisant le RMSE et en augmentant le R^2 entre le débit réel et estimé.

Le Chapitre 6 explore l'application des données réelles de SWOT dans l'un des environnements côtiers les plus difficiles que cette mission spatiale pourrait rencontrer : une région tropicale peu dotée en données, caractérisée par une topographie plane, un environnement fortement urbanisé et un fleuve avec une pente de surface d'eau faible qui fluctue quotidiennement autour de zéro en raison du fort forçage des marées côtières. Pour ce faire, nous com-

parons les produits de niveau d'eau et de pente de SWOT avec des mesures in-situ. Les résultats montrent qu'environ 50 % des mesures de niveau d'eau de SWOT ont été jugées valides par rapport aux données in-situ, montrant une bonne précision malgré les défis posés par cette région. Cependant, les mesures de pente de SWOT manquent de précision et sont peu fiables sans validation préalable par des données in-situ. Malgré ces limitations, SWOT offre des observations à haute résolution spatiale qui peuvent fournir de nouvelles perspectives sur les phénomènes hydrologiques dynamiques lorsqu'elles sont combinées avec des données in-situ et des efforts de modélisation.

Le Chapitre 7 conclut la thèse et propose des perspectives pour les travaux futurs.

Tóm tắt bằng tiếng Việt

Môi trường ven biển từ lâu đã hỗ trợ các xã hội phát triển mạnh nhờ vào nguồn tài nguyên thực phẩm phong phú, đất đai màu mỡ, và vị trí chiến lược như các trung tâm giao thông, thúc đẩy phát triển đô thị và tăng trưởng kinh tế. Xu hướng này vẫn tiếp tục cho đến ngày nay, với nhiều thành phố đông dân nhất trên thế giới nằm ở các Vùng Ven Biển Cao Độ Thấp - Low-Elevation Coastal Zones (LECZs). Hiện nay, với khoảng 896 triệu người, gần 11% dân số toàn cầu vào năm 2020, sinh sống ở vùng LECZ, và con số này dự kiến sẽ vượt qua một tỷ vào năm 2050.

Các siêu đô thị ven biển đang đối mặt với những rủi ro đáng kể từ biến đổi khí hậu do có cao độ thấp, các đặc điểm vật lý và sinh thái nhạy cảm với khí hậu, và xã hội dễ bị tổn thương và thường xuyên đối mặt với các rủi ro. Mặc cho những rủi ro này, các vùng LECZ vẫn chưa được theo dõi đầy đủ trên toàn cầu, đặc biệt là ở các nước kém phát triển và đang phát triển. Luận án này tập trung vào việc đánh giá vùng LECZ ít được khảo sát của Thành phố Hồ Chí Minh (TP.HCM) tại miền Nam, Việt Nam. TP.HCM, một siêu đô thị đông dân, với các trung tâm đô thị có mật độ dân số lên đến 30.000 người trên mỗi km vuông. Thành phố này được chia cắt bởi sông Sài Gòn với chế độ thủy triều, cùng với một mạng lưới khoảng 800 km các con sông và kênh rạch. Cùng với đó 90% diện tích đô thị của TP.HCM không thấm nước, chu trình thủy văn bị ảnh hưởng nghiêm trọng, dẫn đến tình trạng ngập lụt thường xuyên từ các nguồn nước ven biển, sông ngòi, và mưa.

Để đạt được một tương lai bền vững cho TP.HCM, chúng ta cần nâng cao năng lực theo dõi đồng thời các biến số thủy văn và đại dương học để hiểu rõ hơn về các hiện tượng vật lý của các hệ thống này. Để nâng cao hiểu biết về hệ sinh thái cửa sông, hai biến số chính được quan tâm là mực nước của sông và vùng biển ven biển, và lưu lượng dòng sông. Những biến số này có thể được theo dõi hiệu quả bằng cách kết hợp các đo đạc tại chỗ và đo đạc từ vệ tinh. Mục tiêu chung của luận án này là hiểu rõ hơn về quá trình liên tục từ thủy văn đến đại dương trong khu vực LECZ của Thành phố Hồ Chí Minh. Để thực hiện điều này, chúng tôi sử dụng một bộ phương pháp bao gồm: đo đạc tại chỗ, đo đạc từ xa và mô hình thủy động lực học. Cụ thể, chúng tôi quan tâm đến việc đánh giá tiềm năng của vệ tinh SWOT, hay còn gọi là Surface Water and Ocean Topography, ở khu vực này.

Chương 1 giới thiệu về lĩnh vực nghiên cứu của luận án.

Chương 2 đánh giá tác động của cơn bão Usagi, đã đổ bộ vào TP.HCM vào năm 2018. Cơn bão không tạo ra các đợt sóng lớn nhưng gây ra mưa lớn bất thường, dẫn đến sự gia tăng mực nước nội địa đáng kể. Ngập lụt kéo dài ở thành phố, đặc biệt ở khu vực Thảo Điền, là kết quả của sự kết hợp giữa triều cường trên sông cao và các con đường thấp, không thấm nước. Sự thúc đẩy từ thủy triều vùng ven biển là yếu tố chính dẫn đến lưu lượng dòng sông trong sự kiện này. Một cái nhìn tổng quát về chế độ của sông Sài Gòn được phát hiện như sau: sự dâng sóng trong mùa bão ven biển từ các kiểu gió hè Đông Á, thay vì lượng mưa, đã điều khiển mực nước sông.

Chương 3 trình bày dữ liệu từ một chiến dịch khảo sát thực địa kéo dài hai tháng tại TP.HCM, nơi đã thu thập các số liệu đo mực nước sông và lưu lượng nước có độ phân giải cao. Chiến dịch này được tối ưu quản lý và giám sát, với sự hỗ trợ của ông Nguyễn Trung Tín từ Trung tâm Nghiên cứu Nước Châu Á (CARE).

Chương 4 trình bày chi tiết về việc triển khai, hiệu chỉnh và xác thực mô hình thủy động lực học 1D của sông Sài Gòn và sông Đồng Nai, giải quyết các thách thức hiệu chỉnh trong khu vực thiếu dữ liệu. Mô hình này, kết hợp với phương trình Manning-Strickler (MS) đã sửa đổi, được phát triển cùng với ông Dr. Benoit Camenen từ INRAE. Phương pháp hiệu chỉnh tốt nhất được tìm thấy là kết hợp giữa dữ liệu mực nước đo trực tiếp và dữ liệu lưu lượng đo gián tiếp, mặc dù gặp phải thách thức từ điều kiện thủy triều động và thiếu dữ liệu lưu lượng đầu nguồn đáng tin cậy. Việc xác thực với các thông số đo độc lập cho thấy những kết quả hứa hẹn, chứng minh hiệu quả của phương trình MS đã qua sửa đổi trong việc cải thiện các tính toán lưu lượng.

Chương 5 cung cấp một nghiên cứu thống kê về khả năng của dữ liệu vệ tinh SWOT trong việc cải thiện tính toán lưu lượng sông Sài Gòn, được thực hiện trước khi dữ liệu SWOT thực tế có sẵn. Một phương pháp sử dụng các kết quả mô phỏng của SWOT với độ phân giải điểm 200 mét đã cho thấy sự cải thiện trong tính toán lưu lượng bằng cách giảm sai số RMSE tương đối trung bình và tăng R² giữa lưu lượng thực tế và tính toán.

Chương 6 khám phá ứng dụng của dữ liệu thực tế SWOT tại một trong những môi trường ven biển thách thức nhất mà vệ tinh này có thể gặp phải: một khu vực nhiệt đới thiếu dữ liệu với địa hình phẳng, môi trường đô thị hóa mạnh, và một con sông có độ dốc mặt nước yếu dao động hàng ngày xung quanh mức không do tác động mạnh của thủy triều ven biển. Để thực hiện điều này, chúng tôi so sánh các kết quả mực nước sông và độ dốc từ dữ liệu SWOT với các số đo tại chỗ. Kết quả cho thấy khoảng 50% các phép đo mực nước của SWOT được xác nhận là hợp lý so với dữ liệu tại chỗ, cho thấy độ chính xác tốt mặc dù gặp phải thách thức từ khu vực này. Tuy nhiên, các phép đo độ dốc của SWOT thiếu độ chính xác và không đáng tin cậy nếu không

được xác thực trước với dữ liệu tại chỗ. Dù có những hạn chế này, SWOT cung cấp các quan sát với độ phân giải cao theo không gian từ đó có thể đưa ra những hiểu biết mới về các hiện tượng thủy văn động khi kết hợp với dữ liệu tại chỗ và nỗ lực mô hình hóa.

Chương 7 kết luận luận án và đưa ra các hướng nghiên cứu trong tương lai.

Maps of the region

Map 1: Topography of the region. The black line is the district of HCMC for all maps (1, 2, 3 and 4). Topographic data from the NASA Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) ~30 meter product. DOI: 10.5066/F7PR7TFT

Map 2: High-Resolution Land-Use and Land-Cover Map. Land cover data for the year 2020 from the Advanced land Observing Satellite (ALOS) project. DOI: 10.3390/rs12172707

Map 3: Hydrological system of the area. Data from the International Steering Committee for Global Mapping (2016). Retrieved from Stanford digital repository.

Map 4: Population density for 2019. Data from the Global High Resolution Population Denominators Project. DOI: 10.5258/SOTON/WP00674

Contents

Acknowledgements	3
Summary in English	5
Résumé en Français	7
Tóm tắt bằng tiếng Việt	11
Maps of the region	14
Contents	17
1 Introduction	19
1.1 The low-elevation coastal zone: a hub of vulnerability due to climate change	19
1.2 Monitoring the low elevation coastal zone using in situ and satellite measurements	23
1.3 The Surface Water and Ocean Topography satellite mission: a potentially revolutionary altimetry mission	26
1.4 Scientific objectives of this thesis	29
1.5 How to read this thesis	30
2 Assessing typhoon-induced compound flood drivers: a case study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam	33
2.0 Summary and key findings	33
2.1 Article	34
2.2 Conclusion	61
3 Datasets of high-resolution water level and discharge from the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system impacted by a developing megacity, Ho Chi Minh City - Vietnam	63
3.0 Summary and key findings	63
3.1 Introduction to the field campaign	64

3.2 Article	67
3.3 Conclusion	75
4 Operational calibration and performance improvement for hydrodynamic models in data-scarce coastal areas	77
4.0 Summary and key findings	77
4.1 Article	78
4.2 Conclusion	98
5 Enhancing discharge estimation from SWOT satellite data in a tropical tidal river environment	99
5.0 Summary and key findings	99
5.1 Article	100
5.2 S1 Appendix: Figures of study at the H3 location	125
5.3 Conclusion	127
6 Challenging SWOT: early assessment of level 2 high-rate river products in an urbanized, low elevation coastal zone	129
6.0 Summary and key findings	129
6.1 Article	130
6.2 Plots and tables for Water Surface Slope	135
6.3 Conclusion	136
7 Conclusion and Perspectives	139
A Studying the Manning-Strickler Equation for tidal rivers	145
A.1 Water Discharge Estimation	146
A.2 Improving the calibration of parameters using Non-linear Least-Squares curve fitting	146
A.3 Variance-based Sensitivity Analysis (VBSA)	148
A.3.1 Monte Carlo Sampling to perform the VBSA	150
A.4 Results and Discussion	151
B Modelling the Saigon river using C-GEM	155
B.1 C-GEM Hydrodynamics module	155
B.1.1 C-GEM applied to the Saigon river system	157
B.2 Metrics for comparison between experiments	161
B.3 Analysis of Dam and Dongnai boundary conditions	162
B.4 Analysis of the Coastal Boundary Condition	165
B.4.1 Seasonality experiments	165
B.4.2 Storm surge experiments	168
B.5 Experiment seasonality due to Dam	170

1

Introduction

1.1 The low-elevation coastal zone: a hub of vulnerability due to climate change

Since sea level stabilised over 7,000 years ago, humans have used the natural resources and infrastructure of river deltas (Day et al. 2007). Historically, many civilizations thrived along coastlines and river deltas due to the rich food resources from the sea, fertile soils, and strategic locations as transportation hubs, which spurred urban development and economies (Rudd 2008; Kennett et al. 2006). This trend continues today, with some of the world’s most densely populated cities situated on Low-Elevation Coastal Zones (LECZs). These areas are defined as continental or island areas that are hydrologically connected to the sea and lie less than 10 m above sea level (McGranahan et al. 2007). The LECZ encompass a large variety of systems, from small islands to megacities.

In Figure 1.1, the global distribution of LECZs (blue coast lines), major river deltas (green triangles) and coastal megacities (red squares) is presented. The four major archetypes of LECZs are i. urban atoll islands (scattered near coasts and in Polynesia, see black dots in Figure 1.1); ii. arctic communities (northern Russia, western Alaska, and northern Canada); iii. large tropical agricultural deltas (such as the Mekong delta, see orange arrow and circle in Fig. 1.1, and the Ganges–Brahmaputra–Meghna delta) and iv. resource-rich cities (with several cases in the USA, the Netherlands and China). These four coastal archetypes, taken together, provide a picture of the wide variety of coastal settlements around the world (Magnan et al. 2022).

As illustrated in Figure 1.1, LECZs are geographically associated with megacities. A coastal megacity is defined as a city with more than 10 mil-

Figure 1.1: Global distribution of low-lying islands and coasts. The map shows Low Elevation Coastal Zones (coasts <10 m above sea level; blue lines; Source: National Geophysical Data Center, NOAA, <https://data.nodc.noaa.gov/cgi-bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.ngdc.mgg.dem:280>), islands with a maximum elevation of 10 m above sea level (black dots), Small Island Developing States (yellow stars; Source: <http://unohrlls.org/about-sids/>), coastal megacities (>10 million inhabitants, <100 km from the coast, <50 m above sea level; red squares), and major deltas (green triangles). The orange arrow and circle indicate the location of the study area of this work: the Saigon-Dongnai tidal river-estuary around Ho Chi Minh City in South Vietnam. Adapted from Magnan et al. 2022.

lion inhabitants, situated less than 100 km from the coast and at an elevation of less than 50 meters above mean sea level. Currently, approximately 896 million people, nearly 11% of the global population in 2020, reside in LECZs. This number is projected to exceed one billion by 2050 (IPCC 2023).

Coastal megacities face substantial risks from climate change due to their low elevation, climate-sensitive physical and ecological characteristics, and high levels of societal exposure and vulnerability (Magnan et al. 2022). Moreover, approximately 89% of individuals residing in LECZs live within the same latitudinal belt as most tropical cyclone activity. Around 41% of the global population at risk from tropical cyclone-induced flooding reside on river deltas, with 92% of these individuals living in under-developed and developing economies (Edmonds et al. 2020). Additionally, 80% of these populations are located on sediment-starved LECZs, which lack the natural ability to mitigate flooding through sediment deposition. Considering that coastal flooding is expected to intensify, it is crucial to underline that this issue will disproportionately affect populations living on LECZs, particularly in under-developed and developing economies. It is then, of the utmost importance to better understand these estuarine systems especially in intertropical regions.

Figure 1.2: Pictogram showing the main issues affecting low-elevation coastal zones impacted by megacities. Legend: 1) Human pressures. 2) Subsidence. 3) Barrier destruction. 4) Sea level rise. 5) Salinization. 6) Sediment trapping. 7) Erosion. 8) Coastal flooding. 9) River flooding. Adapted from Kronfeld-Goharani et al. 2017.

The main issues affecting LECZs are shown in Figure 1.2. The numbers in Figure 1.2 pertain to the following problems experienced by megacities in LECZs:

1. **Human Pressures:** Coastal development leads to extensive impervious surfaces and pollution.
2. **Subsidence:** Megacities sink due to soil compaction and the extraction of groundwater and other natural resources.
3. **Barrier Destruction:** Expansion of economic activities in coastal cities leads to the destruction of natural barriers such as mangroves.
4. **Sea Level Rise:** Sea level rise threatens to damage infrastructure, submerge low-lying ecosystems, and exacerbate land and water salinization (IPCC 2023).
5. **Salinization:** Increased soil salinization and salt intrusion in rivers.
6. **Sediment Trapping:** Reduced sediment deposits due to upstream dam construction.
7. **Erosion:** Reduced sediment supply leads to increased erosion.

8. **Coastal Flooding:** Storm and cyclone activity heighten flooding incidents. Climate change is expected to increase the frequency and intensity of tropical cyclones (IPCC 2023).
9. **River Flooding:** Intense precipitation, such as monsoons, leads to river flooding and rising water levels. Climate change is projected to cause more frequent and severe rainfall and associated flooding in LECZs (IPCC 2023).

The inherent challenges and risks found in LECZs significantly impact both natural and human environments. Even if the population in LECZs remains unchanged and we ignore future alterations in man-made coastal protection and storm patterns, a 1-meter increase in global sea level could more than double the current population living below the projected annual flood levels (Kulp et al. 2019). Despite this, LECZs are poorly monitored on a global scale (Jérôme Benveniste et al. 2019). To better understand the changes affecting coastal zones and provide essential information for decision-makers involved in environmental risk adaptation and mitigation, comprehensive coastal observations are needed. Information-based solutions, such as early warning systems, have proven effective in reducing flood-related fatalities, especially when combined with structural measures like levees (IPCC 2023). It is therefore crucial to implement observational systems that offer open, free, and reliable data on physical variables in LECZs areas, especially in those which remain ungauged or poorly gauged.

In this thesis, our focus is on the data-scarce, LECZ of Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), located in southern Vietnam. HCMC is a densely populated megacity, with areas in the urban center having up to 30,000 inhabitants per square kilometer. The city is crisscrossed by the tidal Saigon River, comprising a network of about 800 km of watercourses and canals (Ngoc et al. 2016). Due to 90% of HCMC's urban area being impermeable, the hydrological cycle is significantly impacted (Vachaud et al. 2020), leading to frequent flooding from both riverine and rainfall runoff sources (Ho et al. 2014). The situation is exacerbated by an increase in extreme rainfall events, making HCMC highly vulnerable to floods.

This flooding vulnerability is compounded by the several factors mentioned in this chapter but in particular the following:

- Heavy seasonal rainfall brought by the East Asian summer monsoon.
- Ground subsidence, which can be as much as 2 cm per year in certain urban areas (Lossouarn et al. 2016).
- Sea level rise as approximately 65% of the city is situated less than 1.5 meters above sea level (Lossouarn et al. 2016).

HCMC also faces a rapid population growth rate of about 3% per year, and urban expansion at a rate of about 16 km² per year since 2000 (Hanson et al. 2011; Lossouarn et al. 2016). This urban growth increases soil imperviousness, reducing infiltration potential and further heightening flood risks. These factors collectively pose significant threats to the livelihoods of the city’s residents. This coastal megacity is widely recognized as one of the world’s most vulnerable cities to climate change impacts (Lossouarn et al. 2016). Detailed descriptions of the study area will be provided in each chapter, tailored to their relevance in relation to the chapter’s content.

1.2 Monitoring the low elevation coastal zone using in situ and satellite measurements

As discussed in the previous subsection, low-elevation coastal zones are hubs of vulnerability in face of the projected climate change. However, these areas remain relatively under-studied (Jérôme Benveniste et al. 2019), especially in under-developed and developing countries (Chawla et al. 2020).

The LECZ serves as a transition area between terrestrial and marine environments, where the physical phenomena are regulated by the interplay of river discharge and coastal ocean dynamics. To mitigate the risks associated with marine hazards, it is crucial to implement sustained coastal zone monitoring programs, forecasting, and early warning systems (Melet et al. 2020). Achieving a sustainable future for LECZs relies on our ability to monitor both hydrological and oceanographic variables concurrently, to obtain a better understanding of the physics of these systems. This monitoring must encompass different temporal and spatial scales to effectively understand, predict, and manage the evolution of these environments (Laignel et al. 2023).

In this study, we focus on the physical behaviour of the hydro-system in LECZs. To enhance our understanding of LECZ hydrodynamics, two key variables are of interest: river and coastal water levels, and river discharge. A priori, these variables can be effectively monitored using a combination of in-situ and satellite measurements. However, the advantages and disadvantages of these measurement methods vary depending on the specific variable being measured.

Monitoring water levels is essential as it provides insights into both river and coastal-induced flooding, it is needed for design and operation of water structures, policy making, and for the development of water resource management plans (Zaidi et al. 2021). These data can reduce the uncertainties of the decision-making process, particularly in the context of the changing climate. Ideally, effective monitoring of these variables can be achieved through a combination of in-situ gauges and satellite observations. In-situ water level measure-

ments offer the most accurate data with high temporal frequency. However, maintaining long-term water level monitoring can be logistically and financially demanding for any organization. This involves ensuring long-term stability and calibration of measurements, monitoring for possible vertical land movements, conducting quality control, and ensuring proper data archiving (Williams et al. 2020).

Traditional water level measurements require equipment either in the water, like pressure and bubbler systems, or directly above the water, such as radar gauges. Installing and maintaining these in-situ gauges can be particularly challenging in LECZs, especially in megacities. Waterways in megacities are often busy and any type of gauge is susceptible to physical damage, theft, and vandalism. Additionally, natural coastal areas are often difficult to access due to barriers like marshlands, mangroves, lagoons, and other watercourses, complicating the installation and maintenance of monitoring systems. These challenges mean that only the largest and most well-funded projects and organizations can typically afford to install and maintain such systems.

Another crucial hydrodynamic variable for understanding river catchment characteristics and their adaptation to climatic changes is river discharge. Various approaches use the velocity-area method to measure discharge, relying on data about flow velocity and the wetted river cross-section area (Eltner et al. 2020). Established in-situ tools for measuring flow velocities include current meters, acoustic devices such as acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs), and surface velocity radars (Herschy 2014; Welber et al. 2016). These methods provide reliable estimates of river discharge but are labor-intensive, require minimum water depths, or necessitate prolonged measurement periods, making them expensive and time-consuming (Eltner et al. 2020). For these reasons, over the past 30 years, river discharge measurements have significantly declined (Zakharova et al. 2020). For the same reasons as for water level monitoring projects and although many national services continue to monitor key rivers at essential stations, the availability of these observations to the scientific community and for climate research remains limited.

The challenges of in-situ monitoring can be partly mitigated by satellite observations, particularly in ungauged or poorly gauged LECZs. Satellite remote sensing offers the advantage of avoiding the physical challenges associated with in-situ probes. However, these measurements, which depend on the global location of the LECZ under scope, often have lower temporal frequency compared to in-situ measurements. Despite this, long-term satellite missions provide valuable long-term water level time series, archived in spatially semi-continuous gridded formats for ocean water levels and as "virtual stations" for river water levels (Lubczynski et al. 2024). Whereas coastal water level can be used to better understand coastal dynamics, river water levels can be used to

estimate river discharge.

Measuring sea level in coastal zones from space involves dealing with more complex spatial and temporal variability compared to the open ocean (Laignel et al. 2023). In fact, in classical altimetry sea level products, the amount of valid data strongly decrease within 10 to 15 km from the coast (Jérôme Benveniste et al. 2020). Melet et al. 2020 outlines several challenges faced by satellite measurements in coastal zones:

- **Land contamination:** The satellite radar measurement can be compromised by land, making it difficult to retrieve meaningful data very close to the coast, contaminating water level computations.
- **Geophysical corrections:** Coastal areas exhibit greater variability in atmospheric water vapor, temperature, and aerosols compared to the open ocean. These variations can alter the electromagnetic wave propagation and energy spectrum received by the satellite sensor. Additionally, the dynamic nature of coastal oceans, with high spatial and temporal variability and enhanced diurnal changes, requires more complex corrections.
- **Localized coastal hazards:** Coastal hazards, such as marine floods due to cyclones, can be highly localized in space and time (e.g., lasting around one day). This presents sampling issues, as capturing such localized events with satellite observations, which have a revisit time of several days, is unlikely.
- **Geomorphological processes:** Coastal landforms, such as subsidence and topography, exhibit low temporal variability but significant spatial heterogeneity, complicating the measurement process.

Originally developed for sea level monitoring, satellite radar altimetry has also proven valuable for observing river waters, particularly during floods and in water-stressed seasons (Zaidi et al. 2021). It serves as an effective supplement to traditional river monitoring. Altimetry-based water level time series for rivers are typically created at intersections of satellite ground tracks and rivers, known as "virtual" stations. However, the relatively low sampling frequency (10–27 days) of these satellite missions can result in under-sampling hydrological regimes in rivers with events occurring sub-monthly to weekly (Nielsen et al. 2022). In LECZs, river systems usually experience daily tidal fluctuations, leading to significant under-sampling by satellite altimetry. Therefore, while satellite observations are a crucial complement to in-situ monitoring systems, they too present downfalls due to the high variability and complexity of LECZs (Laignel et al. 2023). Despite these challenges, altimetry can provide reliable, regular, and weather-independent measurements of river

water height (Zakharova et al. 2020). The water levels measured by satellite altimetry can be used to derive river discharge, as demonstrated by Tourian et al. 2016, Tarpanelli et al. 2021 and Nielsen et al. 2022. The main methods for estimating discharge using altimetry involve establishing statistical relations or rating curves (RC) between in-situ observations and remotely sensed water heights (Zakharova et al. 2020), or utilizing hydraulic equations with parameters such as width, slope, and height estimated from satellite images (Bonnema et al. 2016).

In-situ coastal and river water level observations and in-situ river discharge observations remain the most effective method for accurate and long-term hydrodynamic studies, while satellite altimetry is well-suited for complementary observations at regional scales. Integrating multiple observation systems is essential for a detailed understanding of the physical behaviour of the LECZ hydrosystem. Enhancing the density of in-situ gauges, along with improving the precision of satellite altimetry, is necessary for more accurate measurements (Adebisi et al. 2021) and thus, for a better management of these systems.

One of the most effective tools for understanding the hydrodynamics of LECZs are numerical models. While these models are data-intensive and computationally demanding, they can provide accurate outputs, particularly when supplied with high-quality input data (Lubczynski et al. 2024). In-situ observations often cover limited areas and are costly. Satellite remote sensing observations, with their freely available, extensive time-series archives but low spatial and temporal resolution can complement in-situ observations. By integrating satellite data with in-situ observations in operational numerical models, a coherent spatiotemporal monitoring of the LECZ can be theoretically achieved. Such integrated systems are crucial for reducing exposure to coastal hazards and related risks (Melet et al. 2020).

1.3 The Surface Water and Ocean Topography satellite mission: a potentially revolutionary altimetry mission

To fully comprehend the dynamics of LECZs and predict their responses to future climate scenarios, it is essential to monitor the interactions between riverine and coastal dynamics. As previously discussed, the scientific community is increasingly interested in complementing in-situ and model data with additional sources of information, such as satellite data, for the hydrodynamic characterization of coastal zones. This interest has given rise to the concept of a coastal hydrology altimetry community, which seeks to address the common interests of both coastal and inland areas (Gómez-Enri et al. 2024). Figure

1.3 summarizes the application of remote sensing technologies in hydrology, particularly focusing on river discharge estimation and how these tools can complement existing monitoring methods.

Figure 1.3: Challenges and opportunities in the field of remote sensing of river discharge. Challenges: The location of Satellite Gauging Reaches (SGR) needs to be known a priori. Reliable estimation of river discharge requires advanced methodologies and sensors, especially to compute river topography. Opportunities: Small-scale remote sensing tools can complement satellites for observing small rivers. Hydrological and hydraulic models complement the monitoring frequency. The novel Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite brings new 2D measurements that, when integrated with current methods, will be of high value for the hydrological community. Adapted from Huang et al. 2024.

As previously discussed, current altimeters face challenges in monitoring rivers due to their low temporal and spatial resolution, typically in the order of tens of days and only at a few locations in a given river. One way to mitigate this limitation is by fusing data from multiple satellites (Chawla et al. 2020). However, most altimeters are designed to monitor the ocean surface and have limitations in coastal and inland river zones. These limitations have historically hindered the study of coastal ocean processes, rivers, and lakes. Despite recent advances in data processing, the geometric properties of altimeter observations, with their one-dimensional spatial extent, complicate the use of radar altimetry for hydrological applications (Le Gac et al. 2021).

The Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite mission, depicted in Figure 1.4, is anticipated to address some of the current challenges of remote sensing river basins. SWOT, a joint mission by NASA and CNES, with contributions from the Canadian Space Agency and the UK Space Agency, was launched in December 2022. Equipped with two SAR antennas separated by a 10-meter mast for interferometry in orbit, SWOT provides the first two-dimensional high-resolution measurements of water levels from space. The

mission’s nominal life is 42 months, including the first 3 months for engineering checkout, 3 months for calibration and validation, followed by a minimum of 36 months for global mapping (Fu et al. 2024).

Figure 1.4: Conceptual depiction of the Surface Water and Ocean Topography mission, highlighting its key instruments: the Ka-band radar interferometer (KaRIn, depicted by yellow polygons representing observed swaths) and a Ku-band nadir altimeter (indicated by a yellow line). The satellite’s size and altitude are not depicted to scale in relation to the background image of South West France sourced from Google Earth, but the ground swaths accurately reflect scale (*background image* Google Earth, Landsat image, data SIO, NOAA, US Navy, NGA, GEBCO). Adapted from Biancamaria et al. 2016.

The SWOT mission will significantly expand measurements of global rivers, providing critical new data sets for both gauged and ungauged basins. SWOT measurements of rivers include river water level, river width, and slope, each invaluable for estimating river discharge. As discussed previously, these hydrodynamic variables are sufficient to characterize the hydraulic regime of a given river. A framework for estimating global river discharge from the SWOT mission is detailed in Durand et al. 2023. SWOT products will provide hydraulic variables for all rivers wider than 100 meters (Biancamaria et al. 2016). However, based on its orbital parameters and designed lifespan, its river discharge observations are limited in both time span and temporal resolution. Integrating SWOT’s river products with long-term, high-frequency discharge estimates obtained from in-situ gauges, hydraulic models, and other satellite

measurements is a question worthy of further research, especially in coastal areas highly vulnerable to climate change. Hence, SWOT's contribution to the body of data in these regions promises a more informed water resource management.

Remote sensing has the potential to democratize essential and new river observing tools, enhancing water security and flood forecasting capabilities. However, while Earth observation through satellites has provided breakthrough scientific advances in understanding river variables globally, it remains challenging to translate knowledge from remote sensing into continuous, valuable information and indicators that can assist decision-makers in supporting water resource governance and related fields (Huang et al. 2024). If remote sensing of river variables can be developed into an operational component of a gauging program, it could augment and economize the current information network and facilitate its expansion into ungauged LECZs.

In this thesis, we evaluate the potential of the SWOT satellite to estimate river discharge for the Saigon River in the complex LECZ of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. This evaluation leverages in-situ measurements and modelling efforts. Each chapter will provide additional details about the SWOT satellite and its capabilities, tailored to the chapter's specific content and relevance.

1.4 Scientific objectives of this thesis

The general objective of this thesis is:

”To achieve a better understanding of the hydrological-to-ocean continuum in the LECZ of the Ho Chi Minh megacity in Southern Vietnam.”

To accomplish this, several sub-objectives have been defined:

1. Contribute to the body of data on the hydrological system surrounding the Ho Chi Minh megacity
2. Implement, calibrate and validate a 1D hydrodynamic model of the Saigon and Dongnai river system traversing the Ho Chi Minh megacity
3. Provide a thorough assessment of the potential of SWOT satellite products to improve discharge estimation in the Saigon river (prior to having access to real SWOT data)
4. Evaluate SWOT river products against in-situ measurements in the Saigon river (once SWOT data available)

These objectives and the research content of this thesis adhere to the following research ethics:

- All scientific publications have been or will be published following open science principles (UNESCO 2021). As such all research outputs of this thesis are distributed online, free of access charges or other barriers.
- All scientific publications have been or will be published by community-managed, not-for-profit scientific publishers except for the contents of chapter 3 (see Haspelmath 2013 for more information on why open-access publication should be nonprofit).
- All measurement data and model outputs will be published in an online repository in open access, following the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) data principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

1.5 How to read this thesis

This thesis follows the french "thesis by articles" format. Each chapter, except for the introduction and conclusion, consists of a scientific article that has been either published or submitted for publication. To ensure coherence, each chapter includes an introductory summary, key findings and a conclusion, connecting the articles into a single, continuous document. Consequently, the main body of each chapter is a standalone article containing its own introduction, literature review, methods and data, results, discussion and conclusion sections.

Chapter 2 offers a comprehensive assessment of the impact of a typhoon that made landfall in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), in 2018. This study builds on data collected during a field campaign between 2017 and 2019, which included water level measurements at two locations in the Saigon River. Additionally, an ensemble of in-situ hydrological data and satellite-derived datasets were analysed to provide a complete picture of the typhoon's impacts, with a particular focus on urban flooding.

Chapter 3 presents the data of a two-month field campaign in HCMC, where high-resolution river water level and discharge measurements were obtained. This campaign was fully conceptualized, managed, and supervised by me, with the assistance of Mr. Tin Nguyen Trung from the Center for Asian Research on Water (CARE).

Chapter 4 details the implementation, calibration, and validation of a 1D hydrodynamic model of the Saigon and Dongnai rivers, highlighting the calibration challenges faced in a data-scarce region. This work was an effort

conducted in close collaboration with Dr. Benoit Camenen of the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE).

Chapter 5 provides a statistical study of the potential of SWOT satellite data to improve discharge estimations in the Saigon River. This study was conducted before the availability of real SWOT data.

Chapter 6 presents an early assessment of real SWOT river products in the challenging environment of the Saigon River.

Chapter 7 concludes the thesis, offering perspectives for future work.

This structure ensures that each chapter functions as an independent scientific contribution while maintaining a cohesive narrative throughout the thesis.

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2

Assessing typhoon-induced compound flood drivers: a case study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

SUMMARY

In this chapter, we analyze the impact of a tropical typhoon on the hydrosystem surrounding Ho Chi Minh City. This analysis offers valuable insights into the hydrology of the Saigon River and its interaction with coastal forces. Additionally, it provides a comprehensive overview of the impact of an extreme event through a combined analysis of in-situ and satellite data. This chapter lays the foundation for the rest of this thesis by presenting a comprehensive view of the hydrodynamics in low-elevation coastal zones and highlighting the necessity of better monitoring to mitigate the impacts of such extreme events, which are expected to increase in frequency and intensity in the future.

KEY FINDINGS

- Typhoon Usagi did not create a significant storm surge but led to extreme rainfall.
- River water level stations showed significant surge from inland drivers like rainfall.
- MSWEP dataset performed best in estimating rainfall during TY Usagi.
- There was a time lag between peak rainfall and peak river discharge, with evidence of widespread flooding upstream of the city.
- A high river spring tide, combined with extreme precipitation, led to prolonged flooding in low-lying areas.
- The Thao Dien ward experienced the highest flood density and depth.
- Coastal tidal forcing was the predominant driver of river discharge even during the event.
- River water levels are controlled by seasonal coastal storm surges caused by the wind pattern of the East Asian summer monsoon.

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Assessing typhoon-induced compound flood drivers: a case study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract. We investigate the most severe rainfall event ever experienced in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), Vietnam. It occurred on 25 November 2018 when Typhoon (TY) Usagi directly hit HCMC. During this event, there was more than 300 mm of rainfall over 24 h which led to flooding and considerable material damage. We propose an in-depth study of TY-induced, compound flood drivers at a short timescale by focusing on the days before and after the event. We use a set of data analysis and signal processing tools to characterize and quantify both coastal and inland effects on the hydrosystem. We found that TY Usagi made landfall without forming a significant storm surge. The extreme rainfall does not translate into immediate river discharge but presents a 16 h time lag between peak precipitation and peak residual discharge. Nevertheless, increased river water levels can be seen at both urban and upstream stations with a similar time lag. At the upstream river station, residual discharge represents 1.5 % of available rainwater, and evidence of upstream widespread flooding was found. At the urban river station, we assess the potential surface runoff during the event to be 8.9 % of the upstream residual discharge. However, a time lag in peak river water level and peak rainfall was found and attributed to the combination of high tide and impervious streets which prevented the evacuation of rainwater and resulted in street flooding of up to 0.8 m. Overall, it was found that despite not having a significant storm surge, the coastal tidal forcing is the predominant compound flood driver even during severe, heavy rainfall with tidal fluctuations in river water level and respective discharge much larger than the residuals.

1 Introduction

Potential impacts of flooding events on low-elevation coastal zones (LECZs) are increasing as populations grow and mean sea levels rise. Instances of flooding within coastal delta areas can arise from various underlying physical factors. These factors encompass storm surges, waves, tides, precipitation and high river discharge (Paprotny et al., 2020). Additionally, the convergence of these elements can lead to flood events known as compound floods, potentially intensifying the overall flood risk (Zscheischler et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2021). In tropical and subtropical regions, the most energetic forcing agents for the coast are storm systems that combine extreme winds with extreme rainfall and that result in severe physical and human damage (Haigh et al., 2014; Gori et al., 2020). Under the impact of global warming and climate change, concerns about such extreme weather events and their local impacts have increasingly been under the scope of scientists and governments (Haigh et al., 2014; Heidarzadeh et al., 2018; Le et al., 2019).

Vietnam lies within the most active cyclogenesis region in the world (Gao et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2021; Klotzbach et al., 2022), and four to six typhoons (TYs) hit the coast every year from October to December (Thuan et al., 2016). TYs are major drivers of compound flooding as they often produce strong onshore winds and low barometric pressure which cause extreme storm surges and simultaneously generate heavy rainfall (Gori et al., 2020; Couasnon et al., 2020). The southern part of Vietnam has generally been per-

ceived to be less vulnerable to TYs compared to other parts of the country. However, a substantial number of TYs have approached southern Vietnam in the past even though the probability of occurrence is smaller than in the northern regions (Takagi et al., 2014). Additionally, a recent study by Wood et al. (2023) simulated 10 000 years of synthetic tropical cyclone activity in the East Sea of Vietnam (also known as the South China Sea) and found that storm surges on both northern and southern Vietnamese coastlines would potentially increase by up to 1 m in the coming decades.

The south of Vietnam consists of a LECZ associated with Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), a mega city with a population density that can reach up to 30 000 inhabitants per square kilometer in the urban city center (Nguyen et al., 2019b) (for comparison, Paris has a density of about 20 000 inhabitants per square kilometer). Water is ubiquitous in HCMC, which is traversed by the tidal river Saigon – a complex system with a network of about 800 km of watercourses and canals (Ngoc et al., 2016). Additionally, 90 % of the urban area of HCMC is impermeable, which leads to strong effects on the hydrological cycle (Vachaud et al., 2020). Furthermore, this leads to recurrent flooding either of riverine origin or by rainfall runoff, which, coupled with an increase in occurrence of extreme rainfall events over HCMC (Ho et al., 2014), makes it one of the most vulnerable coastal regions in the world. In particular, flooding vulnerability is linked to sea level rise, rainfall intensification and ground subsidence, which can reach 0.02 m yr^{-1} (in some geological areas), while 65 % of the city is located less than 1.5 m above sea level (Lossouarn et al., 2016). In addition, HCMC has a population growth rate of about 3 % per year, with these risks posing a threat to many livelihoods. The urban growth rate (about 16 km^2 per year since 2000) is also an important factor as the imperviousness of soils reduces infiltration potential and further increases the flood risk (Hanson et al., 2011; Lossouarn et al., 2016).

On 25 November 2018, HCMC was hit by TY Usagi. According to the forecast department of the Southern Centre for Hydro-Meteorological Forecasting (SCHMF), this was the highest ever recorded rainfall in a 24 h period and caused widespread urban flooding. In Camenen et al. (2021) a monthly evaluation of the Saigon River's response to this extreme rainfall yielded a paradoxical result: a lack of direct response in both river water level and discharge. However, there is a clear interest in better understanding how the hydrosystem physically behaved during and just after this event at finer scales than the monthly average. Additionally, assessing the drivers of the resulting compound flood event over HCMC can provide vital insights for research on coastal and urban flooding prevention.

The presence of concurrent or closely sequential instances of extreme rainfall, extreme river discharge and storm surge can result in extensive destruction, surpassing the impact that these events would have individually (Camus et al., 2021; Eilander et al., 2023; Heinrich et al., 2023). Numerous studies

conducted in recent years have highlighted the significance and highly destructive characteristics of compound flood occurrences connected to TY events across diverse geographical areas (Ye et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021). A frequent approach is to use statistical models such as copula-based analysis (Ai et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2022a) or Monte Carlo approaches (Heinrich et al., 2023) to assess the dependence between TY-induced flood drivers in order to understand the likelihood of co-occurring drivers. Statistical methods generally offer the advantage of requiring relatively moderate computational resources. However, this advantage is counterbalanced by the use of meteorological inputs that frequently lack the necessary spatial resolution in tropical areas to accurately encompass the influences of cyclone activity on storm surge (Cid et al., 2018). Another approach is the application of hydrodynamic model simulations to comprehend the intricate physical interplay among driving factors and their respective significance in influencing the overall flood risk (Gori et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022). Modeling storm surges induced by TYs on a continental or global scale presents a formidable challenge. This is primarily due to the fact that these highly intense storms often possess diameters that fall below the resolution of the model mesh or are attenuated within the broad grid cells of meteorological datasets (Wood et al., 2023). Another downside of modeling approaches is that validation efforts require good-quality field measurements which are hard to obtain in many regions of the world. Furthermore, estuarine regions are areas of active morphological changes, and thus, in situ measurements (such as bathymetry) are dynamic and might not accurately represent reality within a few years' time.

In order to investigate compound flood events within a statistical framework it is ideally necessary to have long time series data (50–100 years) that are both spatially and temporally coherent, encompassing daily river discharge and coastal sea level measurements. Moreover, it is important to note that the availability of daily data varies significantly among rivers, even within regions characterized by relatively good data coverage, and is especially scarce in tropical regions (Wood et al., 2023; Scheiber et al., 2023). These limitations can be partially offset by using model-generated data (Xu et al., 2022a; Heinrich et al., 2023) or satellite data. One example is provided by Zhang and Najafi (2020), who model compound flooding caused by tropical storm Matthew over the small Caribbean island of Saint Lucia. As it is a data-scarce region, there were no in situ records during the event. Thus, they relied on satellite-based inundation images to validate hydrological and hydrodynamic models. However, a sensitivity analysis showed that uncertainties in flooding are significant in areas close to the coast, and thus, a probabilistic approach to understand the chances of flooding is required.

Past studies of compound flood events focus mainly on statistical inter-dependency of rainfall and coastal water levels to provide chances of occurrence, conceptual risk models or inundation maps. Furthermore, conceptual risk mod-

els are defined in a per-case basis and might not be globally applicable. Ai et al. (2018) present a disaster risk model where rain storms and TY surges are assumed to equally affect flood risk. Additionally, the thresholds used to consider precipitation and/or storm surge events as extreme is up to the individual authors, and it depends on the region under scope. Moreover, case studies that focus on synthetic events such as the ones performed by Xu et al. (2022a) and Torres-Freyermuth et al. (2022) do not present a connection between these statistical and model outputs and in situ observations of flood depths and locations usually due to their unavailability. Further, compound flood assessments due to storm surge are usually studied with relation to either rainfall or river discharge, and thus, the combined effects of these two drivers is not investigated.

In this paper, we propose an in-depth assessment of the drivers of compound flooding in this urban estuary region by mainly focusing on in situ observations during the period around TY Usagi. This is done in a data-scarce region where such data are usually hard to obtain or non-existent. Scheiber et al. (2023) were able to set up an urban flood model in HCMC based solely on open-access data. However, there are intrinsic uncertainties and limitations introduced by this type of data in such a model, and thus, their main goal was to provide an estimation of preliminary flood maps for the city rather than deterministic conclusions. Our paper seeks to add a case study based on observations that can help validate future statistical and physical modeling efforts in HCMC and address the growing demand for understanding the combined impacts of different flood drivers in the region. In order to do so, high-resolution in situ measurements of water levels both on the coast and in the river system were gathered and jointly analyzed during an unprecedented extreme event. For these data we applied the harmonic tidal analysis methodology to remove the effect of tides on the water level signal and discern the TY-induced surge both on the coast and also, for the first time, upstream in the tidal river. Additionally, we apply the skewness of surge to determine which flood driver dominates. Furthermore, a modified Manning–Strickler law was used together with the analyzed water level signals to estimate river discharge. Finally, we gather in situ precipitation data and study the performance of several gridded rainfall datasets in estimating the precipitation patterns during TY Usagi. Reported flooding depths and locations are then discussed, taking into account land cover and terrain elevation of the region.

The objectives of this paper are (i) to provide an observation-based, multi-approach methodology to characterize the drivers of compound flooding after an historical TY; (ii) to better understand which of the potential contributors to urban flooding (rainfall runoff, storm surge or river flood) were most relevant during this particular event; and (iii) to characterize how the different parts of the hydrological system (terrain elevation, land cover, precipitation, tidal

river and coastal surge) contribute to the response of the hydrosystem.

In Sect. 2, we introduce the case study by describing and characterizing the study region, HCMC and TY Usagi. Then, Sect. 3 presents the methodologies and data that were used to characterize and quantify the impacts. Results are presented in Sect. 4, discussed in Sect. 5 and followed by a conclusion in Sect. 6.

2 Case Study: Ho Chi Minh City and TY Usagi

HCMC is located in southern Vietnam (Fig. 1) in a LECZ where 65 % of its territory is at an altitude below 1.5 m above mean sea level (a.m.s.l.) (Vachaud et al., 2019). It is characterized by a subtropical monsoon climate with two seasons. The rainy season extends from May to October with a heavy rain period from September to October. The average yearly rainfall over HCMC is 2000 mm, of which about 90 % is received during the wet season (Couasnon et al., 2022; Binh et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2019a). For a given heavy rain event, the precipitation shows a high variability at short spatial scales (on the order of kilometers) with considerable differences from one district to another (Vachaud et al., 2019). Urban flooding due to downpours has a high impact on this megalopolis paralyzing it for several hours (Duy et al., 2017) and can already occur for events starting at 50 mm of accumulated rainfall (Vachaud et al., 2019). Together with heavy precipitation, HCMC is also affected by the combined effects of semi-diurnal tidal waves, with amplitudes reaching a maximum of 4 m (Schwarzer et al., 2016), and high river discharge from the Saigon River (between -1500 and $2000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, where negative discharge represents river flow towards upstream; Camenen et al., 2021). Tidal fluctuations dominate the totality of the river Saigon from the confluence with the Dong Nai River to the outlet of the Dau Tieng reservoir, thus affecting both its water levels and discharge with regular flooding in low-lying urban districts during high spring tides. This flood risk is further exacerbated due to ground subsidence and the possible impacts of upstream dams on sediment trapping (Marchesiello et al., 2019). The Saigon River is a complex river system, subject to several human and environmental interactions before flowing into the Dong Nai River and finally into coastal waters. The Saigon River flows from its source in Cambodia to the Dau Tieng reservoir (270 km² and $1580 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$) before passing through the HCMC megalopolis. In total, it is 225 km long, and its catchment area has a surface of about 4800 km² (Nguyen et al., 2019b).

The watershed is divided into four parts: the upper part (2538 km²) around the Dau Tieng reservoir; the middle part (1840 km²) which extends south from the reservoir, encompasses the first 80 km of the Saigon and crosses it about 2 km north of the Phu Cuong measurement station; the lower part (548 km²) extending down to the urban center and that en-

Figure 1. (a) The estuary of the Saigon–Dong Nai river system (blue). Gray lines represent the complex, natural and artificial canal network of the area. The Saigon River watershed is divided into four sub-catchments: upper, middle, lower and urban. (b) The Ho Chi Minh City center (gray) and the location of surrounding gauges. The water level gauges (orange triangles) were used for the harmonic tidal analysis, and the rainfall gauges (red circles) were used for validation of gridded precipitation datasets. The Pham Van Coi rainfall gauge and the Vung Tau gauge are located outside the spatial extent of (b). The area shown in (b) is represented by the red box in (a). (c) Map of Southeast Asia where the area in red is represented by the red box.

compasses 14 km of river and a complex canal network that flows into it; and, finally, the urban part (211 km²) which encompasses the last, very sinuous 42 km of river, the urban canal network and the Thao Dien measurement station. In the following, we assume that the upper part of the watershed has no direct influence on the river Saigon.

The Saigon River estuary where HCMC is situated borders the East Sea of Vietnam (also known as South China Sea), which is part of the northwest Pacific Ocean, one of the most active TY basins in the world with about 30 % of the world's annual tropical storms occurring in this region (Trinh et al., 2020). On average, about four to six TYs affect the Vietnam coast (Thuy, 2003; Thuy et al., 2016) annually. The expected increase in the number and intensity of TYs due to climate change (Lin et al., 2012), combined with the low elevation and high population density of HCMC, makes it one of the most vulnerable cities to be impacted by TYs. In addition, the heavy rains and extreme high water levels associated with TYs aggravate the already high flood risk in the city. In this paper, we focus on one of the most severe rainfall events that this city has ever experienced. It occurred in November 2018, when TY Usagi hit HCMC. During this event, there was more than 300 mm in rainfall over 24 h, which led to flooding and considerable material damage.

TY Usagi was a tropical cyclone that affected the Philippines and southern Vietnam in late November 2018, causing severe damage around the Visayas region (Philippines) and HCMC. The storm formed from a disturbance in the Central Pacific basin on 3 November and developed into a tropical

storm (TS) 3 weeks later, on 13 November. Usagi underwent rapid intensification and peaked in intensity before making its final landfall on the coastal city of Vung Tau just south of HCMC as a weakening tropical storm on 25 November. In Fig. 2 the track of TY Usagi near HCMC is shown using the lowest pressure as indicator. The Joint Typhoon Warning Center (JTWC) assessed its intensity to be equivalent to Category 2 status on the Saffir–Simpson scale. On 25 November, the JTWC downgraded Usagi from a TY to a tropical storm as central convection weakened. Usagi made landfall on Vung Tau, Vietnam, at 07:00 UTC as a tropical storm, with the JTWC downgrading Usagi to a tropical depression later that day.

3 Methods and data

The impact of a TY on compound floods in an estuarine system can be separated into inland and coastal drivers (Fig. 3), the first in the form of rainfall runoff, infiltration, and exfiltration influenced by topography and land use and the second in the form of storm surges.

In order to characterize the impact of TY Usagi on the tidal river system, the following general steps are applied (Fig. 3) and explained in detail in the following sections. We start by selecting a collection of data representative of the factors influencing the impact of a TY. Different gridded precipitation products are evaluated against in situ measurements to enable a high-temporal- and high-spatial-resolution study of the precipitation pattern during Usagi. We study to-

Figure 2. (a) The track of TY Usagi and Ho Chi Minh City (pink). (b–d) ERA5 10 m wind fields from 23 November 2018 at 00:00 UTC to 25 November 2018 at 00:00 UTC.

pography and land use maps, together with the obtained precipitation time series. Additionally, urban flood reports are mapped and analyzed in order to form a holistic overview of TY-induced compound flooding before, during and after the event. We then process in situ water level measurements using harmonic analysis to obtain the astronomical tide and the residual water level. Furthermore, the skew surge is computed in order to quantify the storm surge and river surge effect on flooding. Then, these signals are used to estimate the discharge of the river Saigon throughout the event. Lastly, the mapping and characterization step encompasses the analysis of the different sources of information and results in order to characterize the impact of this TY on compound flooding in HCMC and upstream of HCMC and clarify the interaction between the different drivers.

3.1 Performance evaluation of gridded datasets of precipitation over HCMC

The accuracy of five gridded satellite precipitation datasets was evaluated against in situ measurements. In order to match the location of observations and dataset pixels, the precipitation values of the datasets were spatially interpolated to the location of ground observations using the bilinear interpolation method (Gaborit et al., 2013; Ang et al., 2022). Additionally, we match the temporal resolution of the datasets and the observations such that an evaluation can be made.

Given the time frame of the heavy precipitation event which started on 24 November and ended on 26 November, we chose the cumulative precipitation over 3 d as the adequate time resolution for the period of available observed precipitation data (2016–2018). Additionally, using the 3 d

Figure 3. Framework to characterize and study the compound flood drivers brought by TY Usagi on the estuarine system. All typhoon-related phenomena that influence coastal dynamics (such as storm surge and wind) are referred to as “coastal” effects. Typhoon-related phenomena influencing the hydrology (precipitation, surface runoff, river discharge, flooding) are referred to as “inland” effects.

total instead of a daily total mitigates some daily gaps in the in situ data. The evaluation was performed over nine rain gauge locations chosen based on the availability of the data. Some of the rain gauges presented data gaps of several weeks and were not used for the study. Only rain gauges with more than 450 daily measurements during the selected period (about 3 years) were used. This number of measurements was chosen given that during the 6 months of the dry season HCMC experiences very few rainy days.

The evaluation was carried out using three statistical indicators: mean bias error (MBE), root mean square error (RMSE) and correlation coefficient (R). These indicators have been widely used in the literature for this purpose (Xiang et al., 2021; Ang et al., 2022). MBE is a statistical assessment of the mean difference between the interpolated and observed rainfall, and RMSE represents the standard deviation between the dataset and the observations. Lower absolute values of MBE and RMSE indicate the better performance of the gridded dataset. R measures the degree of linear correlation between the gridded and observed datasets. Higher values of R indicate the higher accuracy of the product in estimating precipitation. The equation, range and optimal value of each index are presented in Table 1.

3.2 Ground-based and satellite precipitation datasets

Table 2 summarizes the precipitation datasets and observations used in this study. Gridded precipitation products can be classified into three categories based on differ-

ences in the data sources and retrieval models including gauge-interpolated, satellite-based and reanalysis precipitation datasets (Jiang et al., 2021). Satellite-based datasets use polar-orbiting passive microwave (PMW) sensors on low-Earth-orbiting satellites and geosynchronous infrared (IR) sensors on geostationary satellites to estimate precipitation (Larson and Peck, 1974; Kidd and Huffman, 2011). Often these datasets offset their limited abilities by blending rain gauge data with their measurements (Mizukami and Smith, 2012). Reanalysis-related datasets generate several meteorological variables with a consistent spatial and temporal resolution by assimilating observations such as weather stations, satellites, ships and buoys based on different climate models. In this analysis five datasets that belong to the four categories were chosen in order to examine their different performances over HCMC. All datasets that were used are freely available online via public repositories.

3.2.1 Global Precipitation Climatology Centre (GPCC) dataset

The GPCC provides the largest gauge-based dataset product derived from quality-controlled station data sourced from national meteorological and hydrological services, global and regional data collections, and WMO Global Telecommunication System (GTS) data. This GPCC product is recommended to be used when the daily precipitation information is of highest importance, e.g., for analyses of extreme events and related statistics at daily resolution. Despite its low spa-

Table 1. Equations and optimal values of statistical indices. P_i and O_i denote predicted and observed values, respectively, of precipitation on the i th day. $cov(P, O)$ denotes the covariance between the predicted and observed values.

Indices	Equation	Range	Optimal values
Mean bias error	$MBE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - O_i)$	$-\infty$ to ∞	0
Root mean square error	$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - O_i)^2}$	0 to ∞	0
Correlation coefficient	$R = \frac{cov(P, O)}{sp.sO}$	-1 to 1	1

Table 2. Overview of the precipitation data used in this study. The categories are indicated as follows: gauge-based data (G), satellite-based data (S), reanalysis data (R) and in situ data.

Name	Variable	Category	Temporal/spatial resolution	Temporal coverage	Reference
GPCC	Rainfall	G	Daily/1.0°	1982–2019	Ziese et al. (2020)
CMORPH v1.0	Rainfall	S	3 hourly/0.25°	1998–2021	Joyce et al. (2004)
MSWEP v2.0	Rainfall	G, S, R	3 hourly/0.25°	1979–2021	Beck et al. (2019b)
ERA5	Rainfall	R	Hourly/0.5°	1979–2021	Munoz-Sabater et al. (2021)
IMERG	Rainfall	S	3 hourly/0.1°	2000–2021	Huffman et al. (2019)
Urban rain gauges	Rainfall	In situ	daily/n/a	2016–2018	HCMUDC – HOS

n/a: not applicable.

tial resolution, the GPCC product was chosen as the gauge-based dataset since it is recommended for analyses of extreme events and related statistics at daily resolution (Jiang et al., 2021).

3.2.2 Climate Prediction Center MORPHing technique (CMORPH) dataset

This product consists of satellite precipitation estimates that have been bias corrected and reprocessed using the CMORPH to form a global, high-resolution precipitation analysis at very high spatial and temporal resolution. We chose this product due to its advection scheme of cloud features and wide range of applications including hydrological studies and extreme event analysis (Joyce et al., 2004).

3.2.3 Multi-Source Weighted-Ensemble Precipitation (MSWEP)

MSWEP is a global precipitation product which incorporates daily gauge observations and accounts for gauge reporting times to reduce temporal mismatches between satellite reanalysis estimates and gauge observations. It was chosen for the study because it merges gauge, satellite and reanalysis data to obtain precipitation estimates. MSWEP has demonstrated higher overall accuracy than other widely used precipitation products in both densely gauged and ungauged regions (Beck et al., 2017, 2019a). Beck et al. (2019b) provide a detailed description of the MSWEP V2.2 methodology.

3.2.4 European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Re-Analysis product (ERA5)

The ERA5 product is the fifth-generation atmospheric reanalysis to replace ERA-Interim produced by ECMWF. It assimilates observations from over 200 satellite instruments and types of conventional data and information on rain rate from ground-based radar–gauge composite observations. Even though ERA5 has shown stronger data deviations than bias-corrected satellite-based precipitation datasets (Islam and Cartwright, 2020), it was chosen since it can capture the spatial distribution of TY precipitation centers (Jiang et al., 2021).

3.2.5 Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for Global Precipitation Measurement (IMERG)

The IMERG product combines information from the Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) satellite constellation to estimate precipitation over the majority of the Earth’s surface. The product fuses the early precipitation estimates collected during the operation of the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) satellite (2000–2015) with more recent precipitation estimates collected during the operation of the GPM satellite (2014–present). IMERG was chosen given that it generally shows high accuracy and good performance in hydrological simulations when compared to the ground observations (Ang et al., 2022), as well as its good capability in extreme rainfall events applications

(Huang et al., 2019).

3.2.6 Rain gauge observations

We use daily rainfall data from nine rain gauges located in and around the city center of HCMC as shown in Fig. 1a and b. These data were provided by the Ho Chi Minh Urban Drainage Company (HCMUDC) and the Hydrometeorological Observatory – Southern Region (HOS) for the period from 1 May 2016 to 30 November 2018.

3.3 Harmonic tidal analysis

The Saigon River discharge is highly influenced by the mixed, semi-diurnal tidal cycle and presents a relatively low net discharge (Nguyen et al., 2019b, 2020; Camenen et al., 2021) which is 1 order of magnitude lower than the instantaneous discharge. The water level time series are highly influenced by the tidal signal, making it difficult to access the impact of TY Usagi on both river and coastal water levels. It is thus important to process and filter out the tidal component from observed time series. According to Cid et al. (2017), we first remove the average water level variability from the water level time series by subtracting the monthly moving average. Then, we follow the methodology proposed by Pugh and Woodworth (2012) to produce the tidal signal via classical harmonic analysis to extract information on the amplitude and phase of the tidal constituents. Classical harmonic analysis has been developed and widely used to analyze and predict tides (Jin et al., 2018; Trinh et al., 2020; Couasnon et al., 2022). The UTide package developed by Codiga (2011) and implemented in Python by Bowman (2020) was used for extracting the tidal constituents. This package provides harmonic analysis with up to 146 tidal constituents. We use all available constituents for our tidal prediction. However, we exclude the constituents whose harmonic constants usually include mostly quasi-periodic meteorological effects (Mm, MSf, Mf, Sa, Ssa, S1). Excluding these long-term constituents from the analysis avoids over-fitting the tidal prediction with frequencies that capture non-astronomical effects on water level such as wind, temperature and atmospheric pressure (Parker, 2007). Additionally, the upstream location of the river sensors justifies the use of constituents produced by nonlinear mechanisms in shallow water. These mechanisms alter the characteristics of the tidal waves and may include the effect of bottom friction, standing wave generation or local resonances due to interactions with varying topography (Pugh, 2004). Hence, we use a total number of 140 constituents.

In order to obtain the non-tidal effects on water level we compute the difference between the observed water level and the predicted tide, i.e., the residual signal.

3.4 Skew surge

The residual signal at the sea level gauge of Vung Tau (Fig. 1a) presents sporadic peaks and troughs due to small shifts in tidal phase. This is a common challenge in tide prediction analysis in systems with large tidal amplitudes, which is the case here (Williams et al., 2016; Calafat and Marcos, 2020; Couasnon et al., 2022). Hence, in addition to the residual signal, we look at the skew surge which represents the excess water level over the high tide. This metric has seen relevant applications in several coastal flooding studies (Williams et al., 2016; Haigh et al., 2016; Couasnon et al., 2022).

3.5 Water level data

Time series data at 10 min intervals were obtained from a 2-year measurement campaign (2017–2018) directed by the Centre Asiatique de Recherche sur l'Eau (CARE). Measurements were performed using CTD-Diver sensors at two locations: Phu Cuong and Thao Dien as shown in Fig. 1. Phu Cuong and Thao Dien are located at about 137 and 60 km from the coast (along river), respectively. In Camenen et al. (2021) the quality of these measurements has been validated against data from the Center of Environmental Monitoring (CEM) of Vietnam. These data are complemented by the record at the Vung Tau tide gauge from the research quality dataset available through the Joint Archive for Sea Level of the NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (Caldwell et al., 2015). A statistical description of these datasets can be found in Table C1 in Appendix C. The stations of Phu Cuong, Thao Dien and Vung Tau depicted in orange in Fig. 1 will also be referred to as the upstream, urban and coastal stations, respectively.

3.6 River discharge estimation

The instantaneous river discharge was estimated by applying a stage-fall-discharge (SFD) rating curve adapted from the general Manning–Strickler law (Eq. 1), previously tested and validated by Camenen et al. (2017) and used to predict the total discharge of the Saigon River in Camenen et al. (2021):

$$Q(t) = \text{sign}(S) \cdot K \cdot A_w(t) \cdot R_h(t)^{2/3} \cdot \sqrt{|S(t + dt)|}, \quad (1)$$

with Q the river discharge [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$], $K = 27.06 \text{ m}^{1/3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ the Manning–Strickler coefficient, $R_h = A_w/P_w$ the hydraulic radius [m], A_w the wet section [m^2], and P_w the wet perimeter [m]. Note that A_w and P_w are both a function of the water level and thus of time. The term $\text{sign}(S)$ is equal to the sign of the slope, S , taking the value of +1 or –1. The energy slope, S [–], is assumed to equal the water slope and is computed as

$$S = \frac{H_{\text{up}} - H_{\text{dn}} + dH}{L}, \quad (2)$$

with the water level H_{up} and H_{dn} measured at Phu Cuong (PC) and Thao Dien (TD), respectively, and L the distance between the two locations. We use the term “water level (H)” to refer to the height of the column of water above the pressure gauges in the river. The tidal oscillations are propagated from the coastal tide gauge to the river gauges. Since there is no fixed datum between river and tide gauges, we normalize all signals by mean removal. This makes the tidal harmonics oscillate around zero for all gauge locations, thus making them comparable. In addition, the dH parameter in Eq. (2) provides an additional calibration parameter that helps mitigate this problem. The term dt is a time lag required to account for the propagation of the tidal wave between one location and the other. The full observed water levels at Phu Cuong and Thao Dien were used to compute the total discharge of the Saigon River. The predicted tidal signals obtained via harmonic tidal analysis at these stations were used to compute the discharge due solely to tidal fluctuations. Then, the tidal discharge is subtracted from the total discharge in order to obtain a residual discharge – the discharge due to non-tidal effects.

In Camenen et al. (2021), the model calibration is done using two acoustic Doppler current profiler (ADCP) campaigns: (i) March 2017 during an asymmetric tide and (ii) September 2016 during a symmetric tide. During the asymmetric tide the equation has much more difficulty following the discharge measurements than during the symmetric tide. The parameters to be calibrated are the following:

- K , the Manning–Strickler coefficient of the river reach, is a measure of channel roughness or friction and is assumed constant.
- dt is a time lag required to account for the propagation of the tidal wave between the downstream location and the upstream location.
- dH is used to compensate for the fact that the reference points of each location are different and unknown.

The parameters K , dt and dH are calibrated one at a time to optimize the root mean square error (RMSE), which provided good results. However, in this study we improve this calibration by using a nonlinear least-squares fitting technique (not presented here). The optimal parameter values found for this study were $dH = -0.149$ m and $dt = -2$ h. This calibration method yielded better results for the estimation of discharge than in Camenen et al. (2021). We improve the RMSE of total discharge during an asymmetric tide from $350 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $185 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ using $K = 27 \text{ m}^{1/3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $dt = 2$ h and $dH = -0.15$ m. Additionally, statistical information about the estimated discharge can be found in Table C3 in Appendix C.

3.7 Other data

Table 3 summarizes all other data used in this study, namely water level, flood reports, topography and land use. In the following sub-sections more information about these datasets is put forward.

3.7.1 Topography

The topography maps were obtained from the NASA Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) 90 m Digital Elevation Database. The SRTM mission has provided digital elevation model (DEM) data for over 80 % of the globe. These data are currently distributed free of charge by USGS and are available for download from the National Map Seamless Data Distribution System or the USGS FTP site. The vertical error in the DEMs is reported to be less than 16 m (Farr et al., 2007). The SRTM vertical datum is global mean sea level and is based on the WGS84 Earth Gravitational Model (EGM 96) geoid (EROS, 2018). Throughout the paper when using the term “mean sea level” we refer to the global mean sea level used as datum for the SRTM data.

3.7.2 Land use

The land use map of the region around HCMC was obtained from the Large-scale Land-Use Land-Cover (LULC) website (https://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/ALOS/en/dataset/lulc/lulc_vnm_v2109_e.htm, last access: 31 October 2023). LULC information was derived using a random-forest-based algorithm and several geospatial data sources, including Landsat, Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery (Phan et al., 2021). The final product contains annual land cover information from 1990 to 2020 in Vietnam at a 30 m resolution. These data are independently validated with field surveys and visual interpretation data. The overall accuracy of the level-1 layer ranges from 86 % to 92 %.

3.7.3 Wind

A storm surge is produced by water being pushed onshore by the force of cyclonic winds. The impact on surge of the low pressure associated with intense storms is minimal in comparison to the water being forced toward the shore by the wind (NOAA, 2023). Additionally, many other factors, such as angle of approach of the TY, radius of maximum winds and the slope of the continental shelf, may also have an influence (Sebastian et al., 2019). Storm size also significantly contributes to the generation of storm surge (Trinh et al., 2020) and provides an indication of the spatial region influenced by the TY. Larger TYs create higher storm surges and coastal inundation (Orton et al., 2015). Therefore, we use the wind field to determine wind direction and the size of TY Usagi (Fig. 2). ERA5 outputs for 10 m u and v wind components were used to map the approach of TY Us-

agi towards the southern coast of Vietnam. These data are provided free of charge from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu>, last access: 31 October 2023) with an hourly resolution and global grid of 0.25° for the period 1959 to the present (Hersbach et al., 2020).

3.7.4 Flood data

Urban flood reports for 25 November 2018 were provided by the DECIDER project (<https://www.decider-project.org>, last access: 31 October 2023) and were originally obtained from the former Steering Center for Flood Control (SCFC) in HCMC. These include coordinates of flooded streets and corresponding flood height. Additionally, a flood map based on manufacturing firms' reports was obtained from Leitold et al. (2021).

4 Results

4.1 Assessment of precipitation products

The results of all statistical indices (RMSE, MBE and R) for each station are presented in Fig. 4. The worst performing dataset over this domain is ERA5 with large values of RMSE and MBE (both > 100 mm per 3 d) and low linear correlation ($R \leq 0.4$). This indicates that ERA5 is overestimating rainfall over the whole domain. The ERA5 dataset that was evaluated has a 0.5° grid which is not capable of capturing the precipitation patterns over HCMC. The other gridded products perform relatively well in stations within the city center ($20 \leq \text{RMSE} < 50$; $-20 \leq \text{MBE} < 50$ mm per 3 d). This indicates that all datasets, with the exception of ERA5, are able to estimate rainfall patterns over HCMC. The gauge-based dataset GPCC is able to do so with the most coarse grid: a daily temporal window and spatial resolution of 1° . Even though CMORPH presents a sophisticated advection scheme (0.25°), its performance is similar to the higher-spatial-resolution IMERG (0.1°) across all metrics. Additionally, the performance of MSWEP (0.25°) is slightly better than CMORPH over the city center. However, this better performance can also be attributed to the incorporation of in situ data in addition to the satellite data used to produce MSWEP. Nonetheless, this shows that a grid size of 0.25° suffices to estimate rainfall over HCMC using hybrid measurements sourced from satellites and in situ data.

The degree of linear correlation between all datasets and rainfall gauges is always below 0.7 for almost all stations. MSWEP shows higher values of R ($0.4 \leq R < 0.7$) than all other datasets. In fact, all other datasets show very low values of R ($R < 0.5$), indicating that these datasets have a weak linear relationship with the observed daily data. The main factor contributing to the difficulty in accurately portraying the precipitation over HCMC is the convective pattern of precipitation events leading to the non-uniform distribution of rain

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of root mean square error (left), mean bias error (middle) and correlation coefficient (right) between five gridded products and gauged observations at daily timescale during 2015–2018. The circles denote rainfall gauging stations located in and around the Ho Chi Minh City area (light gray). The Saigon–Dong Nai system is represented in dark gray.

at the scale of the city (Vachaud et al., 2019). It can happen that it rains heavily in one district, whereas in another it does not rain at all. The spatial resolution of all datasets (always at least $\geq 0.1^\circ$) remains too coarse to accurately capture the spatial variability during rainfall events. Additionally, this evaluation is undertaken at the relatively high timescale of the day against scarce in situ measurements (both in time and space), which has an impact on the performance of the datasets.

Overall, MSWEP is the dataset that better represents the precipitation patterns over HCMC by either showing similar metrics or outperforming other datasets especially in coefficient of correlation, R . In order to further validate this dataset, the performance metrics (RMSE, MBE and R) were computed for the month of November 2018 on a daily time step. In Fig. 5 the precipitation products are plotted against

Table 3. Overview of water level, flood reports, topography and land use data used in this study. The categories are indicated as follows: gauge-based data (G), satellite-based data (S), reanalysis data (R) and in situ data.

Name	Variable	Category	Temporal/spatial resolution	Temporal coverage	Reference
ERA5	10 m wind	R	Hourly/0.25°	22–27 Nov 2018	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Tide gauge	Sea level	In situ	Hourly/n/a	2007–2021	Caldwell et al. (2015)
Urban river gauge	Water level	In situ	10 min/n/a	2017–2018	Camenen et al. (2021)
Flood reports	Location and flood depth	Report	n/a/n/a	25 Nov 2018	SCFC
Flood reports 2	Location	Report	n/a/n/a	25 Nov 2018	Leitold et al. (2021)
SRTM DEM	Elevation	S	n/a/90 m	n/a	Farr et al. (2007)
Land use	Land use	S	Yearly/30 m	2018	Phan et al. (2021)

n/a: not applicable.

the available rain gauge data (in gray bars). The extreme rainfall brought by TY Usagi on 25 November 2018 is clearly seen in both rainfall gauge and datasets. For this period the rain gauge data are scarce with three out of nine stations not having any measurements, namely Pham Van Coi, Thanh Da and Cau Bong. Additionally, the stations that present measurements have important data gaps. All datasets with the exception of ERA5 underestimate rainfall during Usagi. ERA5 (brown curve in Fig. 5) overestimates it with values above 500 mm for the day that Usagi made landfall. However, for the presented rainfall gauge measurements MSWEP (in light blue) seems to capture the precipitation behavior during TY Usagi better than all other datasets (Table B1 in Appendix B). For MSWEP, the average statistics over the month of November 2018 and over all stations for RMSE, MBE and R are 7.6, -4.3 mm d^{-1} and 0.6, respectively.

4.2 Statistical analysis of data and characterization of TY Usagi

In this section we perform a seasonal statistical overview of water level, discharge and precipitation. Additionally, we quantify the effect of TY Usagi on these hydrological variables in comparison to seasonal variations. The boxplots referring to these data are presented in Fig. 6. The x axis for the water levels are separated into the direct measurement (referred to as “observed”), the tidal signal predicted via harmonic tidal analysis (“tidal”), the signal without tidal influence (“residual”) and the computed skew surge (“skew surge”). Similarly, for the discharge computed at Phu Cuong the estimations are divided into “observed”, “tidal” and “residual”.

4.2.1 Seasonal patterns

Predicted tide

As can be seen in Fig. 6a, b and c, the predicted tide signal presents no seasonality, as its average, median and interquartile range do not vary between wet and dry season. However, the tidal signal changes from Vung Tau on the coast towards upstream at Phu Cuong on the river Saigon. The whiskers in the boxplots decrease in size from coast to upstream, which means that tidal amplitude decreases. We verify a decreasing tidal amplitude from 3.9 m (4 m) on the coast to 3.1 m (3.2 m) at the urban city center and to 2.7 m (2.5 m) upstream during the wet (dry) season. This is equivalent to a decrease in tidal amplitude of 8 mm per along-river kilometer between the coast and the city center and of 11 mm per along-river kilometer between the city center and upstream of HCMC. It can also be seen that negative water levels can reach greater values in modulus than positive water levels. This is due to the low tides that are very low during spring tidal cycles, as illustrated in Fig. 7a. Additionally, the size of the boxes decreases upstream, which indicates the data are less spread in the river than on the coast, as the interquartile range (IQR) is smaller. Furthermore, the box is closer to the higher values of water level at all stations. Hence, the probability density function of the tide is skewed towards higher values. This is due to the asymmetric nature of the tide with cycles where low tide is not as pronounced and the lowest water level differs by less than 1 m from the neighboring high tides (see Fig. 7a).

Observed water levels

The observed water level signals show average water levels that are higher than the tide prediction during the dry season and lower during the wet season. This behavior is counter intuitive from a hydrological point of view where water levels are strongly connected to seasonal rains. This seasonality

Figure 5. The five precipitation products compared to the six rain gauges with available observations for the month of November 2018. The peak of precipitation during TY Usagi is best captured by MSWEP (light blue), whereas the other datasets either underestimate or overestimate it. ERA5 (brown) presents estimations above 500 mm. The high spatial variability over the city makes it hard to obtain accurate results at all stations simultaneously.

Figure 6. Boxplots of water level (observed signal, tidal prediction, residual signal and skew surge) for the upstream station of Phu Cuong (a), the urban station of Thao Dien (b) and the coastal station of Vung Tau (c). Boxplots of estimated discharge (using observed water level signals, tidal prediction and residual signals) for Phu Cuong (d). Boxplots of daily cumulative precipitation averaged over the spatial extent of the upper, middle, lower and urban parts of the watershed (e). Each variable on the x axis has two boxplots corresponding to wet (left) and dry (right) seasons. A legend of the boxplots is provided in the bottom right corner: the box extends from the first quartile (Q1) to the third quartile (Q3), and the whiskers extend from the box by 1.5 times the interquartile range ($IQR = Q3 - Q1$). Extreme values for TY Usagi are reported in red (max) and blue (min) horizontal bars and correspond to the time window from 24 to 26 November 2018. The time period of the data presented here corresponds to the temporal coverage in Tables 2 and 3.

pattern in the coastal water levels is in line with Trinh et al. (2020), and it propagates upstream as shown in Camenen et al. (2021). This clarifies that river water levels are interconnected with seasonal coastal storm surges caused by the wind pattern of the East Asian summer monsoon, typically from November to April (Marchesiello et al., 2020). Thus, the monsoon wind passes over precipitation effects on the Saigon River.

Residual water levels and skew surge

For both seasons we expect the same behavior as the observed time series and thus higher average residuals in the dry season than in the wet season. The difference in average residual between seasons is 24 cm on the coast, 26 cm at the urban center and 18 cm at the upstream station. As for the seasonal difference in average skew surge we find 19 cm on the coast, 23 cm at the urban center and 17 cm at the upstream station. These results show that at the urban center we have consistently higher surges than on the coast or upstream, which indicates that the surrounding highly urbanized land cover and complex canal system are playing a role in the water levels at this location. Additionally, both residual signals and skew surge take on more negative values in the wet season as all values below the upper quartile (Q3) are negative. The inverse is seen for the dry season as all values above the first quartile (Q1) are positive. This behavior is due to the difference in tidal and observed water levels. Observed water levels are lower than predicted in the wet season leading to negative average residuals and skew surge and vice versa for the dry season. This further justifies a seasonal surge in the river due to a seasonal surge on the coast.

Discharge

The estimated discharge boxplots (Fig. 6d) show similar discharge due to tides during both seasons. However, the observed discharge differs from the wet to the dry season. The dry season tidal discharge is similar to the observed discharge on average, its median and its IQR. However, the observed discharge signal presents longer whiskers and thus higher discharge values with observed discharge between -1604 and $2492 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ versus -1500 and $1500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the tidal discharge. This means that in the dry season tides are the main driver for discharge in the Saigon, and less frequent but higher values occur due to other factors. Such factors include the outlier precipitation events during the dry season (see Fig. 6e). On the other hand, the wet season average and median discharge are, respectively, 168 and $217 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ higher than for the tidal discharge. The larger observed discharge in the wet season could be attributed to the more intense rainfall during this period: the average wet season daily rainfall is 22 mm against 5 mm in the dry season averaged over the full watershed (Fig. 6e). As a result, the average residual discharge in the wet season is larger and the distribution is more

spread (larger IQR) than in the dry season. This translates to an average residual discharge of $180 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the wet season and $72 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the dry season.

Rainfall

In Fig. 6e, a clear increase in rainfall from the dry to the wet season can be seen over the whole watershed as expected. We see a lot of outlier events in both seasons with the dry season sometimes having exceptionally high-rainfall events that are well above the average even for the more rainy wet season. The increased wet season rainfall seems to not change the water levels at the seasonal timescale. This is because we have a clear increase in rainfall in the wet season but a decrease in water levels over the two river stations. This shows that the coastal water level is the main driver of river water levels and not rainfall over the whole extension of the Saigon River. On the other hand, we see a slight increase in discharge during the wet season.

4.2.2 Effect of TY Usagi (24–26 November 2018)

Water levels

From Fig. 6c, it can be seen that TY Usagi occurred during a large-amplitude spring tide (see also Fig. 7) with a low tide below Q1 of the tidal levels on the coast. At this location both residual water level and skew surge are within the IQR for the dry season. Hence, one can infer that the storm surge on the coast was not statistically significant when compared with the distribution of values during this season. Furthermore, the maximum coastal residual water level and skew surge were 19 and 14 cm, respectively, which corresponds to 5 and 1 cm above the respective dry season averages. At the urban city center (Fig. 6b) the skew surge is close to being an outlier with a value of 31 cm, which is 22 cm above the seasonal average. The residual signal maximum would be an outlier in the wet season, and in the dry season it is above Q3 with a value of 32 cm, which is 20 cm above the seasonal average. Finally, at the upstream station the skew surge due to Usagi is less statistically significant than at the city center with a value of 23 cm, which is above Q3. However, the residual signal is stronger at this location than at the city center with a value of 44 and 33 cm above the seasonal average.

Discharge

The Usagi impact seems to have brought about higher discharge at the upstream location of Phu Cuong than usual. The discharge peak sits well above Q3 for the wet season and is a clear outlier for the dry season. The peak discharge during Usagi was $413 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which corresponds to $233 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ above the average of the wet season. It can also be seen that there have been higher discharges in the wet season during the period of these data, even though it is clearly an outlier discharge for the dry season.

Figure 7. Result for tide prediction at the river stations – Phu Cuong (black) and Thao Dien (gray) – and the coastal station Vung Tau (blue). Time series of the full observed signal (a), the tidal prediction (b), the residual (c) obtained by subtracting the tidal prediction from the observed signal and the skew surge (d). For the sake of readability, the signals in (a) and (b) are displaced by 3 m and the signals (c) and (d) by 1 m. Additionally, the vertical red line represents the time of landfall of TY Usagi at Vung tau.

Rainfall

In Fig. 6e it is confirmed that the rainfall brought by Usagi constituted the maximum daily rainfall in this data series for both wet and dry seasons. On the day of the landfall (25 November 2018), it rained on average 227 mm over the upper part, 285 mm over the middle part, 274 mm over the lower part and 270 mm over the urban part of the watershed (see Fig. 1).

4.3 Coastal driver: storm surge effect on river dynamics

The results from the harmonic tidal analysis are presented in Fig. 7 for the period of 1 month around the Usagi event. Additionally, a statistical description of the residual water level signal can be found in Table C2 in Appendix C. The predicted tide shows a mixed semi-diurnal character for the

three stations (Fig. 7b). The observed time series of water level (Fig. 7a) illustrates how the tidal wave propagates from the coast at Vung Tau to the upstream river stations. The tidal forcing is dominant along the river system and even throughout the Usagi event where no direct impact can be observed on the water level time series. This is expected (see Sect. 4.2) and further certifies that the Saigon River's hydrodynamics are mainly controlled by tidal forcing.

A clear anomaly during the event can be seen when using the harmonic tidal analysis methodology to obtain a water level without tidal influence (namely, the residual water level; Fig. 7c). Both river stations present an increase in water level after landfall (Fig. 7c, black and gray lines). On the other hand, the coastal response is not evident (Fig. 7c, blue line). This indicates that TY Usagi had an inland effect on the hydrological system rather than a coastal effect. Additionally, a substantial decrease in residual water level at the two river stations (Thao Dien and Phu Cuong) prior to landfall can be seen (Fig. 2a). This suggests that at the timescale of the event river and coastal water levels are decoupled: river stations experience negative residual prior to landfall and a significant surge after landfall, whereas the coastal station does not.

4.4 Inland drivers: rainfall effect on river dynamics

As seen in Sect. 4.2, TY Usagi brought heavy precipitation over the region. In order to better understand the effect of this event on river discharge we map the Saigon system, the topography of the region, the land cover and the spatial distribution of rainfall (Fig. 8a–f). The watershed, urban center and water level stations are also shown in Fig. 8a. The DEM (Fig. 8b) represents the flatness of the region with the middle, lower and urban parts of the watershed sitting well below 50 m a.m.s.l. Further, the lower and urban parts are mostly at an altitude below 10 m a.m.s.l (see Fig. 10a). In fact, the slope of the water surface between the upstream and urban water stations is of the order of 10^{-5} . The distance between these stations is 20 km in a straight line and 35 km along river.

In terms of land cover (Fig. 8c), the middle part of the watershed is composed of bare land and grassland in its northern half; of rice paddies, crops and grassland southwest of the Saigon; and of urban cover, crops and rice paddies southeast of the river. However, only about 15 % of this part is urbanized cover (Nguyen et al., 2022). The lower part of the watershed is mainly covered by crops and grassland west of the river and urbanized land to the east. The urban part is mainly urbanized land cover and waterways with the southeast corner having some grassland (see Fig. 10c).

In Fig. 8d–f, the daily cumulative precipitation is plotted over the Saigon–Dong Nai system. On 24 November 2018 (the day before landfall; Fig. 8d) we see spatially homogeneous precipitation over the whole watershed of about 100 mm. The following day Usagi made landfall at 06:00 UTC. Figure 8e shows that the bulk of the rainfall happened in the middle of the watershed with some locations

Figure 8. (a) The Saigon–Dong Nai system, TY Usagi trajectory and the Saigon watershed. The watershed is split into four parts: upper, middle, lower and urban. (b) Digital elevation model (DEM) of the region. The SRTM vertical datum is global mean sea level and is based on the WGS84 Earth Gravitational Model (EGM 96) geoid (EROS, 2018). (c) Land use map of the region. (d–f) MSWEP daily precipitation over the 3 d of heavy precipitation connected to TY Usagi.

with values above 300 mm. The lower and urban parts also witnessed heavy rainfall between 200 and 300 mm. On 26 November 2018 Usagi was already over Cambodia. The bulk of the rainfall occurred on the upper part of the watershed. The northern part of the middle part of the watershed saw levels of precipitation above 100 mm, while the lower and urban parts saw values below 100 mm.

The discharge results during the period of TY Usagi are presented in Fig. 9a, and the MSWEP precipitation is summed over the watershed in Fig. 9b. Residual discharge starts increasing after landfall, whereas the precipitation event starts about 1 d before landfall on 24 November 2018. Additionally, peak precipitation occurred 10 h after landfall (16:00 UTC on 25 November 2018) with a volume of 65 mm over 3 h, and peak discharge occurred about 26 h after landfall (08:00 UTC on 26 November 2018) and thus with a time lag of 16 h after peak precipitation.

The residual discharge goes to zero about 41 h after the precipitation event is over. During this time the Saigon River evacuated $7.9 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3$ of water at the Phu Cuong location where discharge is computed. On the other hand, the middle, lower and urban sub-catchments received a total of 472, 399 and 383 mm of cumulative rain (Fig. 9c). This equates to, respectively, 8.5×10^8 , 2.2×10^8 and $7.6 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3$ of available water after the event. We can also see (Fig. 8f) that the upper part of the watershed received heavy precipitation on 26 November 2018. However, from Fig. 9a there is no dis-

charge response of the Saigon River, which justifies assuming that the upper part of the watershed is not influencing the river’s discharge. Even though a river response to rainfall is seen, the residual discharge provoked by the storm is negligible when compared to the total discharge amplitudes due to the tidal forcing (Fig. 6d). Hence, tidal forcing dictates the Saigon’s dynamics even during an unprecedented extreme rainfall event. Nonetheless, the behavior of the residual discharge follows closely the water level’s behavior with a similar time lag in the hydraulic response (see Figs. 9a and 7c).

4.5 Urban flooding

The greatest impact of TY Usagi on the population of the HCMC megalopolis came from urban flooding. In this section we discuss the flooding reports at the urban city center in connection with its topography, land use and rainfall extent.

As can be seen from Fig. 10a, the HCMC is very flat (below 5 m a.m.s.l) with the highest part at the center with an altitude of up to 15 m a.m.s.l. This higher topography is west of the urban watershed, implying a surface runoff gradient from west to east into the Saigon River. The land cover is mainly impervious concrete (Fig. 10c) with some patches of grassland north of the city center.

In Fig. 10d, the cumulative precipitation during TY Usagi can be found. We see an increasing south–north precipitation

Figure 9. (a) Estimated residual discharge at Phu Cuong (upstream) and total volume output during TY Usagi. (b) MSWEP 3 h precipitation averaged over the middle, lower and urban parts of the watershed. The upper part of the watershed is not considered since all runoff is directed towards the Dau Tieng reservoir. Additionally, the Saigon watershed is delineated in black. (c) MSWEP cumulative precipitation averaged over the middle, lower and urban part of the watershed as well as total available water after the event.

gradient which follows the direction of Usagi after it made landfall. The north of the city saw the highest amount of precipitation (up to 400 mm), and the lower and urban parts of the watershed received between 350 and 370 mm. As seen in Sect. 4.4, this amounts to $8.4 \times 10^7 m^3$ of available water after the 3 d of the event. By design, the proposed model to estimate discharge is not able to estimate discharge at the urban location. Hence, the direct evacuation by the river cannot be discussed. Nonetheless, the Thao Dien station showed a non-negligible increase in water level (see Sect. 4.2) pointing to a surface runoff effect. Rujner and Goedecke (2016) use the ABIMO model to show that for the urban cover situation in 2016 the total runoff is 38 % of the input by rainwater. Thereafter the surface runoff has a share of 22 % and the infiltration 16 %. These values are indicative of the periodic urban flooding problems following heavy rainfall events in HCMC. For TY Usagi, these percentages translate to $6.4 \times 10^6 m^3$ of surface runoff and $4.6 \times 10^6 m^3$ of infiltration over the urban part of the watershed. The values for total runoff (surface runoff and infiltration) represent 36.7 % of the total volume discharged ($7.9 \times 10^7 m^3$) at Phu Cuong after the event. This provides an indication that, contrary to the upstream situation, the Saigon River might be capable of evacuating a sub-

stantial amount of the rainfall within the few days after the event.

As reported by Vietnamese media, Thao Dien suffered heavy, prolonged flooding with some wards under water for over 24 h. The spatial extent and depth of flooding can be found in Fig. 10b. Indeed, the Thao Dien location shows the highest density of flood points but also the highest depths of flood (up to 0.8 m). Furthermore, flood depths of up to 0.4 m can be found in the highest elevations of the urban center, namely on the west of the urban watershed, which in principle creates runoff in the direction of the Saigon River and thus towards the Thao Dien location.

The observed time lag in water level increase at the Thao Dien station (Fig. 7c, gray) is compatible with the reported flooding locations and duration. Additionally, both peak rainfall and high tide (Figs. 7b and 9b) coincided with the reported flooding duration. The high tide and heavy rainfall effectively removed the possibility of surface runoff to flow towards the river, and flooding occurred around Thao Dien. This comes to show that despite the lack of storm surge at the fluvial–marine transition, the coastal tidal forcing is still a main player in the dynamics of urban flooding in HCMC even during TY Usagi.

Figure 10. (a) Digital elevation model (DEM) of the urban city center. The Phu Cuong (upstream) and Thao Dien (urban) water level stations are indicated as orange triangles. The lower and urban parts of the Saigon watershed are delineated in red. (b) Flood extent and depth reported on 25 November 2018. (c) Land use map of the urban city center. (d) Cumulative MSWEP precipitation during TY Usagi over the 3 d of heavy precipitation connected to TY Usagi (24–26 November 2018).

5 Discussion

Coastal regions are often the zones with the highest concentration of population and economic advancement across numerous nations. Ironically, they are also positioned as the most exposed areas to the potential threat of compound floods, arising from the conjunction of intense precipitation and storm surges. This increased vulnerability can be attributed to the combined factors of dense population, substantial property density and the inherent risk of storm surges (Shen et al., 2019). Within this study, we present a framework that holds potential for application across coastal urban centers grappling with limited data.

The correlation between precipitation and storm surges is bound by several factors, including meteorological conditions and the topography of the region. TYs often provide the required extreme conditions for the occurrence of compound flooding events, and they are one of the most important triggers of such events in coastal regions (Xu et al., 2022a). Even though compound floods have been receiving attention in recent years, few studies exist on the interplay between compound flood drivers during an historical TY in HCMC (Couasnon et al., 2022; Scheiber et al., 2023). This research contributes to this body of knowledge by analyzing and quantifying the driving factors of the compound flood event due to TY Usagi. On the other hand, it is worth not-

ing that the length of the records of observational data used in our study is relatively short, and thus, a statistically based study is not possible. However, our fortunate circumstance of having sensors operational before, during and after the event within this data-scarce region has facilitated the presentation of this case study.

In this study, we found that most precipitation datasets can approximate rainfall patterns over HCMC. Furthermore, when it comes to accurately portraying TY-induced rainfall MSWEP showed the best capabilities by being able to represent rainfall quantity and spatial extent which are in line with the literature (Prakash, 2019; Fernandez-Alvarez et al., 2020; Tran et al., 2023). It was found that the worst performing dataset over this domain is ERA5. ERA5 presented large values of RMSE and MBE and low linear correlation, which indicate that ERA5 is overestimating rainfall over the whole domain. This finding is in line with the current literature: Lavers et al. (2022) found that the largest ERA5 errors are in the tropics and that ERA5 presents a general wet bias. Additionally, it was found that ERA5 can capture locations and patterns of extreme events, but it cannot model the observed precipitation totals. Jiang et al. (2021) found that ERA5 has difficulties in accurately detecting moderate and high daily precipitation events (above 10 mm d^{-1}) over mainland China. It also found that in relatively wet climates such as in the tropical climate zone ERA5 has a higher RMSE than

satellite-based precipitation products. Indeed, satellite-based products perform generally better than model-based products in low latitudes (Xu et al., 2022b). Rivoire et al. (2021) also found that while ERA5 and CMORPH products would agree over the mid-latitudes, they disagreed over the tropics. In fact, reanalysis products usually struggle to resolve precipitation over the tropics and especially tropical cyclones and their surrounding environment. Slocum et al. (2022) analysis showed biases in the ERA5 environmental diagnostic quantities where the most significant discrepancies are observed in the thermodynamic fields. Notably, there is a cold temperature bias in the boundary layer, which constrains convective instability. Additionally, ERA5's biases in temperature are evident in the upper troposphere and are accompanied by a notable overestimation of relative humidity.

It was found that the increased rainfall during the wet season appears to have minimal impact on water levels at the seasonal timescale. This phenomenon is attributed to the distinctive pattern of increased rainfall during the wet season coupled with a reduction in river water levels at the two river stations. This observation underscores the dominant influence of coastal water levels on river water levels across the entirety of the Saigon River. On the other hand, a marginal rise in discharge is discernible during the wet season. Several arguments could hold. Firstly, we see that river levels are generally lower during the wet season due to the coastal forcing. However, the estimated river discharge, which is a function of the slope, is higher in the wet season despite lower river levels. We propose that this is explained by a decrease in river water level everywhere in the river such that the slope is less influenced than the local river levels by this coastal forcing. Thus, we still capture seasonal differences in discharge given that our discharge estimate is a direct function of river slope. This increased discharge is most likely lead by rainfall runoff given that the upstream dam management decreases its outflow during the wet season and increases it in the dry season to mitigate saline intrusion (Ngoc et al., 2014).

For the timescale of the event (3 d) we find a statistically significant river surge but not a coastal surge. Therefore, there was no impact of coastal water level surge, and the river surge seems to be due solely to inland drivers such as rainfall. The Saigon River's water level seems to follow the seasonality of the sea level but at short timescales, and it is impacted by inland factors. This could be partly explained by the apparent lack of storm surge (see Sect. 4.3). This indicates that TY Usagi had an inland effect on the hydrological system rather than a coastal effect. Additionally, from the wind vector maps of Fig. 2b–d it can be seen that offshore winds are created in the Vung Tau region due to the direction and angle of approach of TY Usagi. Hence, throughout the event strong onshore winds never occurred, which explains the lack of storm surge on the coast (Figs. 2a and 7c). Examining the skew surge results of Fig. 7d further demonstrates a lack of coastal storm surge but a significant river surge (as seen in Sect. 4.2) after landfall. Furthermore, the event

reaches land coinciding with a very low coastal water level during a spring tide (Fig. 7b). This result is in line with the study of Takagi et al. (2014), which modeled storm surge in Vietnam and found that the potential maximum of the storm surge for the southern sections is rather low (0.7 m) due to the S shape of the country's shoreline and the cyclonic rotation of TYs in this region. The lack of storm surge during TY Usagi is not unprecedented particularly along the Vietnam coast. Trinh et al. (2020) show that even some of the strongest historical TYs that hit Vietnam can show no record of high storm surges in certain locations along the coast of Vietnam, namely near the cities of Da Nang and Quy Nhon. This indicates that more studies following the methodology of this paper could be valuable if applied to other urban hydrological systems in Vietnam or elsewhere in Southeast Asia.

The analysis of discharge and rainfall results showed a time lag of 16 h between peak rainfall and peak residual river discharge. Considering that the middle part of the watershed is the main driver of residual discharge at Phu Cuong, this time lag can be partially explained by the very flat nature of the terrain (Fig. 8b). As shown in Fig. 8c, the middle part of the watershed has a significant amount of vegetation which intercepts precipitation and slows the movement of water into river channels. Furthermore, widespread flooding upstream of Phu Cuong played a role in delaying the discharge response. An analysis of flood areas was conducted using MODIS satellite daily and eight-daily surface reflectance products (Fig. A1 in Appendix A). This analysis proved difficult to interpret within the watershed area due to the presence of clouds throughout the event. However, we found evidence of widespread flooding immediately east of the watershed around the river Vam Co Dong, which has similar land cover to the middle part of the watershed (Fig. 8c). Another possible driver of the lag time between rainfall and discharge are aquifer recharging processes. In the middle part of the watershed the groundwater is more influenced by rainfall than by river recharge with shallow aquifers being predominantly recharged by heavy wet season rainfall events (Tu et al., 2022). The existence of a time lag between rainfall and discharge at this location after such heavy rainfall might be due to the recharge of the groundwater table functioning as a buffer. Additionally, monitored groundwater levels are generally above the Saigon River's water level creating a hydraulic gradient from the shallow aquifers towards the river (Khai and Koontanakulvong, 2015; Tu et al., 2022). This possibly indicates a groundwater recharge phenomenon followed by a slow spill towards the river over the few days following the event.

The residual discharge goes to zero about 41 h after the precipitation event is over. Assuming the middle part of the watershed is the principal driver of the residual discharge at Phu Cuong, the river evacuated 9.3 % of all available water. This low percentage of evacuation is partly explained by the important role that evapotranspiration plays in the climate of the region, which can effectively reduce the peak discharge

of the river. Rujner and Goedecke (2016) use the water budget model ABIMO to describe the long-term annual means of the total runoff, surface runoff, evaporation and infiltration around HCMC. The results show that surface runoff takes 7% and infiltration 6%, and the remaining 87% is evapotranspiration, which is in line with our findings.

Throughout this study, it was assumed that the upper part of the watershed had no influence on the hydrological behavior of the Saigon River. On 26 November 2018 (the last day of TY Usagi), the upper part of the watershed received heavy precipitation (Fig. 8f). However, we found no discharge response of the Saigon River (Fig. 9a), which justifies assuming that the upper part of the watershed is not influencing the river's discharge. This part of the watershed is regulated by the Dau Tieng reservoir, which is managed by the Dau Tieng–Phuoc Hoa Irrigation Exploitation Company. According to its design, the maximum capacity of overflow discharge is $2800\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$. However, during the dry season the maximum output from the dam is $30\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$, and during the wet season it is around $100\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$ with peaks that can go up to $400\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$ during heavy rainfall events (Dinh and Nguyen, 2019). The reservoir has only one available flood route, which is the Saigon River. The flood capacity of the Saigon River section at the foot of the dam is much lower than the maximum overflow capacity, causing severe downstream flooding every time the discharge through the spillway exceeds $200\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$. Ever since 2013, the province of HCMC has ensured that the reservoir flood discharge capacity is kept below $500\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$. However, when heavy rains are predicted the dam's discharge can be increased to levels close to the peak residual discharge found in Fig. 9. It is thus possible that part of the residual discharge is a direct cause of the dam's discharge policies, which would make the evacuation of rainfall by the river even smaller.

The behavior of the residual discharge follows closely the river water level's behavior with a similar time lag in the hydraulic response (see Figs. 9a and 7c). This is expected as the driver of the discharge computation is the slope (Eq. 2), which is a function of the river water levels at both stations. The relatively weak hydraulic response could be explained by the fact that both stations have a quasi-simultaneous increase in water level which leads to a less steep slope and thus weaker discharge. This is due to the regional scale of the precipitation brought by Usagi. Thus, the slope should remain relatively constant, and river discharge might be underestimated. Other possible sources of error in the estimation of discharge can be an over sensitivity to the water level measurement error and difficulty in capturing asymmetrical tide dynamics. Therefore, the interpretation of these discharge estimations must be made carefully.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we investigate the most severe rainfall event ever experienced in HCMC, Vietnam. It occurred on 25 November 2018 when TY Usagi directly hit HCMC. During this event, there was more than 300 mm of rainfall over 24 h which led to flooding and considerable material damage. In this work, we put forward an evaluation of the compound flood event and its impact on the region by using a set of tools to characterize and quantify both coastal and inland drivers. For the first time in a data-scarce region, all hydrological information was gathered and analyzed during an unprecedented extreme event that affected millions of people in the HCMC megalopolis. We go from a hydrological approach to a data analysis and signal processing approach in order to analyze coastal and river water levels, rainfall, and urban flooding. This approach not only allowed a thorough investigation of the TY's impacts but also allowed new insights into the hydrological behavior of this region.

From the evaluation of five research-quality precipitation datasets against in situ measurements, we find that the MSWEP dataset shows the best performance in estimating rainfall over the region of interest and can capture the precipitation behavior during TY Usagi ($R = 0.6$, $\text{MBE} = -4.3\text{ mm}$ and $\text{RMSE} = 7.6\text{ mm}$). Hence, it is used to analyze TY Usagi's rainfall over the watershed. A statistical overview of the dataset shows that the rainfall brought by Usagi constituted the maximum daily rainfall in the MSWEP data series.

We observe that the impact of increased wet season rainfall on river water levels is dwarfed by the seasonal coastal storm surge caused by the wind pattern of the East Asian summer monsoon, which typically lasts from November to April. This translates to higher water levels during the dry season and thus a coastal control of the Saigon River at the seasonal scale. A mono-disciplinary hydrologist approach may have expected a higher water level during the wet season, which underlines the interest of crossing disciplines at the interface between river and ocean. Additionally, it was found that the highly urbanized land cover and complex urban canal system of HCMC are modulating the river water level, which shows consistently higher residual water levels and skew surge than elsewhere.

The main coastal driver related to a TY event is the associated storm surge. At first, no direct observation of the hydrological impact of TY Usagi is possible for the Saigon River, and harmonic tidal analysis was required to filter the tidal fluctuations and observe the effects of such an event. For TY Usagi, the analysis of coastal residual water level and skew surge showed that the storm surge was not statistically significant when compared with the distribution of values during the wet season. The lack of coastal surge is associated with the timing of the landfall, the direction and the angle of approach of TY Usagi. Landfall occurred during a large-amplitude spring tide with a very low tide, and the TY never produced strong onshore winds but instead off-

shore and shore-parallel winds. However, the lack of storm surge is mainly attributed to the wind direction during this event. On the other hand, the Saigon River's urban and upstream water level stations show a significant surge, which shows that there was no impact of coastal surge on river water levels and that the river surge was due solely to inland drivers such as rainfall. At short timescales and during the sudden, heavy precipitation event, the river and coastal water levels were decoupled.

After landfall, we find that both river levels and discharge start increasing, whereas the precipitation event starts about 1 d before landfall. The peak precipitation and peak discharge occurred 10 and 26 h after landfall, respectively. The very flat nature of the terrain in addition to the significant amount of vegetation creates a time lag of 16 h between peak discharge and peak precipitation. Furthermore, the river evacuates 9.3 % of available rainwater pointing to widespread flooding and aquifer recharging processes in the middle of the watershed. In fact, the extreme rainfall brought about a peak discharge that is above the third quartile for the wet season but that is far from being an outlier. Even though it was not possible to know the dam's discharge policy during Usagi, it is clear that part of the residual discharge could be a direct cause of the dam's discharge. Historically, the dam's discharge policy was of increasing outflow in anticipation of heavy rainfall making the river contribution to evacuating rainfall smaller.

TY Usagi released $7.6 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3$ of water over the urban watershed over 3 d. The urban river station showed a non-negligible increase in water level pointing to a surface runoff effect. Our estimation says that total urban runoff is 36.7 % of the water volume discharged at Phu Cuong, and thus, at the urban location the river is able to evacuate the rainwater over the few days after the event. Additionally, we find that the Thao Dien ward shows the highest density of reported flood points but also the highest depths of flood (up to 0.8 m). Furthermore, floods in the west of the urban watershed create runoff in the direction of the Saigon River and thus towards the Thao Dien water level station, explaining its consistently higher surges than in the upstream station. The time lag in river surge and peak precipitation are due to the high tide removing the possibility of surface runoff towards the river. The river water levels were high, and rainwater would not effectively drain towards the river but rather linger in the impervious streets of HCMC. In fact, during spring tides it is common to have river-induced, short-lived flooding in the lower-elevation areas of the city, namely in Thao Dien. Adding to this an extreme, persistent precipitation caused widespread flooding. Hence, the river flood is delaying the surface runoff and prolonging the flood residence time. This shows that despite the lack of storm surge the astronomical tide forcing is still a main player in the dynamics of urban flooding in HCMC even during TY Usagi.

The methodology presented in this paper encompasses a data processing and analysis work applied to a complex, ur-

ban estuarine system. Its foundation lies on the correct choice of TY compound flood drivers and gathering of relevant data in order to characterize the response of the hydrological system to an extreme event. This methodology could easily be applied to any other urbanized estuary both in Southeast Asia and elsewhere in the world by tailoring the choice of impact factors to the region of interest. Additionally, the extreme event does not need to be a TY but could be any other event that provokes compound flooding and impacts the respective communities. However, in this study fortunate circumstances allowed us to observe the impact of TY Usagi on the Saigon River system, as our sensors were actively recording during its landfall. River water level measurements at such high time resolution are not generally available in data-scarce regions. Hence, efforts to work together with local researchers and authorities in order to develop data monitoring strategies are crucial for studies of this type in other data-scarce regions. A way to mitigate this problem is by using open-access data such as global precipitation datasets. However, this type of data comes with inherent data quality issues and uncertainties (Scheiber et al., 2023). Another limitation of this study is the adapted Manning–Strickler equation used to estimate discharge which, even though previously validated for the Saigon River (Camenen et al., 2021), assumes uniform flow for a tidal river. Additionally, if both river water level stations feel an increase in water level, the equation will not translate this to increased discharge, as the surface slope remains constant. Nevertheless, the equation behaves rather well representing the river discharge throughout the monitoring time and during TY Usagi.

Future prospects would be high-resolution modeling of the city's flooding regimes during TY events even though models of such complex hydrosystems have expected limitations. Additionally, simulating high numbers of TYs around the area to find TY characteristics that would be more damaging to HCMC could be an interesting follow up. This would allow early warning depending on early developing storm characteristics and a better understanding of expected damage, thus providing the city with better information for impact mitigation. Finally, a better understanding of the upstream area of HCMC and the interaction between river discharge, rainfall and groundwater is required, as well as a better understanding of the canal network dynamics.

Appendix A: MODIS satellite study

Appendix B: Performance metrics for MSWEP during TY Usagi

Figure A1. DEM, land cover, weekly cumulative precipitation and results of flooded area over the region of interest using the MODIS surface reflectance 8 d product. The left column represents the week before the event and the right column the week after. Three methodologies are used to find inundated pixels: Sakamoto et al. (2007), modified normalized difference water index (MNDWI) and automated water extraction index (AWEI).

Table B1. Performance metrics for MSWEP over the month of November 2018 over six rainfall gauges in HCMC.

Rainfall gauge	RMSE [mm d ⁻¹]	MBE [mm d ⁻¹]	R [-]
Phuoc Long A	7.2	20.2	0.62
Binh Chieu	4.2	-7.8	0.71
Ly Thuong Kiet	17.3	-20	0.8
An Lac	11.7	-15.8	0.77
Binh Hung Hoa	1.3	-3.5	0.11
Cu Chi	4.2	1.2	0.64
Average	7.6	-4.3	0.6

Appendix C: Statistical description of datasets

Table C1. Statistical description of water level data for the period from January 2017 to December 2018 at the three stations under study. The mean water level over the full period was removed from the series. All non-specified units are in meters.

Station	Vung Tau		Thao Dien		Phu Cuong	
Distance from coast	0 km		60 km		80 km	
Frequency	1 h		10 min		10 min	
Season	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
Count of data points	8224	8774	48 312	52 993	48 312	52 993
Mean	0.13	−0.01	0.14	−0.12	0.1	−0.09
Standard deviation	0.8	0.83	0.73	0.79	0.59	0.65
Minimum	−2.35	−2.91	−2.01	−2.52	−1.8	−2.12
25th percentile	−0.40	−0.64	−0.39	−0.69	−0.29	−0.5
50th percentile	0.31	0.07	0.26	−0.03	0.2	0.01
75th percentile	0.76	0.55	0.75	0.52	0.58	0.43
Maximum	1.61	1.47	1.48	1.4	1.15	1.11

Table C2. Statistical description of residual water level for the period from January 2017 to December 2018 at the three stations under study. All non-specified units are in meters.

Station	Vung Tau		Thao Dien		Phu Cuong	
Distance from coast	0		60 000		80 000	
Season	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
Mean	0.14	0.02	0.12	−0.02	0.11	0.003
Standard deviation	0.16	0.21	0.16	0.25	0.17	0.21
Minimum	−0.33	−0.73	−0.75	−2.35	−0.46	−0.86
25th percentile	0.02	−0.14	0.01	−0.16	−0.01	−0.14
50th percentile	0.13	0.01	0.12	−0.003	0.1	−0.01
75th percentile	0.25	0.17	0.23	0.16	0.22	0.15
Maximum	0.76	0.76	0.91	0.94	0.93	0.93

Table C3. Statistical description of computed discharge for the period from January 2017 to December 2018 at Phu Cuong.

Season	Total discharge [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$]		Discharge due to tide [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$]		Net discharge [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$]	
	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry
Count	52 993	48 305	52 993	48 305	52 993	46 211
Mean	242.05	135.41	60.17	66.13	181.9	68.78
Standard deviation	940.96	937.86	928.96	884.64	150.09	118.03
Minimum	−1626.45	−1513.89	−1454.15	−1421.38	−352.15	−535.28
25th percentile	−777.9	−862.25	−924.57	−868.44	88.57	19.37
50th percentile	632.81	476.49	397.32	385.62	158.95	65.94
75th percentile	1112.16	1042.00	970.93	923.61	267.18	117.24
Maximum	2482.67	1630.29	1376.30	1302.63	1769.07	987.94

Code availability. All the necessary Python codes supporting the contents of this publication are available upon request. These are not made publicly available as they are unpolished source code that is not ready for use by third persons. Additionally, providing support to others who would download the software and use it is currently not possible. Hence, we do not provide the code in a public repository.

Data availability. All data used in this paper can be either accessed via public repositories or upon request to the original owners in case of proprietary data. The precipitation datasets are available in public repositories. Namely, GPCC data are available from the Deutscher Wetterdienst (https://doi.org/10.5676/DWD_GPCC/FD_D_V2020_100, Ziese et al., 2020). CMORPH ([https://doi.org/10.1175/1525-7541\(2004\)005<0487:CAMTPG>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1525-7541(2004)005<0487:CAMTPG>2.0.CO;2), Joyce et al., 2004) and MSWEP (<https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-17-0138.1>, Beck et al., 2019) data are available from the American Meteorological Society. ERA5 data for precipitation (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.68d2bb30>, Munoz-Sabater et al., 2021) and wind (<https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>, Hersbach et al., 2020) are available for free in the Copernicus Climate Data Store, and IMERG data are available in the NASA Global Precipitation Measurement data directory (<https://doi.org/10.5067/GPM/IMERGDF/DAY/06>, Huffman et al., 2019).

Water level data from the Vung Tau tide gauge are available from the University of Hawaii Sea Level Center website (<https://doi.org/10.7289/V5V40S7W>, Caldwell et al., 2015).

Land cover data are available from the ALOS Research and Application Project (https://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/ALOS/en/dataset/lulc/lulc_vnm_v2109_e.htm, Phan et al., 2021).

The SRTM Digital Elevation Model data are available at NASA's Earthdata portal (<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/sensors/srtm>, Farr et al., 2007).

The urban river gauge data (Camenen et al., 2021) and flood reports (Leitold et al., 2021) are available upon request to original owners (proprietary data).

The in situ precipitation data are not publicly available (proprietary data).

Author contributions. Conceptualization, investigation, data collection and curation: FRdA; formal analysis, writing and editing: FRdA; reviewing and supervision: NG, TP and TAT.

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2.2 CONCLUSION

This chapter has demonstrated the vital role of combining satellite-derived data with in-situ hydrological measurements to understand and manage the impacts of extreme weather events on urban environments. The case study of Typhoon Usagi's impact on Ho Chi Minh City in 2018 underscores the complexity of compound flood drivers in low-elevation coastal zones. By examining the interplay between coastal tidal forces, extreme rainfall, and river discharge, the research has highlighted the predominant role of tidal fluctuations in driving urban flooding in Ho Chi Minh City during such events. These insights emphasize the need for integrated flood management strategies that consider multiple hydrological and meteorological factors.

Overall, this chapter contributes to the broader field of satellite hydrology by providing a methodological framework for assessing the impacts of typhoon-induced flooding in data-scarce regions. The insights gained from this research are not only applicable to HCMC but also offer valuable lessons for other vulnerable urban regions worldwide. Future research should continue to refine these methodologies and expand the scope of study to include other types of extreme weather events and their impacts on different hydrological systems.

This chapter highlights the need for higher quantity and quality of in-situ measurements in megacities situated in low elevation coastal zones. The next chapter is an attempt to address these issues and provides information on a two-month field campaign in Ho Chi Minh City to obtain valuable new in-situ data. This campaign was fully conceptualized, managed, and supervised by me, with the assistance of Mr. Tin Nguyen Trung from the Center for Asian Research on Water (CARE).

3

Datasets of high-resolution water level and discharge from the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system impacted by a developing megacity, Ho Chi Minh City - Vietnam

SUMMARY

In this chapter, we introduce a new hydrological dataset obtained from a field campaign in the Saigon-Dongnai system. This dataset encompasses water level and temperature readings at five points along the Saigon River and two points along the Dongnai River, alongside discharge measurements from four 24-hour ADCP campaigns at strategic locations. Despite its short duration, the dataset offers unprecedented spatial and temporal resolution in a region with limited freely available data. The simultaneous logging of multiple sensors along the river sets the stage for the continuation of this thesis as this data will permit the validation of a 1D hydraulic model of the river system (Chapter 4) and the analysis of water surface profiles in the context of simulating and validating SWOT satellite products (Chapter 5).

KEY FINDINGS

- Water level data are recorded every 15 minutes with a spatial resolution of 10 km along the river, while discharge measurements from ADCP campaigns cover different tidal regimes.
- The dataset could support better decision-making by local environmental protection, management agencies and policymakers concerning urban flooding and dam management.
- The concurrent high-resolution discharge and water level data enable calibration and validation of hydraulic and hydrological models as well as remote sensing data.

This chapter has been published in *Data in Brief*, 48, 109147, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109147>. All data are openly available in the DataSuds repository (IRD, France) at <https://doi.org/10.23708/KLQMSR>. Data reuse is granted under CC-BY license.

3.1 Introduction to the field campaign

In this section, we provide an overview of the deployment and monitoring activities of a two-month field campaign in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), Vietnam. This campaign was the fruit of the collaboration between the Centre Asiatique de Recherche sur l'Eau (CARE) in Ho Chi Minh City and the Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement (IGE) in Grenoble, France.

This campaign was conducted in connection with a hydraulic study aimed at evaluating the new capabilities of the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite, specifically applied to the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system and presented in Chapter 5. The measurement efforts involved 8 HOBO pressure sensors and 4 Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) campaigns conducted in the Saigon and Dong Nai rivers. This mission aimed to enhance data collection for hydrological studies by installing new sensors and conducting ADCP campaigns to gather detailed water level and river discharge information. The measurement efforts are summarized below:

Saigon river: 4 new sensors. 2 already in place. 3 ADCP campaigns.

- 1 sensor stolen: no data.
- 5 sensors during mission (3 new + 2 already in place).
- 3 sensors ongoing.

Dongnai river: 2 new HOBO sensors. 1 ADCP campaign.

- 1 sensor stolen and replaced: lost about 4 days of data.
- 2 sensors during mission.
- 0 sensors ongoing.

In Saigon, four new HOBO pressure sensors were added to the existing two, despite one being stolen before data recovery. The Dongnai river saw the installation of two new sensors, with one also stolen but subsequently replaced. The loggers were deployed using a cost-effective brick-and-pipe system (Figure 3.1), wherein each logger is secured inside a PVC pipe attached to a brick. To minimize sediment deposition on the loggers, several holes were drilled into the PVC pipes. The pipes and bricks were installed so that the sensors were positioned at least 15 cm above the riverbed. Before their initial deployment, all loggers were tested and calibrated using a water column. Additionally, the system was secured to the riverbanks with a metal cable (Figure 3.2) to make it as inconspicuous as possible, reducing the likelihood of tampering or theft. Despite these precautions, there were instances where people removed

Figure 3.1: Examples of brick system installation of the water level sensors (left and right images). Inside the PVC pipe is the HOBO U20L-01 water level sensor (middle image). These particular installations are the ones deployed in the Dongnai river.

the sensors from the water and then threw them back in, which was clear from anomalies observed in the logger data.

Another significant challenge we encountered was accessing the riverbanks, which are predominantly privatized or owned by the government. The most ideal locations for sensor deployment are government-owned ports along the river. However, privately owned riverbanks, such as those in cafes or residences, often prove to be more advantageous because they are monitored by their owners, reducing the risk of public tampering.

We were fortunate to identify some suitable locations where we could negotiate with locals, thanks particularly to Mr. Tin Nguyen Trung, an engineer at CARE, who accompanied me throughout the city to deploy sensors. His ability to communicate effectively with the locals and explain our mission and objectives was invaluable. In some cases, the locals immediately understood the importance of our work and were willing to cooperate. However, in other instances, they were skeptical of our intentions, fearing a potential scam. Unfortunately, in certain river locations, sensor deployment was not feasible due to the absence of private infrastructure and the inaccessibility of government-owned sites. Additionally, natural barriers posed further challenges in identifying ideal locations.

Moreover, it was crucial that the sensor locations be sufficiently submerged during the lowest tides of the spring cycle, adding another layer of complexity to our search for suitable sites. This constraint significantly limited the number

Figure 3.2: Example of brick system installation seen from the street level. Left: location at a private person’s house (named HOBO 2 in the following article). Right: Location at a local café (named HOBO 3 in the following article).

of viable locations for our sensors.

The data collected from these sensors, along with the ADCP campaigns, will be instrumental in the next chapters of this thesis. The mission faced challenges such as theft and data loss, which were mitigated through strategic relocation of the sensors and other protective measures. This measurement effort produced a data article that constitutes the main content of this chapter. In the article, we present the dataset gathered during the field campaign, along with the details of its pre-processing and post-processing.

Data Article

Datasets of high-resolution water level and discharge from the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system impacted by a developing megacity, Ho Chi Minh City - Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

We present a new hydrological dataset collected during a field campaign in the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system, Vietnam. These data include water level and water temperature measurements at five locations along the Saigon river and 2 locations along the Dong Nai river as well as discharge measurements from four 24-hour Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) campaigns at 2 locations in the Saigon river and 1 location in the Dong Nai river. Additionally, water level was barometrically compensated using air pressure measurements. Data were sampled between October 21st, 2022 and December 16th, 2022 and are provided in three processing stages namely, direct measurements as provided by the sensors (raw), barometrically compensated measurements (pre-processed) and corrected measurements (post-processed). Even though of short duration (about 2 months), this dataset provides water level measurements at unprecedented spatial and temporal resolution in a region where data is scarce and not freely available. The synchronous logging of multiple water level sensors along river provides an opportunity to study profiles of water surface slope and upstream tidal propagation. Furthermore, the con-

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current discharge measurements can be used to calibrate hydrological and/or hydraulic models of this estuary system. Additionally, the spatial resolution of this dataset is similar to the prospective measurements that the novel Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite will provide. Thus, it enables the study of synthetic SWOT measurements to evaluate the future potential of the SWOT satellite over this estuary system.

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Specifications Table

Subject:	Water Science and Technology
Specific subject area:	Water level and discharge measurements in tidal rivers using low-cost installation of water level loggers and 24-hour ADCP campaigns.
Type of data:	Table Graph
How the data were acquired:	Water level: Submersed brick-and-pipe installation of Onset HOBO U20L-01 water level loggers measuring absolute pressure and temperature. The HOBOWare Pro version 3.7.21 software is used to convert absolute pressure into water level and perform barometric compensation. Air pressure: Measurements from a Watson W-8681-MKII wireless weather station are used as barometric reference. Discharge: 24-hour campaigns using the Workhorse Rio Grande Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) measuring discharge twice hourly.
Data format:	Raw Pre-processed Post-processed
Description of data collection:	Water level measurements were performed at 5 locations in the Saigon river branch and at 2 locations in the Dong Nai river branch between October 21 st , 2022 and December 16 th , 2022. We perform barometric compensation, identify and correct of out-of-water instances using temperature and pressure readings and quadratic interpolation. Discharge measurements were performed at 2 locations in the Saigon river and 1 location in the Dong Nai river. We use the free, open-source QrevInt software for post-processing and quality control and obtain mean discharge, mean width and mean river cross-section. The uncertainty in discharge is computed using the OURSIN framework [1].
Data source location:	City/Town/Region: Ho Chi Minh City Country: Vietnam Latitude and longitude (and GPS coordinates, if possible) for collected samples/data: presented in Table 1.
Data accessibility:	In a public repository. Repository name: DataSuds Data identification number: doi.org/10.23708/NKQDNB Direct URL to data: https://doi.org/10.23708/NKQDNB Full reference: Rodrigues Do Amaral, Francisco; Nguyen, Trung Tin; Gratiot, Nicolas; Pellarin, Thierry, 2023, "High-resolution water level and discharge measurements from the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system, Vietnam, 2022", https://doi.org/10.23708/NKQDNB , DataSuds, V1, UNF:6:mWcp4LMDvHYz+oaLv15f4w== [fileUNF]

Value of the Data

- The new water level dataset provides a series of unprecedented measurements over the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system at high time (every 15 minutes) and space (every 10 km along river) resolution. The new discharge dataset encompasses four 24-hour ADCP measurements at three locations providing discharge measurements during different tidal regimes.
- Can benefit environmental protection and management agencies with a more reliable forecasting of river water levels and better decision making by researchers and policy makers regarding urban flooding and dam management.
- Can be used to verify and validate remote sensing measurements such as water surface level and water surface slope. In particular, given that the chosen spatial resolution (every 10 km along river) matches the prospective resolution of the new Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite this dataset can benefit the study of SWOT measurements over this system. The short time period of measurements is sufficient for feasibility and measurement evaluation studies related to SWOT.
- The concurrent discharge and water level data at high spatial and temporal resolution may be used to calibrate and validate both hydraulic and hydrological models and provide new insights on macro- and micro-pollutant transport, saline intrusion and urban flood dynamics.
- Even though provided for only two months, the resolution of this data enables a better scientific understanding of tidal wave propagation along the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system by providing a high spatial resolution of measurements.

1. Objective

The dataset presented was collected during a 2-month field campaign in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), Vietnam within the context of a French-Vietnamese collaboration between the Centre Asiatique de Recherche sur L'Eau (CARE) and the Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement (IGE). This particular campaign was carried out in connection with a hydraulic study to assess the new capabilities of the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite applied to the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system. It includes water level and temperature measurements at five locations along the Saigon river and 2 locations along the Dong Nai river as well as discharge measurements from four 24-hour ADCP campaigns at 2 locations in the Saigon river and 1 location in the Dong Nai river. Additionally, water level was barometrically compensated using air pressure measurements. Data were sampled between October 21st, 2022 and December 16th, 2022 and are provided in raw (e.g. *.hobo* files), pre-processed (e.g. barometric compensation) and post-processed (e.g. quadratic interpolation) form [1]. A brief description of each data format is given below.

2. Data Description

The location of sensors and ADCP campaigns are presented in [Table 1](#) together with their respective variables. The water level datasets are provided in files named as follows: “[Location ID]-[type].csv” or “[Location ID]-[type].hobo”. Similarly, the discharge datasets are provided in files named as follows: “[type]-[Location ID]-[date].csv”. The File IDs are summarized in [Table 1](#) and the types refer to the level of processing namely, “raw”, “pre-processed” or “post-processed”. Details on the level of processing are given in sections 3.1 and 3.2.

2.1. Water Level

Raw files – Files in *.hobo* format directly provided by each sensor. These files provide absolute pressure and temperature readings.

Table 1

Summary of information on location of measurements, file ID and corresponding variables.

Location ID	River Basin	Lat. [°N]	Lon. [°E]	Type	Variables
Cu-Chi	Saigon	11.054518	106.539539	raw	Absolute pressure, temperature
				pre	Absolute pressure, temperature, Water level
HOB01	Saigon	10.931750	106.652340	post	Corrected water level
				air	Absolute and relative air pressure
HOB02	Saigon	10.869837	106.699607	raw	Absolute pressure, temperature
				pre	Absolute pressure, temperature, Water level
HOB03	Saigon	10.829748	106.709833	post	Corrected water level
				raw	Absolute pressure, temperature
La garden	Saigon	10.785773	106.721540	pre	Absolute pressure, temperature, Water level
				post	Corrected water level
HOB0 DN1	Dong Nai	10.944861	106.816343	raw	Absolute pressure, temperature
				pre	Absolute pressure, temperature, Water level
HOB0 DN2	Dong Nai	10.678755	106.777768	post	Corrected water level
				ADCP	Discharge, discharge uncertainty and estimated error, width, cross-section
HOB0 DN2	Dong Nai	10.678755	106.777768	raw	Absolute pressure, temperature
				pre	Absolute pressure, temperature, Water level
				post	Corrected water level

Pre-processed files – Raw files processed using HOBOWare Pro v3.7.21 software in .csv format. These files contain water level compensated for barometric pressure changes.

Post-processed files – Pre-processed files processed using Python in .csv format. These files contain water level data which was corrected for out-of-water periods, homogenized for reference point and normalized across sensors (Fig. 1).

2.2. Discharge

ADCP files – Files produced with QrevInt software and the OURSIN framework [2] in .csv format. These files contain mean discharge, mean width and mean river cross-section as well as the OURSIN discharge uncertainty and error estimation in the discharge measurement (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Post-processed water level measurements for the Saigon river (a) and for the Dong Nai river (b). For the sake of readability, the water levels are displaced by 3 meters in a) and by 4 meters in b). The HOBODN1 location shows a data gap due to a stolen sensor. This data corresponds to the post-processed water level data found in “[Location ID]-post.csv” files.

Fig. 2. Plot of the post-processed ADCP measurements and corresponding error uncertainties. This data corresponds to the post-processed water level data found in “[Location ID]-ADCP.csv” files.

3. Experimental Design, Materials and Methods

3.1. Water Level

The water level dataset comprises data for the locations summarized in [Table 1](#) and was obtained using HOBO U20L-01 water level loggers at a time resolution of 15 minutes. This device has a typical error of $\pm 0.1\%$, a maximum error of $\pm 0.2\%$ and a resolution of < 0.21 cm. The loggers were deployed using a low-cost brick-and-pipe system where the logger is secured inside a PVC pipe and attached to a brick. In order to minimize sediment deposition over the logger several holes are made on the PVC pipe and the pipe and brick are installed in such a way that the sensor is at least 15 cm off the bottom of the river. Prior to the first deployment all loggers were tested and calibrated using a water column.

3.1.1. Pre-Processing

Pre-processed data includes the HOBO logger records of absolute pressure, which are converted to water level readings by HOBOWare Pro software version 3.7.21. In this application, absolute pressure includes atmospheric pressure and water head. Atmospheric pressure is nominally 100 kPa at sea level, but it changes with weather and altitude. To compensate for barometric pressure changes, we use measurements from a Watson W-8681-MKII wireless weather station as barometric reference. This reference was deployed at the Cu-Chi location. Barometric pressure readings are consistent across a region (except during fast-moving weather events), thus it is generally correct to use barometric pressure readings that are taken within 30 km of the logger without significantly degrading the accuracy of the compensation. Therefore, this weather station was used to compensate all the water level loggers in the area. The HOBOWare Pro software uses the hydrostatic equation to calculate water level from pressure measurements. The level of water can be calculated from the hydrostatic pressure using the formula:

$$h = \frac{P}{\rho \cdot g} \quad (1)$$

where h is the height of the liquid column [m], P is the pressure, ρ is the density of the liquid [kg/m^3], and g is the gravitational acceleration [m/s^2]. However, the column of air above the water will affect the pressure readings due to fluctuations in atmospheric pressure. The measured pressure at the bottom of the column of water will be the sum of the hydrostatic pressure due to the weight of the water and the atmospheric pressure due to the weight of the air above it. To accurately measure the water level, the atmospheric pressure must be subtracted from the pressure readings. This computation is performed using the HOBOWare Pro dedicated tool and is referred to as barometric compensation.

3.1.2. Post-Processing

Post-processed data includes water level that has been corrected for out-of-water periods, homogenized for reference point differences and normalized across sensors.

The temperature signal was used to identify out-of-water periods. During these periods the sensor captures the air temperature rather than the water temperature creating temperature anomalies. We remove water level readings below the 2nd and above the 98th percentile of temperature over the measurement period. We fill these values by using quadratic interpolation [3] and implement it using the interpolate function in Python. Quadratic interpolation is a numerical method used to estimate missing values in a dataset. It involves fitting a quadratic function, which is a second-order polynomial of the form

$$y = ax^2 + bx + c \quad (2)$$

to the data points surrounding the missing values. The coefficients a , b , and c are determined by solving a system of equations using the known data points. Once the quadratic function has been fitted to the data, it can be used to estimate the values of the missing data points by

evaluating the function at their x values. This provides a smooth curve that passes through all of the known data points and can be used to estimate the values of the missing data points.

In order to retrieve the data, the logger needs to be removed and re-placed in the water. This means that the position of the sensor slightly changes every time data is retrieved. Hence, the reference point changes between data retrievals. In order to mitigate this effect, the following methodology was applied. Given a water level signal y and a retrieval of data m times during the campaign, for each time period between data retrievals, the average water level, a_i , can be computed for the i^{th} time period. Then, we subtract the average water level a_i from the signal y_i in that time period to obtain the corrected signal $y_{\text{corrected}}$:

$$y_{\text{corrected}_i} = y_i - a_i \quad (3)$$

This process can be repeated m times for each time period between data retrievals to obtain the corrected water level signal over the full time period of measurements. This helps to improve the accuracy and consistency of the water level data.

At each sensor location, the reference point is different and unknown. In order to be able to compare the signals at different locations we normalize all signals. One way to do this is by using a method called mean normalization. This involves calculating the mean water level for each sensor over the full time period of measurements and then subtracting this mean from the water level signal for that sensor. This is done for each sensor using Eqn 3 applied to the full period of measurements.

3.2. Discharge

The discharge dataset comprises data for the locations summarized in Table 1 and was acquired using the Teledyne Workhorse Rio Grande Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). Four 24-hour measurement campaigns were performed. Two transects were made every hour yielding one discharge measurement per hour.

3.2.1. Post-Processed Files

Post-processed ADCP discharge files include mean discharge, mean width and mean river cross-section. Additionally, these files include discharge uncertainty calculated using the OURSIN framework [2] and error estimation in the discharge measurement.

The mean discharge, mean width and mean river cross-section are taken over two transects every hour. The discharge uncertainty is calculated using the OURSIN method. The OURSIN method is a framework for computing the uncertainty of moving-boat ADCP discharge measurements that has been implemented in QrevInt software. The uncertainty of extrapolated discharges in unmeasured areas is estimated by varying the maximum number of parameters, as an alternative to the Monte Carlo approach. A uniform distribution of errors is assumed so that any value in the minimum-maximum possible range is equally likely to occur. The OURSIN method also accounts for systematic versus random errors in the computation of the uncertainty of discharge measurements averaged over repeated ADCP transects. Then, the decomposition of the different error sources allows determining their influence on the overall uncertainty [4]. In addition, the error in ADCP measurements was evaluated at 10% using a minimum error value of $100 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ given the adverse conditions encountered during the campaigns [5,6].

CRedit Author Statement

Francisco Rodrigues do Amaral: Conceptualization Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing, Review & Editing; **Tin Nguyen Trung:** Methodology, Data curation; **Nicolas Gratiot:** Supervision, Review & Editing; **Thierry Pellarin:** Supervision, Review & Editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

[High-resolution water level and discharge measurements from the Saigon-Dong Nai estuary system, Vietnam, 2022 \(Original data\)](#) (Dataverse).

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3.3 CONCLUSION

This chapter presents the hydrological dataset collected during the field campaign in the Saigon-Dongnai estuary. The high-resolution measurements of water levels and discharge provide unprecedented temporal and spatial details, crucial for environmental management and scientific research. By enabling more accurate forecasting of river water levels and validation of remote sensing data, this dataset supports better decision-making in urban planning, flood mitigation strategies, and environmental protection efforts.

The ability to calibrate hydraulic and hydrological models enhances our understanding of pollutant transport, saline intrusion dynamics, and tidal wave propagation. In Chapter 4, we use this data to validate a 1D hydrodynamic model of the Saigon-Dongnai system. Moreover, the dataset's alignment with the prospective resolution of the SWOT satellite underscores its utility in evaluating this satellite mission. In Chapter 5, this data is used to simulate SWOT river products and assess the potential benefits of using SWOT data to improve discharge estimations.

4

Operational calibration and performance improvement for hydrodynamic models in data-scarce coastal areas

SUMMARY

In this chapter, we delve into the complexities of hydrodynamic modelling in the Saigon-Dongnai river system. We address the challenges posed by data scarcity in this LECZ and explore innovative calibration strategies for a 1D hydrodynamic model. Our calibration effort relies on minimal in-situ data from an existing local monitoring program, with validation performed using the data presented in Chapter 2. Additionally, we integrate a modified Manning-Strickler equation to enhance discharge estimations from the 1D model, with the primary objective of improving operational water resource management in Ho Chi Minh City.

KEY FINDINGS

- The best calibration strategy is to use directly measured water level together with indirectly measured discharge data.
- Calibration efforts were challenged by the dynamic tidal conditions and the absence of reliable upstream discharge data.
- Validation against independent measurements showed promising results, indicating the effectiveness of the modified MS equation in enhancing discharge estimates.
- Demonstrated the utility of low-cost 1D hydrodynamic models in understanding complex tidal river dynamics, especially in regions with limited data availability.
- Provided long time-series data (2016-2022) of modelled water levels and discharges available for open-access use by the community.

This chapter has been submitted to Hydrology and Earth System Science and is available as a preprint in EGU sphere. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-1563>. All model output are openly available in the DataSuds repository (IRD, France) at <https://doi.org/10.23708/KLQMSR>. Data reuse is granted under CC-BY license.

Technical Note: Operational calibration and performance improvement for hydrodynamic models in data-scarce coastal areas

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Abstract.

In this study, we address the challenges posed by data scarcity in hydrodynamic modeling within one of the most vulnerable coastal zones in the world—the Saigon-Dongnai tidal river system in South Vietnam. We investigate calibration strategies for a 1D hydrodynamic model using minimal in-situ data obtained from an existing local monitoring program, which provides 48 hours of measurements per month. To further improve discharge estimation from the 1D model, the coupling of a modified Manning-Strickler (MS) equation is explored. Calibration efforts reveal distinct trends in friction coefficients along the river. The introduction of indirectly measured discharge data significantly improves model performance, particularly for the Saigon River branch. Validation against independent measurements demonstrates promising results, with the coupling of the modified MS equation providing improved discharge estimates. The study underscores the complexities of calibrating hydrodynamic models in data-scarce regions, with recommendations for future modeling endeavors including incorporating more accurate upstream boundary conditions. The long time-series of estimated water level and discharge provided by this study have practical implications for water resource management and decision-making in data-scarce estuarine systems and are provided in open-access for operational use.

1 Introduction

Tidal rivers represent intricate systems bridging continental surfaces and the ocean, where water levels and river discharge are profoundly affected by tidal movements. Consequently, the interplay between flooding and tidal constraints on water levels becomes pivotal, particularly in the context of flood protection, pollution management, and climate change adaptation characteristic of these areas. The complex back-and-forth advection coupled with dispersion makes it challenging to predict the propagation of sediment particles or pollutants in such environments.

The Saigon and Dongnai rivers in Vietnam serve as a notable case of a tidal river system, characterized by its flat watershed and, for the Saigon branch, the marginal significance of its net flow compared to tidal influence (Camenen et al., 2021). This river system flows through Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), one of the most vulnerable megacities globally concerning climate

change impacts (Lossouarn et al., 2016). Research has shown the critical need to understand its hydrodynamics for assessing flood risks (Vachaud et al., 2019), managing saline intrusion (Ngo et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2018), and mitigating pollution (Babut et al., 2019; van Emmerik et al., 2019) and eutrophication (Nguyen et al., 2022).

The limited availability of data for evaluating flow and tidal variations in this region negatively impacts the management of these rivers and their source reservoirs. In April 2024, an intense drought swept through southern Vietnam, with temperatures soaring to nearly 40 degrees Celsius, as reported by several news outlets (Orie, 2024; FranceInfo, 2024). This heatwave significantly impacted irrigation activities and fish populations in the Dongnai region, exemplifying the vulnerability of human activities to climate change in such areas. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of modeling efforts for this hydrosystem and the necessity of providing free and open-access time-series data of hydraulic variables. Therefore, numerical modeling emerges as a strategic tool for elucidating the behavior of such complex tidal river systems.

The current body of literature contains a few examples of hydrological and hydraulic modeling efforts in the region. For instance, Camenen et al. (2021) estimated the discharge of the Saigon River using two water level measurement points and a modified Manning-Strickler equation. However, their methodology allows discharge estimation at only one point and relies on continuous water level sensor data. Their discharge estimates are limited to the duration of their measurement campaign from 2017 to 2018. Similarly, Khoi et al. (2022) employed the SWAT model to study the impact of climate change on the Saigon River's discharge. Their model calibration and validation relied on daily discharge data from 1981 to 2000 at four points along the river. Since the study focused on climate impact, the calibration was not as precise as it could have been; the primary requirement was a reference discharge to compare against future discharge estimates, thereby assessing the impact of climate change. This highlights the scarcity of recent, accurate, high temporal resolution discharge data for this system. This is partly due to the fact that traditional river discharge monitoring methods are labor-intensive, require minimum water depths, or necessitate prolonged measurement periods, making them costly and time-consuming (Eltner et al., 2020). Indeed, river discharge measurements have significantly declined over the past 30 years even in developed countries (Zakharova et al., 2020).

Hydraulic data availability varies significantly among rivers, even in regions with relatively good data coverage, and is particularly scarce in tropical areas (Wood et al., 2023; Scheiber et al., 2023). These limitations can be partially mitigated by using model-generated data (Xu et al., 2022; Heinrich et al., 2023). However, model calibration and validation require in-situ data, which is often lacking. The primary obstacle to modeling efforts for the Ho Chi Minh City region is the very limited amount of data for calibration and validation. Despite this, Scheiber et al. (2023) managed to set up an urban flood model for HCMC using only open-access satellite data and monthly mean river discharge from reservoir operations. Nonetheless, the model introduced significant uncertainties and limitations inherent to satellite data, aiming to provide preliminary flood maps rather than deterministic conclusions.

This paper aims to i. demonstrate the challenges of operating a 1D hydrodynamic model with minimal data and ii. to illustrate the utility of a low-cost modeling effort in understanding flow dynamics in a poorly gauged tidal river network. Leveraging the Mage code developed at INRAE Lyon, previously validated on other tidal river systems like the Adour river (Camenen et al., 2022) or the Lower-Seine river (Mendez Rios et al., 2023), the study explores three calibration strategies

for the Saigon-Dongnai river system using scarce in-situ measurements sourced from an already existing local measurement protocol. The calibration approaches put forward are: i. using direct measurements of water level, ii. using discharge data
60 computed from vertical velocity profiles using the velocity index method and iii. using both sources of data. Calibration of friction coefficients poses particular challenges for tidal rivers due to the downstream water level's control over flow dynamics. The River Saigon presents additional difficulties, including the absence of reliable and open-access data on upstream net discharge and the potential impact of extensive canals within the HCMC megalopolis on flow dynamics. Calibration efforts focused on optimizing the Strickler coefficient, K_s , by minimizing a loss function comprising water level and discharge relative
65 root mean square errors (rRMSE). Validation against independent measurements was then performed. Additionally, a modified Manning-Strickler (MS) law was coupled with the hydrodynamic model to improve discharge estimation.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights and practical implications for water resource management and decision-making in data-scarce estuarine systems. The long time-series of estimated water levels and discharge data are made available in open access, offering a critical resource for both scientific and operational use.

70 2 Materials and Methods

In this study we consider three strategies for calibrating a 1D hydrodynamic model over a complex tidal estuary located in a data-scarce region. The hydrodynamic model under consideration is the Mage code, which will be further presented in sub-section 2.2. The flowchart outlining the methodology is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart outlining calibration and validation methods.

The calibration of the Mage model uses minimal in-situ measurements obtained from the Sub-Institute of Hydrometeorology and Climate Change (SIHYMECC), a local Vietnamese agency. The locations for these measurements can be found as white dots in Figure 2. The measurement data, collected using a protocol in place for several years, include hourly river water level and velocity profiles gathered during monthly campaigns of 48-hours from 2016 to 2020. Water level is directly measured with a scale, while discharge is derived from water level and depth-averaged velocity using the velocity index method (Chen et al., 2012). Considering the highly dynamic tidal conditions, the error in discharge estimation is approximately 15% with a minimum error of 150 m³/s (Ruhl and Simpson, 2005).

Due to the quality limitations of discharge data available for calibration, three strategies are employed. Firstly, the Mage model is calibrated solely using water level data and we denote it as MAGE-H. Secondly, Mage is calibrated solely using discharge data, denoted as MAGE-Q. Finally, both water level and discharge data are used for calibration, resulting in MAGE-HQ. In an effort to improve discharge estimation, a modified MS law is coupled with the 1D model. The modification to the classic Manning-Strickler law enables negative slope values and thus, negative water discharge as it is observed in tidally forced rivers (see Section 2.3). This coupling involves feeding slope outputs from MAGE-H and MAGE-HQ into the modified MS law, which is then re-calibrated with discharge data, leading to MS->MAGE-H and MS->MAGE-HQ outputs.

Although coupling a 1D hydrodynamic model with a simplified flow law, such as the Manning-Strickler equation, may initially seem counter-intuitive, it provides essential insights into the dynamics of estuarine rivers. The use of different Strickler coefficients for water levels and discharge, allows for a more detailed calibration of specific components of the system. This approach can enhance the understanding of system behavior by isolating the effects of discharge. It is important to note that recalibrating the MS equation using results from the 1D model aims to refine discharge estimations, despite the fixed water levels that should vary for a modified Strickler coefficient. This refinement can improve operational predictions (as shown in Section 3) for processes such as pollutant advection, nutrient residence times, and salt intrusion. Ultimately, this methodology, when applied with caution, helps to bridge the gap between simplified and detailed modeling approaches, providing a balance between computational efficiency and model accuracy.

The models' validation is conducted using data from the Center of Asian Research on Water (CARE), which includes water level measurements every 15 minutes from October to December 2022 (Rodrigues do Amaral et al., 2023), as well as hourly discharge measurements from four 24-hour Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) campaigns in 2016, 2017, and 2022 (see figure 2, black crosses).

2.1 Case study

The Saigon-Dongnai river system, situated in South Vietnam (Figure 2), comprises two main rivers: the River Dongnai and the River Saigon. The River Dongnai originates from Central Vietnam and flows southward through the Tri An reservoir, while the River Saigon originates in Southeastern Cambodia and flows through to the Dau Tieng Reservoir. Downstream of the Dau Tieng reservoir, the River Saigon traverses a highly urbanized area, Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), which has significant impacts on water quality due to inadequate wastewater treatment (Nguyen et al., 2019). The region features predominantly flat terrain, and the river system is heavily influenced by tides (Camenen et al., 2021).

The instantaneous flow in the Saigon-Dongnai river system can fluctuate between $-2000 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $+2500 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, with the net discharge typically remaining below $100 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and occasionally reaching up to $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during peak flow seasons. The River Saigon, crossing through HCMC, is interlinked with numerous urban canals and serves as a tributary to the River Dongnai. In contrast, the Dongnai river exhibits substantially higher net discharge values, typically an order of magnitude greater, with monthly averages ranging from $200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during the dry season to $1200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during the rainy season (see Figure 4).

Figure 2. Map of the study area. The estuary water bodies (grey) and the Mage model domain (blue) with the Dongnai river (right) and its Saigon river branch (left) can be seen. Locations of river measurements from the Sub-Institute of Hydrometeorology and Climate Change (SYHIMECC, white dots) and from the Center of Asian Research on Water (CARE, black crosses) are also shown. The Saigon river presents six measurement locations namely, Phu Cuong (PC), Hobo 1 (H1), Hobo 2 (H2), Binh Phuoc (BP), Hobo 3 (H3), La Garden (LG) and Phu An (PA). The Dongnai river presents four measurement locations namely, Hoa An (HA), Cat Lai (CL), Nha Be (NB) and Vam Sat (VS). The Vung Tau tidal gauge from the University of Hawaii Sea Level Center (UHSLC) is depicted as a green triangle. The Ho Chi Minh City area and the heavily populated urban center are depicted by a black line and a green polygon, respectively. The area shown in the larger map is represented by the red box in the overview map.

2.2 1D Hydrodynamic modelling: Mage

The model for the Saigon-Dongnai river system was constructed utilizing the PamHyr interface presently written in Java and soon to be accessible as a Python interface (Rouby et al., 2023). This interface offers capabilities for editing network topology, geometry (including cross-sections and mesh), hydraulic conditions (such as friction coefficients and boundary conditions), setting numerical parameters, and visualizing primary results. Subsequently, numerical modeling was conducted using the Mage code (Souhar and Faure, 2009).

The Mage code solves the 1D Barré-de-Saint-Venant equations, comprising the mass conservation equation (Eq. 1) and momentum conservation equation (Eq. 2):

$$\frac{\partial A_w}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = q_{lat}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\beta \cdot \frac{Q^2}{A_w} \right) + g \cdot A_w \cdot \frac{\partial Z}{\partial x} = -g \frac{Q \cdot |Q|}{K_s^2 \cdot A_w \cdot R_h^{4/3}} - g \cdot A_w \cdot J_s + k \cdot q_{lat} \cdot \frac{Q}{A_w}, \quad (2)$$

where A_w represents the wet section, Q the water discharge, q_{lat} a lateral input or output (overflow), Z the water surface elevation, K_s the Strickler coefficient, R_h the hydraulic radius and J_s the a singular head loss. k is a boolean variable such that $k = 1$ if $q_{lat} < 0$, and $k = 0$ otherwise. Friction head losses are modeled using the classical Manning-Strickler law. Mage employs a finite difference method utilizing a Preissman scheme and an iterative approach (Newton-Raphson) for solving the system of non-linear discrete equations (Equations 1 and 2).

Given the geometry of our system domain (Figure 2), the Mage model requires three boundary conditions: (i) a discharge time series at the source of the Saigon River branch, namely, the Dau Tieng reservoir; (ii) a discharge time series at the source of the Dongnai River branch namely, the Tri An reservoir; and (iii) a water level time series at the river mouth. A significant challenge in modeling arises from the lack of data for the upstream boundary conditions, as tidal influence extends to both upstream dams. As an initial approximation, we will use mean monthly discharge from the period of 2012-2016 as reported by Nguyen et al. (2019). The upstream boundary conditions are presented in Figure A1 in the Appendix A. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis showed that the uncertainties on these upstream boundary conditions have a negligible impact on the instantaneous flow dynamics in the river system (Camenen et al., 2023). However, if the instantaneous discharge were to be filtered to obtain the net discharge, we would retrieve the upstream boundary condition. Hence, the model output cannot be used to access the net discharge of these rivers as this variable is an input to the model.

For the downstream boundary condition, we use data from the Vung Tau tide gauge obtained from the research-quality dataset available through the Joint Archive for Sea Level of the University of Hawaii Sea Level Center (UHSLC) (Caldwell et al., 2015).

2.3 Manning-Strickler law for operational applications

Given Mage's challenges in accurately predicting both water level and river discharge (Camenen et al., 2023), we opted to couple this model with a discharge estimation approach that has demonstrated efficacy for different tidal rivers (Camenen

et al., 2017), including for the Saigon River branch (Camenen et al., 2021; Rodrigues do Amaral et al., 2024). Illustrated in
 145 Figure 1, the slope output from Mage feeds into a stage-fall-discharge (SFD) rating curve adapted from the general Manning-
 Strickler law (Eq. 3):

$$Q(t) = \text{sign}(S) \cdot K_s \cdot A_w \cdot R_h^{2/3} \cdot \sqrt{|S(t)|}, \quad (3)$$

with Q representing the water discharge [m^3s^{-1}], K_s the Manning-Strickler coefficient [$\text{m}^{1/3}\text{s}^{-1}$], $R_h = A_w/P_w$ the hydraulic
 radius [m], where A_w denotes the wet section [m^2] and P_w the wet perimeter [m]. The term $\text{sign}(S)$ equates to the sign of the
 150 slope, S , taking on values of +1 or -1. The energy slope, S [-], is assumed to be equal to the water slope and is derived from
 the water surface elevation output by Mage around the point where discharge estimation is desired. All variables (S , A_w , R_h)
 except K_s are as outputted by the Mage model. However, this equation can only yield a discharge value for a specific point in
 the river. This point must be a location where discharge measurements exist, as the equation requires calibration of the Strickler
 coefficient, K_s . Consequently, this integration of a 1D hydrodynamic model and a simplified flow law only has an interest at
 155 locations where SIHYMECC measurements exist (Figure 2, white dots).

2.4 Modelling calibration strategy

The calibration of Strickler coefficients in the Mage model follows a sequential approach, starting from downstream to upstream
 in accordance with tide propagation. Initially, the Dongnai River is divided into three reaches: two before its confluence with
 the Saigon River and one between the confluence and the Tri An reservoir. Subsequently, the Saigon River is divided into seven
 160 reaches: five within the urban center and two between the city center and the Dau Tieng reservoir. The calibration exclusively
 utilizes data from SIHYMECC (Figure 1).

For each reach, a bounded Brent's algorithm (Grund, 1979; Brent, 2013) is employed to minimize a loss function. This
 is implemented using Python's `minimize_scalar` function from the Scipy library (Virtanen et al., 2020). The loss function
 (Equation 4) is a weighted sum of the relative root mean square error for water level (rRMSE_H) and discharge (rRMSE_Q)
 165 across all measurement locations. The loss function $f(K_s)$ is formulated as:

$$f(K_s) = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \cdot [\text{rRMSE}_H^i(K_s) + \text{rRMSE}_Q^i(K_s)], \quad (4)$$

$$\text{rRMSE}_H^i(K_s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\frac{H_{\text{true}}^j - H_{\text{model}}^j(K_s)}{H_{\text{true}}^j} \right]^2}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{rRMSE}_Q^i(K_s) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\frac{Q_{\text{true}}^j - Q_{\text{model}}^j(K_s)}{Q_{\text{true}}^j} \right]^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $n = 7$ denotes the number of SIHYMECC measurement locations, C_i represents the weight assigned to each measure-
 170 ment location, and rRMSE_H^i and rRMSE_Q^i are the water level and discharge rRMSE for location i , respectively. The superscript
 m represents each value in the time-series of water level and discharge. The weights (C_i) are constant values between 0 and 1,

with higher importance assigned to measurement locations near the urban city center, as detailed in Table 1. This prioritization ensures that the model performance is given more significance around Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), which is the focal point for flooding applications and other environmental impacts. By weighting the measurements in this manner, we aim to enhance the model's accuracy in areas that are most critical for urban planning and risk mitigation efforts.

Minimizing Equation 4 yields the optimal K_s value for a given reach within the Mage code.

Table 1. Weights assigned to each measurement location for the calibration of the Mage model.

Location	PC	BP	PA	NB	HA	CL	VS
Weight	0.8	1	1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.5

For the modified MS equation, the Strickler coefficient is calibrated against discharge data using the same algorithm as for the Mage model. However, this calibration is performed separately for each location and focuses solely on discharge data. Therefore, the loss function to be minimized is exclusively Equation 6. The calibration of the modified MS equation constitutes a secondary phase of calibration on discharge, as the slope input is already derived from the calibrated Mage model. It is important to note the the discharge data used in this phase of calibration is the same as the one used for the Mage model calibration. Additionally, it is important to reinforce that the modified MS equation can only be applied pointwise, meaning that discharge output is available only at the exact locations where the equation is calibrated, i.e., locations where discharge data is available, notably at the SIHYMECC locations.

The validation of the models utilizes independent measurements from CARE (Figure 1). Two performance metrics are employed: rRMSE and the coefficient of determination, R^2 . These metrics are computed as follows:

$$\text{rRMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\frac{y_{\text{true}}^j - y_{\text{model}}^j}{y_{\text{true}}^j} \right]^2} \times 100, \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m (y_{\text{true}}^j - y_{\text{model}}^j)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^m (y_{\text{true}}^j - \bar{y}_{\text{true}})^2}. \quad (8)$$

where y_{true} and y_{model} are the measurement and the model output of the variable of interest, respectively, i.e. water level or discharge.

3 Results

Three calibration strategies were tested for the Mage model: calibration solely based on water level, solely on discharge, or on both parameters simultaneously. For the coupled modified MS equation models, namely MS<-MAGE-H and MS<-MAGE-HQ, calibration was conducted exclusively using discharge data. Calibration results for rRMSE and R^2 can be found in Figure B1 in Appendix B. For the validation results, the relative Root Mean Square Error (rRMSE) metric is presented in Tables 3 and

2, while the coefficient of determination (R^2) can be referenced in Figures C1 and C2 in Appendix C. The resulting Strickler coefficient values across the river extent are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Strickler coefficients obtained from the calibration of the Mage model. Solid lines in red, green and blue correspond to MAGE-H, MAGE-Q and MAGE-HQ. The blue and orange squares correspond to the MS<-MAGE-HQ and MS<-MAGE-H at the locations of SIHYMECC measurements.

For the Saigon River, when calibrating the model using water level measurements only (MAGE-H, depicted in red in Figure 3), Strickler coefficients (K_s) exhibit an increasing trend as distance from the reservoir increases, with some variability around the urban city center (100 km to 150 km). When calibrating the model using discharge data only (MAGE-Q, in green in Figure 3), K_s values experience further increments for most parts of the river. Furthermore, introducing discharge data into the calibration process (MAGE-HQ, shown in blue in Figure 3) results in increased K_s values throughout the river, except near the confluence.

Figure 4 presents validation data from the ADCP campaigns plotted against model output. These data, distinct from those employed in model calibration, stand as fully independent from the model's output (see Figure 1). For the Saigon River, the Strickler coefficients were found to be larger for the MAGE-Q calibration compared to the MAGE-HQ and MAGE-H calibrations. This results in larger discharge amplitudes, as indicated by the red, blue, and green curves in Figure 4. Moreover, the rRMSE between ADCP measurements and model output substantially decreases for the MAGE-Q and MAGE-HQ calibration (refer to Table 2), indicating a significant improvement in model capability despite the lower quality of discharge data compared to water level measurements. Table 2 also demonstrates that calibrating without utilizing water level data results in an improvement in rRMSE for the Saigon river. However, this is not the case for the Dongnai river as introducing discharge data into the calibration effort provides comparable performance to using only water level measurements. Table 2 shows that

MAGE-HQ calibration yields better results than MAGE-H and MAGE-Q as calibrating using discharge data only leads to overestimation. However, all models are behaving similarly for the asymmetric tide (ADCP campaign of 2016, Figure 4c). In this case the modified MS model does not bring any notable improvements. In terms of net outflow, the modified MS coupling may slightly modify results (Figure 4).

Table 2. Validation results for rRMSE [%] between model discharge and ADCP campaigns. The ADCP data was not used for the calibration efforts and thus, model output and validation data are fully independent.

	MAGE-H	MAGE-Q	MAGE-HQ	MS<-MAGE-H	MS<-MAGE-HQ
PC 2016	-148	-62	-75	38	31
PC 2017	-148	-68	-78	49	51
HA 2016	31	36	23	43	52
HA 2022	-38	47	29	36	40

For operational purposes, achieving the most accurate discharge estimation is crucial regardless of the method. Table 2 reveals that coupling the modified MS equation reduces the rRMSE of the Mage model discharge output by half during the symmetric tide of the 2016 campaign and by approximately 20% during the asymmetric tide of the 2017 campaign for the Saigon River. However, errors still range between 31% and 51%, underscoring the challenge of accurately estimating discharge in such dynamic tidal rivers. Conversely, the coupling provides similar or slightly worse results than Mage for the Dongnai River.

Introducing discharge data in the calibration efforts marginally impacts water level output, resulting in slight increases in rRMSE values at most stations (Table 3). However, this calibration approach does not significantly affect the rRMSE values between validation data and model output. The rRMSE difference between MAGE-H and MAGE-Q is consistently below 10%. Additionally, the rRMSE between MAGE-H and MAGE-HQ exhibits minimal differences, always below 5%. Consequently, regardless of the calibration approach, the model effectively reproduces the dynamic nature of water level fluctuations, which is also demonstrated by the R^2 values exceeding 0.80 at every measurement station (refer to Figure C1 in Appendix B).

Table 3. Validation results for rRMSE [%] between model water level and water level measurements.

	MAGE-H	MAGE-Q	MAGE-HQ
H1	30	38	30
H2	28	32	27
H3	25	27	24
LG	25	32	30
HA	31	41	33
NB	17	21	18

Figure 4. Discharge time-series and net outflow comparison between ADCP campaigns and model output. Black dots with uncertainty bar represent the ADCP measurements. Solid lines with dots represent MAGE-H, MAGE-Q and MAGE-HQ in red, green and blue, respectively. Dashed lines with squares represent the MS<-MAGE-H and MS<-MAGE-HQ in orange and blue, respectively. a) and b) Campaigns of September 2016 and March 2017, at the Phu Cuong (PC) location in the Saigon river during a symmetric and asymmetric tide, respectively. c) and d) Campaigns of September 2016 and November 2022, at the Hoa An (HA) location in the Dongnai river during an asymmetric and symmetric tide, respectively.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

230 The calibration strategies employed in this study provide insights into the hydrodynamic modeling of dynamic tidal rivers, particularly the Saigon and Dongnai rivers in Southeast Asia. The three calibration strategies tested for the Mage model, focusing on water level, discharge, or both parameters simultaneously, offer valuable understanding of model behavior under varying calibration conditions with scarce data. Additionally, the coupling of the modified Manning-Strickler (MS) equation with the Mage model presents a novel approach to enhance discharge estimation for operational purposes, albeit with mixed

235 results across different river systems.

In this tidal-dominated system, the methodology for calibrating friction coefficients involved starting from downstream reaches and then proceeding to calibrate upstream reaches following tidal wave propagation. The model yielded very accurate results for both water levels and discharges in the Dong-Nai River. However, achieving a satisfactory fit for both datasets in the Saigon River proved more challenging. The calibration effort was notably affected by the system's complexity, characterized by significant tidal discharges and low net discharges originating from the watershed. Notably, the introduction of discharge data from measured vertical velocity profiles significantly impacts model performance, leading to improved accuracy in discharge estimation, especially for the Saigon River. However, the effectiveness of this approach varies, with the Dongnai River demonstrating comparable performance across different calibration strategies.

Modeling efforts are challenging due to the tradeoff between model simplicity for operational use and the accurate representation of physical phenomena. For example, the Mage model does not effectively capture tidal wave attenuation, and different calibration strategies result in only negligible improvements. However, when we couple the Manning-Strickler law with a second calibration step, the improvements become significant. This operational trick enhances discharge accuracy, as validation efforts demonstrate. Nonetheless, the one-dimensional nature of the model is not the limiting factor in this case. Using a higher-dimensional model would be impractical, as calibration would require more data, including higher-dimensional data such as velocity fields, which are hardly available in data-scarce regions like the one under study.

The calibration results reveal distinct trends in Strickler coefficient, K_s , values along the river extent, reflecting variations in channel roughness. We observe significant variations in K_s values depending on the calibration strategy and after implementing modified MS coupling. The Strickler coefficient represents the hydraulic roughness of the channel bed, influencing water levels, flow velocity and thus discharge. For instance, a higher Strickler coefficient indicates smoother channel conditions, allowing for faster flow velocities, while a lower coefficient suggests rougher conditions, resulting in slower velocities. In our study, we observed a range of K_s values from a very rough value of $10 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$ to a smoother $50 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$, indicating substantial variability in channel roughness along the river network. These variations illustrate the challenges of modeling tidally influenced river systems. The Strickler coefficient influences discharge rates during both rising and falling tidal phases, with higher coefficients typically resulting in increased discharges. The Saigon and Dongnai rivers exhibit asymmetrical flow patterns due to tidal amplitudes, morphology, and coastal features. The impact of the K_s value on discharge varies with the dominant tidal phase and river response to tidal forcing, emphasizing the importance of timing in data collection for calibration and validation. Moreover, the physical behavior of the river may vary at different tidal phases, affecting the Strickler coefficient.

The validation of model outputs against independent measurements underscores the importance of incorporating discharge data for enhancing model capability. Despite the challenges associated with accurately estimating discharge in dynamic tidal rivers, the Mage model and the MS<-MAGE coupling demonstrate promising results, especially when considering the operational implications of discharge estimation. The impact of calibration efforts on water level output highlights the trade-off between accuracy and simplicity in hydrodynamic modeling. While introducing discharge data may marginally affect water level output, the model retains its ability to capture the dynamic fluctuations in water level, as evidenced by high coefficient of determination (R^2) values across measurement stations.

270 While the current model provides sufficiently good estimates of discharge dynamics within the Saigon-Dongnai system, further refinements are needed, particularly regarding the use of accurately measured upstream boundary conditions. Accurate upstream discharge values from the reservoirs are crucial for model precision. Given that the model is one-dimensional (1D), it inherently requires net discharge as a boundary condition input, preventing the derivation of net discharge directly from the model's results. Consequently, the primary goal of the modeling effort is to obtain more precise instantaneous discharge and
275 water level estimates, incorporating tidal dynamics throughout the entire river system. This objective has been successfully achieved, and the resulting time series data can provide valuable insights to reservoir managers controlling the river system. Additionally, the modeling effort can be significantly improved if reservoir discharge data are accurately measured and shared with the scientific community. Tidal gauge data, such as those from the Vung Tau station (coastal boundary condition), are already available in near real-time and openly accessible through the University of Hawaii Sea Level Center's website. There-
280 fore, it is imperative that reservoir discharge data are similarly monitored and made publicly available, as they play a crucial role in improving modeling efforts.

In recent years, there has been growing interest in leveraging advanced statistical and machine learning techniques to enhance the calibration of hydrodynamic models. However, this is not possible in data-scarce regions as these methods rely on large amounts of data. Similarly, machine learning algorithms and AI systems require the leveraging of large datasets for au-
285 tomating and optimizing the calibration process. On the other hand, Bayesian methods offer a robust framework for calibrating hydrodynamic models (Mendez Rios et al., 2023), thereby improving parameter estimation and predictive accuracy. Integrating these techniques with traditional calibration approaches for 1D models like Mage holds great potential for improving model performance and reducing uncertainty in predictions. Future research endeavors could explore the applicability and effectiveness of such methodologies in the context of dynamic tidal river systems, thereby advancing our understanding and predictive
290 capabilities in hydrodynamic modeling. In future modelling works, the consideration of canal network impact on the rivers is also recommended. Subsequently, the model could be used to analyze significant flood events. Coupling the model with an advection-dispersion model like AdisTS developed at INRAE (Launay et al., 2019) would also be beneficial in understanding pollutant dispersion in this complex system.

Overall, this study sheds light on the complexities of calibrating hydrodynamic models in data-scarce regions and under-
295 scores the importance of incorporating discharge data, even if it has important uncertainties associated with it, for enhancing model accuracy. The model outputs have practical implications for water resource management and decision-making in this estuary system and all model output is provided in open-access format in Rodrigues Do Amaral et al. (2024).

Code and data availability. The Mage 1D hydrodynamic model is developed by INRAE (French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment), its source code is written in FORTRAN and can be downloaded here: <https://gitlab.irstea.fr/jean-baptiste.faure/mage>
300 [accessed 4. Apr. 2024]. The data and related documentations that support the findings of this study are openly available in DataSuds repository (IRD, France) at <https://doi.org/10.23708/KLQMSR>. Data reuse is granted under CC-BY license.

Appendix A: Mage model boundary conditions

Figure A1. Boundary conditions used in Mage model: example for the year 2018. a) Upstream boundary condition for the Saigon river branch: discharge at the Dau Tieng reservoir. b) Upstream boundary condition for the Dongnai river: discharge at the Tri An reservoir. c) Downstream boundary condition at the mouth of the river Dongnai: water level at the Vung Tau tidal gauge.

Appendix B: Calibration results: rRMSE and R^2

Figure B1. Calibration results for the Mage model and for the MS<-MAGE coupling. rRMSE and R^2 between model output and calibration data from the SIHYMECC measurement locations are shown. Dark red, green and dark blue bars represent the MAGE-H, MAGE-Q and MAGE-HQ results. Light red and light blue bars represent the MS<-MAGE-H and MS<-MAGE-HQ results.

Appendix C: Validation results: R^2

Figure C1. Linear regression lines and R^2 values between CARE water level measurements and model water level output. The black dashed line represents the $y = x$ line. Red, green and blue circles represent the MAGE-H, MAGE-Q and MAGE-HQ results. Solid lines represent linear regressions for each model with the same color code. a) to d) show results for Saigon locations H1, H2, H3 and LG. e) and f) show results for the locations in the Dongnai river HA and NB, respectively.

Figure C2. Linear regression lines and R^2 values between ADCP discharge and model discharge. The black dotted line represents the $y = x$ line. Red, green and blue circles represent the MAGE-H, MAGE-Q and MAGE-HQ results and blue and orange squares the MS<-MAGE-H and MS<-MAGE-HQ results. Solid lines represent linear regressions for each model with the same color code as the circles and squares. a) and b) ADCP campaigns of September 2016 and March 2017, at the Phu Cuong (PC) location in the Saigon river during a symmetric and asymmetric tide, respectively. c) and d) ADCP campaigns of September 2016 and November 2022, at the Hoa An (HA) location in the Dongnai river during an asymmetric and symmetric tide, respectively.

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4.2 CONCLUSION

This chapter underscores the critical role of accurate hydrodynamic modelling in managing tidal river systems, particularly in data-scarce regions like the low elevation coastal zone surrounding Ho Chi Minh City. By exploring various calibration strategies and coupling a modified Manning-Strickler equation with a 1D hydrodynamic model, the study offers valuable insights and practical tools for improving discharge estimations.

Further modelling improvements could be achieved if better upstream boundary condition data is available. The difficulties encountered in this chapter could be mitigated by the contributions of the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission, with its high spatial resolution water level and slope measurements. This possibility is studied in Chapter 5, which was prepared before SWOT data became available for the region.

5

Enhancing discharge estimation from SWOT satellite data in a tropical tidal river environment

SUMMARY

Building on the challenges of studying extreme events and modelling in data-scarce regions outlined in Chapters 2 and 3, this chapter explores the potential of the upcoming Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite mission to enhance our understanding of the hydrology of Ho Chi Minh City's area. Specifically, we focus on improving river discharge estimates for the Saigon River. We present a methodology to simulate SWOT data using in-situ data from the field campaign detailed in Chapter 3. We investigate the variability of expected SWOT errors through a Monte Carlo approach and propose a methodology to improve them. This study anticipates the long-term contribution of SWOT data to improve our knowledge of dynamic coastal regions and proposes an adaptable approach applicable to similar data-scarce environments. The content of this chapter was produced prior to availability of SWOT products.

KEY FINDINGS

- We developed a methodology to enhance discharge estimation from SWOT data, using simulated SWOT products at a 200-meter node resolution.
- The methodology results in a reduction of mean relative RMSE from 1400 m³/s to 180 m³/s and an increase of R² from 0.31 to 0.95 between true discharge and estimated discharge.
- The percentage of Monte Carlo particles meeting the 30% relative RMSE threshold increased from 0% to 79%.
- We demonstrate the feasibility of obtaining reliable discharge estimates from SWOT data in complex coastal areas where river slope is of the same order of magnitude as SWOT river slope error.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Enhancing discharge estimation from SWOT satellite data in a tropical tidal river environment

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Abstract

The Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission aims to provide essential data on river width, height and slope in order to estimate worldwide river discharge accurately. This mission offers a powerful tool for monitoring river discharge in dynamic coastal areas, like the Saigon-Dongnai estuary in Southern Vietnam. However, estimating discharge of tidally-influenced rivers using SWOT measurements can be challenging when hydraulic variables have the same order of magnitude as SWOT measurement errors. In this paper we present a methodology to enhance discharge estimation accuracy from SWOT measurements based on simulated SWOT products at the 200 meter node resolution and varying river reach size. We assess measurement error variability and its impact on discharge estimation by employing a Monte Carlo analysis. Our approach significantly improved discharge estimation in the Saigon tidal river, reducing RMSE from 1400 m³/s to 180 m³/s and increasing R² from 0.31 to 0.95. Notably, the percentage of Monte Carlo particles meeting the 30% rRMSE threshold rose from 0% to 79%. This study underscores the feasibility of obtaining reliable discharge estimates from SWOT data in complex coastal areas where hydraulic variables are of the same order of magnitude as SWOT errors. Additionally, the proposed methodology to improve discharge estimation from SWOT measurements is widely adaptable as it can be applied to similar regions and can be combined with any discharge estimation method.

1. Introduction

Geophysical processes occurring at the surface of the Earth in low elevation coastal zones (LECZs) are primarily regulated by the interplay of river discharge and the intricate dynamics imposed by the coastal ocean. Within this transitional zone, there exists a region often referred to as “the tidal river”. This area is profoundly influenced by tidal movements, surges, and the variations in mean sea level but remains devoid of significant salinity. It is a stretch of the river that is impacted by these marine forcing processes, yet it has historically received relatively

access publication: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352340923002664?via%3Dihub> This data can be downloaded directly from the following public repository: <https://dataverse.ird.fr/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.23708/NKQDNB>.

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little attention from the geophysical research community [1]. Notably, these tidal river reaches can extend inland for hundreds of kilometers, and in the case of larger rivers, they often rival or surpass the estuary in terms of both length and sometimes even area. Predicting water levels in tidal rivers or estuaries is a challenge due to the highly variable flow conditions that characterize these environments. The hydrological dynamics within a tidal river are inherently distinct, marked by a constant flux in water levels driven by the interplay of hydro-meteo-marine phenomena. Consequently, the hydrodynamic processes governing tidal rivers defy simplification, showcasing traits such as complexity, non-stationarity, and nonlinear behavior [2].

Remote sensing observations play a pivotal role in providing information on the spatial variations of water surface elevations across diverse hydrodynamic scenarios. In the last two decades, satellite radar altimeters, which excel at gauging sea level fluctuations, have introduced significant advancements in our understanding of ocean dynamics [3, 4]. However, their utility has been notably impeded when applied to coastal environments, where data accuracy decreases as these instruments approach coastal regions. This limitation is further exacerbated by the inherent constraints of nadir altimetry missions, exemplified by missions like Topography Experiment/POSEIDON (TOPEX/POSEIDON) and the Jason series [5]. These missions grapple with challenges posed by inter-track spacing and temporal resolution, which curtail their ability to effectively observe smaller-scale coastal phenomena, including shelf tides, coastal tides, wind-induced effects, and storm surges [6]. A transformative shift in the landscape of coastal remote sensing is to be expected with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration/Centre National d'Études Spatiales (NASA/CNES) Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite mission, launched on December 15th, 2022.

The SWOT satellite signifies a leap forward in our capacity to estimate global river discharge, substantially enriching our observational foundation for understanding worldwide hydrological phenomena [7]. River discharge measurements offer a comprehensive synthesis of upstream water cycle processes, rendering them indispensable data resources for gaining insights into hydrology across scales, from watershed dynamics to continental-scale patterns. Nonetheless, a substantial portion of the world's rivers remains unmonitored, owing to various constraints encompassing resource limitations and data sharing challenges [8, 9] especially in the inter-tropical zone [10]. Remote sensing techniques aimed at gauging river discharge hold the potential to extend global observation capabilities, even in regions lacking conventional gauging infrastructure. However, this expanded reach comes with trade-offs. Remote sensing methods generally entail compromises, encompassing reduced measurement precision, accuracy, and temporal sampling frequency when compared to in-situ discharge monitoring practices [11]. SWOT's capability of capturing parameters such as river water surface elevation (WSE) (also referred to simply as river water level), top width, and longitudinal water surface slope (also referred simply as slope) [12] enables estimations of river discharge.

The SWOT satellite, equipped with advanced radar altimetry technology and unprecedented spatial resolution, offers an innovative opportunity to quantify river discharge across the globe with unparalleled accuracy. However, harnessing SWOT data for discharge estimation requires comprehensive evaluation and optimization, particularly in complex hydrological settings such as tidal rivers. The SWOT team's objective for the coastal ocean is to "quantify the water exchanges between coastal regions, estuaries, deltas, and wetlands" [13]. It is in accordance with this objective that we propose an evaluation of the capability of future SWOT satellite measurements in estimating water discharge in the Saigon river situated in Southern Vietnam. The Saigon river is a tidal river located in a densely populated, highly complex LECZ. The study of the hydrodynamics and hydrology of the Saigon River is important in water resource management, flood control, and navigation in the Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC)

megalopolis. Nonetheless, this case study has the potential to be applied to other megalopolis sharing comparable human and geophysical environments.

Another reason for the interest in how SWOT satellite measurements can be used to estimate tidal river discharge is the alarming flood vulnerability in coastal and other low-lying cities [14]. In particular, HCMC is one of the most vulnerable cities in the world with respect to climate change [15]. Some of these vulnerabilities are water-related issues such as lack of urban services like drinking-water management, sanitation, rainwater drainage and compound flooding. Specifically, flooding vulnerability is linked to sea level rise, rainfall intensification, storm surges and ground subsidence while 65% of the city is located at less than 1.5 m above sea level. In addition, HCMC is home to almost 10 million inhabitants and its population grows at about 3% per year with these risks posing a threat to many livelihoods [15]. Several studies consider HCMC as a hotspot of vulnerability to climate change [16–21]. However, there has been little comprehensive studies regarding the potential of SWOT in an estuary setting such as the one in this study area. Furthermore, we suggest an innovative approach to simulate SWOT data and enhance its quality. This method is adaptable and can be applied to other intricate tidal river systems within dynamic coastal areas.

Given the accessibility of hydrological variables derived from SWOT, characterized by specific resolutions and accuracy thresholds, the scientific community has put forward multiple methodologies for estimating river discharge. These methodologies are constructed upon distinct assumptions and simplifications. For instance, Durand et al. 2016 [22] conducted a comparative analysis, evaluating the efficacy of five different algorithms that leverage SWOT-like observations in assessing flow rates across 19 major rivers. While this examination revealed that, in nearly every case (specifically, 14 out of 19 instances) at least one approach yielded satisfactory performance as indicated by a root mean square error below the 35% threshold, it underscores that achieving precise and dependable discharge estimation remains a topic of concern. However, SWOT capabilities for estuaries and tidal rivers have received comparatively little attention [5, 23, 24]. This calls for continued research efforts in the field to enhance the accuracy and reliability of these estimations, particularly in LECZs, a focus that this paper seeks to address.

In this paper we propose an original methodology to obtain high spatial resolution water level time-series directly from in-situ measurements. Then, we re-create SWOT-like measurements of water level and slope along the Saigon river, coupled with innovative reach size selection to estimate river discharge. Through an extensive analysis, we evaluate the performance of this methodology under various conditions, including reach sizes, discharge values, and error considerations. Our investigation explores the limitations of the expected SWOT-like discharge estimation errors and proposes an enhanced approach that leverages SWOT data more effectively. We assess the impact of reach size, a critical parameter in SWOT-based discharge estimation, on accuracy and computational efficiency. By conducting a Monte Carlo analysis, we scrutinize the sensitivity of discharge estimates to errors inherent in SWOT-like measurements [25, 26]. Ultimately, this research advances the broader goal of harnessing the potential of SWOT measurements to enhance our understanding of tidally forced riverine systems, contributing to improved water resource management and environmental conservation efforts in vulnerable LECZ.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area description

The Saigon-Dongnai River system is located in Southern Vietnam (Fig 1). The Saigon river branch is a complex river system, subject to several human and environmental interactions

Fig 1. Map of the study area. The Saigon-Dongnai river system and the two SWOT satellite swaths (hatch pattern) and nadir lines (dotted line) that cover the area. The river is covered by both swaths in areas where the red and blue hatch patterns intersect and form squares. The water level gauges namely, Cu Chi (CC), Hobo 1 (H1), Hobo 2 (H2), Hobo 3 (H3), La Garden (LG) and Dongnai 2 (DN2) are shown as well as the ADCP campaign locations (triangles). The spline spatial interpolation nodes at every kilometer is illustrated as white dots. The area shown in the larger map is represented by the green box in the overview map. Basemap used in main map can be downloaded from www.igismap.com/vietnam-shapefile-download-country-boundaryline-polygon (under CC BY 3.0 IGO licence). For terms of use please see: <https://map.igismap.com/terms-of-services>. Basemap used in the overview map downloaded from www.naturalearthdata.com/downloads/10m-cultural-vectors/10m-admin-0-countries (public domain data see www.naturalearthdata.com/about/terms-of-use/ for the terms of use).

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before flowing into the Dongnai River and finally, into coastal waters. It flows from its source in Cambodia to the Dau Tieng Reservoir (270 km² and 1,580 · 10⁶ m³) before passing through the HCMC megalopolis. In total, it is 225 km long and its catchment area has a surface of about 4,800 km². The Dau Tieng Reservoir was designed for flood control, water supply, and preventing saltwater intrusion [27, 28]. The hydrodynamics of the Saigon River are influenced

by various factors including tidal processes, freshwater inflows, and sediment transport. Tidal dynamics play the most significant role in shaping the river's behavior, with tidal amplitudes ranging from 1 (neap tide) to 4 meters (spring tide) [29] and water discharge ranging between $-1500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $2000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [30]. Tidal fluctuations dominate the totality of the river Saigon from the confluence with the Dongnai river to the outlet of the Dau Tieng reservoir. In fact, at the seasonal scale the river water levels are controlled by the coastal water levels [20].

The HCMC megalopolis, with a population of approximately 10 million inhabitants, is located along the banks of the Saigon River and is the largest and most densely populated city in Vietnam. The population is concentrated in the heart of the city, with the urban districts housing about 6.7 million inhabitants [31]. The city's rapid urbanization, economic development, and population growth have posed challenges including river pollution, flood risk, and wastewater management [32, 33].

2.2. Measurement campaign

A high-resolution dataset comprising water level measurements and Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) campaigns was collected during a 2-month field campaign conducted in the study region, as part of a collaborative effort between the Centre Asiatique de Recherche sur L'Eau (CARE, Vietnam) and the Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement (IGE, France). The campaign was specifically designed to support the hydraulic study aimed at assessing the applicability of the SWOT satellite to the Saigon-Dongnai estuary system. The dataset includes water level measurements at six selected locations along the Saigon River, namely Cu Chi (CC), Hobo 1 (H1), Hobo 2 (H2), Hobo 3 (H3), La Garden (LG) and Dongnai 2 (DN2) (triangles in Fig 1). The selection of these locations was bound by on-site constraints (inaccessibility to the riverbank, challenges in sensor installation, among others) and aimed to align with two primary criteria: i. comprehensively covering key sections of the Saigon River, particularly within Ho Chi Minh City and immediately upstream, areas of significant societal interest and impact; and ii. maintaining a distance of approximately 10 km between sensors to emulate the spatial resolution of SWOT reach products.

These measurements were obtained by a submersed brick-and-pipe installation of Onset HOBO U20L-01 water level loggers measuring absolute pressure at a time resolution of 15 minutes. To ensure accuracy, the water level measurements were barometrically compensated using air pressure measurements. The vertical reference point of the pressure sensors is different and unknown. In order to be able to compare the signals at different locations, all signals are normalized [34]. Furthermore, we use a slope correction parameter in our discharge estimation method that is used to compensate for the fact that the reference points of each location are different and unknown (explained in Sect. 2.6). Additionally, discharge measurements were obtained through three 24-hour ADCP campaigns during both symmetric and asymmetric tidal regimes at two locations (yellow triangles in Fig 1). Despite its relatively short duration, the dataset provides unprecedented spatial and temporal resolution for water level and discharge measurements. The synchronous recording of multiple water level sensors along the river enables the study of water surface slope profiles. Furthermore, the concurrent discharge measurements facilitate the calibration of the discharge estimation law proposed in this paper. More detailed information on this dataset can be found in [34].

2.3. The SWOT mission

The SWOT mission, led by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the French space agency (Centre National d'Études Spatiales, CNES), in collaboration with the Canadian and UK space agencies (CSA and UKSA, respectively), aims to contribute to the

fundamental understanding of the Earth system by providing high spatial resolution and global measurements for ocean and inland water. The launch of SWOT took place on December 16, 2022, and the mission is currently in the science phase. The first validated river products of water surface elevation (WSE), width, and slope are expected to be available in April 2024. The mission focuses on ocean and terrestrial water bodies including lakes, reservoirs, wetlands, and rivers, with specific criteria such as surface area exceeding 62,500 m² and rivers wider than 100 m, with the goal of potentially reaching 50 m [12, 35, 36]. The SWOT satellite's core payload includes a Ka-band radar interferometer (KaRIn) operating at a frequency of 35.75 GHz (wavelength of 8.6 mm) and with a near-nadir incidence angle [37].

In terms of spatial coverage and revisit time, the SWOT satellite aims to achieve near-global coverage between 78°S and 78°N with a revisit time of approximately 21 days. The satellite will employ radar observations with pixels of about 6 m in the azimuth direction and varying from 10 to 60 m in the direction perpendicular to the azimuth. To meet mission requirements for observation accuracy, averaging procedures will be applied to the radar data [7, 12, 38]. The resulting SWOT products will be available within two swaths of 50 km width, separated by a gap of 20 km known as the “nadir gap”.

The SWOT mission's capabilities enable the measurement of water extent, water surface elevation, and slope, facilitating the estimation of river and global storage variation at sub-monthly, seasonal, and annual time scales [12]. The SWOT observations, with their finer spatial resolution, provide a global inventory of terrestrial water bodies, offering insights into lakes, reservoirs, wetlands, and rivers. The relative error for water-surface-area measurements is targeted to be less than 15% [9]. Additionally, SWOT products combined with hydraulic models or flow laws show potential to estimate instantaneous river discharge within 35% root-mean-square error [22].

The Saigon-Dongnai river system is monitored by two SWOT orbits: 90 and 271 (Fig 1 red and blue, respectively). This system will therefore receive two observations within the period of 21 days (i.e., satellite revisit time) namely, on day 4 (orbit 90) and day 10 (orbit 271). Together both orbits cover the entirety of the system at least once per 21 day period. The Saigon portion of the system is observed in a heterogeneous way in both space and time due to the nadir gaps on both orbits intercepting the river. Starting from the upstream Dau Tieng reservoir, the first 56 kms are observed on day 10; the section from kilometers 56 to 94 is observed on day 4 and the remaining section from kilometer 94 to the confluence with the Dongnai river is monitored on day 4 and 10. On the other hand, the Dongnai river is observed in its entirety by both orbits' right swaths.

The section of the Saigon river under scope extends from the CC water level gauge to the DN2 gauge downstream of the Saigon confluence with the Dongnai river (Fig 1, triangles). This section of about 90 km in length will be monitored once per orbit from CC to a few kilometers downstream of H1 and twice per orbit on the remaining river reaches up to DN2. The main interest of this study is to understand the potential of SWOT observations to observe instantaneous discharge in a low elevation tidal river given SWOT's expected errors. Hence, the temporal resolution of the SWOT observations is not taken into account.

2.4. Spatial interpolation of in-situ measurements of water level

In order to provide spatial continuity to the data, we chose to employ a quadratic spline interpolation technique. We explored alternative interpolation techniques, including higher-order polynomials and Kriging, but these methods did not yield results as favorable as the second-degree polynomial interpolation (results not presented). The alternative techniques frequently introduced unrealistic characteristics into the water surface due to their increased degrees of

freedom. To define the spatial framework for our interpolation, we used the SWOT River Database (SWORD) [39]. The SWORD database contains the SWOT mission's river vector products for each SWOT overpass, as detailed in the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) internal document [25]. These vector data products are the definition of SWOT river reaches and nodes for all observable rivers (width > 100 m) in the world. The database provides high-resolution river nodes (200 m) and reaches (≈ 10 km). The 200 meter nodes defined in SWORD for the Saigon river serve as the basis for our spatial interpolation.

The quadratic spline interpolation technique was employed to estimate water levels at unmeasured locations between the in-situ measurement points. This method utilizes a piecewise continuous quadratic polynomial to fit the available data points and provide a smooth representation of the water level distribution along the river. The quadratic spline interpolation relies on the assumption that the river water level between two measurement points can be approximated by a quadratic function. Let's consider a set of in-situ measurements at distinct locations along the river, denoted as (x_i, y_i) , where x_i represents the spatial coordinate and y_i represents the measured water level at that point. The quadratic spline interpolant, $I(x)$, between two consecutive data points (x_i, y_i) and (x_{i+1}, y_{i+1}) , can be expressed as follows [40]:

$$I(x) = a_i(x - x_i)^2 + b_i(x - x_i) + c_i, \quad \text{for } x_i \leq x \leq x_{i+1} \quad (1)$$

where a_i , b_i , and c_i are the coefficients of the quadratic polynomial determined by solving a system of equations based on the boundary conditions and smoothness constraints. These constraints ensure that the interpolant is continuous and has continuous first derivatives at the data points. Boundary conditions define the behavior of the interpolant at the endpoints of the data points. In our case, we used the natural boundary condition, where the second derivative at the boundary points is set to zero. This condition ensures a smooth and continuous curve throughout the interpolation range. Smoothness constraints impose constraints on the first derivatives of the interpolant at the internal points. These constraints guarantee a smooth transition between adjacent quadratic polynomials and prevent any sudden changes or discontinuities. The quadratic spline interpolation method enforces these constraints, resulting in a physically sound representation of the water level variation along the river's surface. To compute the quadratic spline interpolation, we utilized Python's Scipy library [41]. The library provides a convenient function that automatically determines the parameters for smoothness based on the data distribution. By using these parameters, the spline interpolation adapts to the characteristics of the in-situ measurements, ensuring an optimal balance between smoothness and fidelity to the observed data. The extensive amount of interpolant functions, $I(x)$, results in a considerable number of parameters (a_i , b_i , and c_i) as interpolant functions are computed piece-wise at each 15-minute timestep throughout the 1.5-month period of in-situ measurements (not shown).

To assess the accuracy of the spline interpolation, we employ a framework encompassing three steps: firstly, we evaluate the RMSE and R^2 between the measured and spline time-series, then we compute and compare different tidal metrics, also called datums, that are important for understanding the tidal behavior at each gauge location and its evolution as the tidal wave progresses upstream [42]. Finally, we use wave celerity as a reliable proxy for validation. In a tidal river such as the Saigon River, the tidal wave propagates upstream and is captured by all sensors along the river. The wave celerity is independent of a vertical reference for water level measurements and can serve as a reliable validation parameter for the spline interpolation results. The process of calculating wave celerity involves identifying points where the first derivative of water level measurements is zero at each sensor location. These points, which correspond to the maxima and minima of water levels, are tracked from the downstream to the

upstream sensors to determine travel times. Subsequently, wave celerity in the Saigon river is derived by computing the velocity of these maxima and minima, a procedure that can also be applied to the spline interpolation using the corresponding water level data at sensor locations. A close agreement between the measured and interpolated wave celerities provides confidence in the accuracy of the spline interpolation method to capture the tidal propagation dynamics that govern the water level surface. To contextualize the wave celerity results, we considered several river geomorphological metrics for each river section. Along-river length (L_a), straight-line length (L_s), and sinuosity were quantified to characterize the shape and meandering nature of each river section. Sinuosity is calculated as the ratio of L_a to L_s :

$$\text{Sinuosity} = \frac{L_a}{L_s} \quad (2)$$

This ratio provides a measure of the river's curvature and its deviation from a straight-line course. Rivers can have sinuosity ranging from 1 to 3 (i.e., the river length is three times longer than the valley).

For the period of water level measurements the following metrics were computed according to the general tidal datum computation procedures as described by the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration [43]:

MHHW (Mean Higher-High Water): MHHW is defined as the arithmetic mean of the higher high water heights of the tide observed over a specific period of measurement. Solely, the higher high water of each pair of high waters of a tidal day is included in the mean. It is a reference point for the highest high tides, which occur during spring tides.

MHW (Mean High Water): is defined as the arithmetic mean of all of the high water heights observed over a specific period. It is a reference for the typical height of high tides and is used for navigation, coastal construction, and environmental monitoring.

MRL (Mean River Level): MRL is the average water level over a time period.

MLW (Mean Low Water): is defined as the arithmetic mean of all of the low water heights observed over a specified period and serves as a reference for the typical height of low tides. It is used for navigation, especially in shallow waters.

MLLW (Mean Lower-Low Water): MLLW is defined as the arithmetic mean of the lower low water heights of the tide observed over a specific period. Only the lower low water of each pair of low waters of a tidal day is included in the mean. It serves as a reference point for extremely low tides and is used for coastal planning and environmental monitoring.

Gt (Great Diurnal Range): Gt represents the difference between the mean higher high water (MHHW) and the mean lower low water (MLLW). A larger GT implies a greater difference between high and low tides.

Mn (Mean Range of Tide): Mn is the difference between MHW and MLW. It provides a general measure of the typical tidal variation in a given location.

DHQ (Mean Diurnal High Water Inequality): DHQ is the difference in elevation between MHHW and MHW. It helps assess variations in daily high tide levels.

DLQ (Mean Diurnal Low Water Inequality): DLQ is the difference in elevation between MLLW and MLW. Similar to DHQ, it assesses variations in daily low tide levels.

2.5. Simulation of SWOT satellite products: Water level and slope

In order to conduct an extensive study of error analysis on water level and slope and their impact on discharge estimation using SWOT satellite data we need to simulate these variables. This section outlines the methodology we employed to simulate SWOT water level and slope products.

2.5.1. “True” water level and slope. From the previous section’s spline spatial interpolation, we consider the water level obtained as the “true” water level of the river. For the purpose of this study, we focus on the river section around our two sites where ADCP campaigns were done, specifically location H1 and H3 (yellow triangles in Fig 1). However, we will only provide the results for section H1 due to its lower hydraulic complexity compared to location H3, which is located downstream in the center of Ho Chi Minh City. At this location the Saigon river is connected to a complex canal network making the estimation of discharge more challenging. A recent 1D numerical modelling effort has showed that canals influence the dynamics of the river Saigon locally but have negligible influence on the river as a whole [44]. Additionally, at H1 we conducted two ADCP campaigns during both symmetric and asymmetric tidal regimes, allowing us to calibrate our model (to be explained in the next section) based on different tidal types whereas at H3 we only conducted one ADCP campaign.

At the exact location of the ADCP campaign (H1), we consider the spline water level as the true water level, z_{true} . To compute the slope, we select two water level nodes, n_0 and n_N , around H1 with a distance of 1 km between them, as illustrated in green in Fig 2. The true slope, S_{true} , is then calculated using the following equation:

$$S_{true} = \frac{n_N - n_0}{x} \tag{3}$$

with x the along-river distance between the two nodes. This approach allows us to determine the true slope value for our discharge estimation.

To simulate SWOT water level and slope products, we employ two different approaches. Firstly, we aim to obtain the SWOT variables as they are expected to be outputted by the satellite’s measurements. Secondly, we propose a new methodology to compute water levels and slope from the SWOT water level products at 200 m resolution.

2.5.2. Approach 1: Expected SWOT products. In this approach, we compute the average water level from the 200 m nodes for the 10 km reach between nodes n_i and n_N as illustrated in red in Fig 2, where N is the total number of water level nodes in the reach and n_i the i th water

Fig 2. Flowchart of methodology. Flowchart of data used for estimating discharge based on the spline water level (green) to obtain the “True” discharge; based on water level as expected to be provided directly by SWOT (red) to obtain the “SWOT-like” discharge; and based on water level using improved reach selection methodology (blue) to obtain an improved SWOT-like discharge. Discharge is obtained from a modified Manning-Strickler law referred to as the “MODEL” in this flowchart.

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level node. The SWOT-like water level, z_{swot} is thus given by:

$$z_{swot} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N n_i \quad (4)$$

The obtained value for z_{swot} mimics the water level product as directly provided by SWOT at the reach scale. We then add the expected noise of 10 cm [12, 45–47] directly to this value. To study the variability of the error, we employ a Monte Carlo white noise approach with standard deviation equal to the expected error and mean equal to zero as has been done in previous studies [22, 36]. For the computation of SWOT-like slope, we follow the methodology proposed by the SWOT team [48] at reach level where the first, n_0 , and last node, n_N , of a given reach are used to compute the slope as follows:

$$S_{swot} = \frac{n_N - n_0}{x} \quad (5)$$

where x is the distance spanned by the reach. Similar to the SWOT-like water level, \bar{z}_{swot} , we directly add the expected SWOT error of 1.7 cm/km [12, 45–47] to the computed slope using a Monte Carlo white noise approach. Using this methodology we obtain 1000 samples of SWOT-like water level and slope with associated errors that correspond to the 10 km reach products that will be provided by the SWOT mission.

2.5.3. Approach 2: Improved methodology for water level and slope estimation from SWOT observations. The order of magnitude of the Saigon river's slope (cm/km) is the same as the expected SWOT error's magnitude. Thus, we anticipate that SWOT slope products may introduce significant errors in discharge estimation when used as is. To mitigate this, we propose a new methodology to compute water levels and slope from the SWOT water level product at 200 m resolution, which are expected to have an error of 35 cm [12, 45]. To incorporate this error, we add it to the 200 m nodes of the spline using the Monte Carlo white noise approach as previously described. The water level, z_2 , is taken as the average water level between points n_0 and n_N (Fig 2, blue illustration):

$$z_2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N n_i \quad (6)$$

For the slope computation we take a reach length of x km and compute two supplemental water levels: the first, P_1 , is the average of the nodes in the section between point n_0 and the ADCP point (yellow triangle in illustration, Fig 2) with a length of $x/2$ km, and the second is the average of the nodes in the section between the ADCP location and n_N , also with a length of $x/2$ (point P_2). The slope is then computed as follows:

$$S_2 = \frac{P_1 - P_2}{x} \quad (7)$$

We conduct experiments for reach lengths equal to 10, 15, 20 and 25 km. These lengths translate to using 50, 75, 100 and 125 nodes for the water level and slope computations, respectively. By utilizing more information from the SWOT measurements and increasing the number of river nodes used to compute the hydraulic variables we expect a reduction in the error associated with discharge estimation.

The simulated water levels and slopes, obtained through the aforementioned approaches, are utilized to estimate the discharge. The details of the discharge estimation process are explained in the subsequent section.

2.6. River discharge estimation

The instantaneous river discharge was estimated by applying a stage-fall-discharge (SFD) rating curve adapted from the general Manning-Strickler law (Eq 8), previously tested and validated by [49] and used to predict the total discharge of the Saigon river in [20, 30]. The discharge is estimated as follows:

$$Q(t) = \text{sign}(S) \cdot K \cdot A_w(z(t)) \cdot R_h(z(t))^{2/3} \cdot \sqrt{|S(t + \Delta t)|} \tag{8}$$

with Q the water discharge [$m^3 s^{-1}$], K the Manning-Strickler coefficient [$m^{1/3} s^{-1}$], $R_h = A_w/P_w$ the hydraulic radius [m], A_w the wet section [m^2], P_w the wet perimeter [m]. Note that A_w and P_w are both a function of the water level and thus, of time. Furthermore, in Eq 8 above $z(t) = z_{true}(t)$ for computing the ‘‘True’’ discharge, $z(t) = z_{swot}(t)$ for approach 1 and $z(t) = z_2(t)$ for approach 2. The term $\text{sign}(S)$ is equal to the sign of the slope, S , taking the values of +1 or -1. The energy slope, S [-], is assumed equal to the water slope and is computed as in sub-sections 2.5.2 and 2.5.3 for approaches 1 and 2, respectively. Since there is no fixed datum between river gauges, we normalize all signals by mean removal, as previously mentioned. This makes the tidal harmonics oscillate about zero for all gauge locations thus, making them comparable. However, datum errors still persist and a vertical adjustment is required for discharge computation. This adjustment is done via an additional term, dz , which serves as an extra tuning parameter of our model and allows it to better capture the surface slope dynamics of the Saigon river. This parameter is introduced in the slope computation as follows:

$$S(t) = s + \frac{dz}{x} \tag{9}$$

where $s = S_{true}$ for computing the ‘‘True’’ discharge, $s = S_{swot}$ for approach 1 and $s = S_2$ for approach 2. In addition, a time lag, Δt , is required to account for the propagation of the tidal wave between the two points used to compute the slope. This method allows the computation of three time-series of discharge namely: the ‘‘True’’ discharge which is used as the benchmark for the discharge computed using approach 1, the SWOT-like discharge, and using approach 2, the improved SWOT-like discharge.

2.7. Performance evaluation indices

The evaluation of the applied approaches was carried out using two statistical indicators: root mean square error (RMSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The RMSE has been evaluated both in terms of absolute (m^3/s) and relative (rRMSE expressed as a percentage) values. These indicators have been widely used in literature for this purpose [36]. Those performance indices have been evaluated referring to the discharge time-series obtained via the Monte Carlo approach for each of the methods described in section 2.6. The equation, range, and optimal value of each index are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Equations and optimal values of statistical indices. Q^i and Q_{true}^i denote the predicted discharge from SWOT-like variables and ‘‘True’’ discharge from spline variables, respectively, at time i .

Indices	Equation	Range	Optimal values
Root Mean Square Error	$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (Q^i - Q_{true}^i)^2}$	0 to ∞	0
Coefficient of determination	$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (Q_{true}^i - Q^i)^2}{\sum_i (Q_{true}^i - Q_{true}^i)^2}$	0 to 1	1

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3. Results

3.1. Validation of the spline spatial interpolation

In Fig 3, the time-series from the in-situ water level gauges are shown in the top panel. Six curves are shown for each river gauge from the most downstream (bottom, darker green) to the most upstream (lighter green, top) locations DN2 and CC, respectively. As can be seen, tidal fluctuations govern the water level dynamics at all locations. In fact, the Saigon river's levels are influenced by tides up until the Dau Tieng reservoir (Fig 1) [20]. The panels 0 to 3 illustrate the spatial spline interpolation (black points) and in-situ measurements (triangles) for the four SWOT passes that would occur during the time period of in-situ measurements. For simplicity, we assume that the first pass over the Saigon river (Orbit 1, Day 4, Pass 90) happens on the first day of in-situ measurements. Additionally, the SWOT spatial coverage of the river is indicated in red (pass 90) and blue (pass 271).

Fig 3. Illustration of spline interpolation and SWOT satellite passes. Time-series from in-situ water level gauges at all locations (top panel). Water levels have been displaced by 3 meters for easier reading. Measurements are shown in increasingly darker shades of green from closest to source to further away from source namely, CC, H1, H2, H3, LG and DN2. Additionally, 4 time stamps corresponding to what would be the SWOT satellite temporal resolution during the period of in-situ measurements are indicated by black, vertical lines. Panels 0 to 3 correspond to the timestamps in the top panel. The results of the spatial interpolation using a second degree spline are illustrated for the SWOT passes over the region namely, pass 90 and 271. Additionally, the SWOT spatial coverage of the river is shown in red (pass 90) and in blue (pass 271). Triangles in panels 0 to 3 indicate in-situ measurements whereas the black dots are the interpolated spline values at the SWOT nodes location.

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Table 2. Water level Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination R^2 at each measurement location. Comparison between the spline fit and in-situ data.

River Location	CC	H1	H2	H3	LG	DN2
RMSE [m]	0.02	0.09	0.10	-0.08	-0.05	0.04
R^2	0.99	0.98	0.96	0.99	0.99	0.99

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At the DN2 gauge different tidal regimes can be seen propagating upstream. At the beginning of the time-series, a symmetric regime can be seen where different cycles of high and low tide present similar amplitude (Fig 3, from timestamps 0 until November 8th, 2022 in top panel). Then, the tide fluctuations transition to an increasingly asymmetric semi-diurnal regime (timestamp 1) that passes through a diurnal phase (around November 17th, 2022) before cycling back towards a symmetric regime.

From panels 0 to 3 in Fig 3, it can be seen that the quadratic spline fits well to the measured values. From the depicted examples the H3 location seems to be consistently below the spline curve whereas H2 is consistently above. In Table 2, the RMSE and R^2 values for all locations are presented. The results reveal that river measurements at the H2 and H3 locations differ the most from the spline values with, respectively, RMSE of 10 cm and -8 cm. At the other locations RMSE values are below ± 10 cm agreeing to the measured values. Additionally, the R^2 values at all locations are above 0.96 which indicates that the spline replicates well the tidal fluctuations along the river.

The tidal metrics are reference water levels describing the characteristic periodic variations in sea surface elevation relative to a vertical datum at a particular location. Table 3 presents tidal metrics for the six gauge locations in meters. For each location, two values are provided in the format “measured, spline.” The first value represents the metric computed from measurements (in-situ data), while the second value represents the metric computed from the spline interpolation. The results show consistency in the measured MHHW and MHW values across all locations with values ranging from 0.56 to 1.14 meters and 0.50 to 1.03 meters, respectively. Note that both metrics increase from upstream to downstream within the Saigon river (from CC to LG) and then decrease between the Saigon river (LG) and the Dongnai river (DN2). The spline-based estimates closely align with the measured values, demonstrating the reliability of this method for capturing the tidal dynamics. However, the aforementioned behaviour between the Saigon and Dongnai rivers is not captured by the spline-derived metrics as they monotonically increase from upstream to downstream.

Table 3. Tidal metrics for each gauge location in meters. Two values are shown in the form “measured, spline”: the first is the value computed from measurements and the second is the value computed from the spline.

	CC	H1	H2	H3	LG	DN2
MHHW	0.56, 0.56	0.78, 0.79	0.84, 0.88	0.89, 0.85	1.14, 0.98	1.07, 1.06
MHW	0.50, 0.51	0.72, 0.72	0.77, 0.81	0.81, 0.76	1.03, 0.88	0.95, 0.95
MRL	-0.11, -0.11	0.00, 0.02	0.00, 0.05	0.00, -0.04	0.15, 0.00	0.00, 0.00
MLLW	-1.28, -1.28	-1.26, -1.25	-1.37, -1.32	-1.46, -1.49	-1.49, -1.65	-1.80, -1.81
MLW	-0.81, -0.81	-0.79, -0.76	-0.84, -0.78	-0.89, -0.91	-0.83, -0.99	-1.04, -1.03
Gt	1.84, 1.84	2.04, 2.04	2.21, 2.20	2.35, 2.35	2.63, 2.63	2.87, 2.87
Mn	1.31, 1.31	1.51, 1.47	1.61, 1.59	1.69, 1.67	1.86, 1.87	1.99, 1.98
DHQ	0.06, 0.05	0.06, 0.07	0.07, 0.07	0.09, 0.09	0.10, 0.10	0.12, 0.12
DLQ	-0.47, -0.47	-0.47, -0.49	-0.53, -0.54	-0.57, -0.58	-0.66, -0.66	-0.77, -0.77

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Table 4. Along-river length, L_a , straight-line length, L_s , and sinuosity of each river section between two sensors. Wave celerity is computed for each river section. The “Measured” column refers to the wave celerity computed from measurements and the “Spline” column to wave celerity computed from the spline interpolant. The last row shows the wave celerity for the whole domain.

River section	L_a [km]	L_s [km]	Sinuosity	Measured [m/s]	Spline [m/s]
CC-H1	27.8	16.8	1.65	6.0	5.3
H1-H2	10.5	9.2	1.14	5.6	6.0
H2-H3	8.2	3.8	2.56	6.3	7.3
H3-LG	15.9	5.3	3.00	7.5	6.9
LG-DN2	23.5	13.8	1.70	6.8	6.8
CC-DN2	85.9	48.5	1.77	6.4	6.8

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MRL values exhibited some variability among locations. The expected measured values for this metric should be around zero which is the case for most stations. However, at the CC station MRL is negative (-0.11 m) and at LG it is positive (0.15 m) potentially due to a measurement bias in the sensors. Spline interpolation provided MRL estimates generally close to zero for all locations. It matched the MRL at the CC station but not at the LG station. This could indicate that the spatial interpolation removed the bias from the measured data at LG as it is located between two other measurement points whereas at CC it could not as it was the last point in the studied river reach.

The results show consistency in the measured MLLW and MLW values across all locations with values ranging from -1.28 to -1.8 meters and -0.81 to -1.04 meters, respectively. As for MHHW and MHW, these metrics increase (in modulus) as we travel downstream but do not show the decrease in value from LG to DN2. The spline-based estimates closely follow the measured values, reinforcing the robustness of the interpolation technique. Other metrics such as Gt, Mn, DHQ and DLQ are computed from MHHW, MHW, MLLW and MLW. As expected these derived metrics show similar characteristics as those discussed and a close agreement between the measured and spline-derived values.

In the Saigon river the tidal wave progresses upstream and is detected by all sensors distributed along the river’s course. Wave celerity, a parameter unaffected by the vertical reference of water level measurements, emerges as a dependable means of accessing the capacity of the spline interpolation to propagate the tidal wave. By calculating wave celerity through the use of available in-situ measurements, we can compare it with the wave celerity estimated from the spline-generated water level data. Table 4 presents the wave celerity computed from measured values and from the spline interpolation for river sections between sensor locations.

The results show an average wave celerity along the whole domain of 6.4 m/s based on measured data and 6.8 m/s for the spline interpolation across the domain. Wave celerity values show variability between river sections as these are of different lengths and sinuosity. The most sinuous section is H3-LG with the river being 3 times longer than the straight line course. Overall, the spline is capable of simulating the propagation speed of the tidal wave over the whole domain. However, it seems to have problems in the parts of the river that are most sinuous namely, H2-H3 and H3-LG. This proxy highlights that variations in wave propagation are influenced by the interpolation method and its capacity to capture the timing of high and low waters.

3.2. Calibration of the discharge model using ADCP measurements

Two ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) campaigns were conducted in November 2022 and December 2022, with the utilization of a Rio Grande 600 kHz instrument [50]. Over

a 24-hour period, hourly gauging activities were carried out, encompassing two transects, at locations H1 and H3 (indicated by yellow triangles in Fig 1) using a boat equipped with a georeferenced ADCP device. Nevertheless, the subsequent discussion will focus solely on the H1 location and results for the H3 location can be found in the Figs A-D in S1 Appendix. These ADCP campaigns aimed to calibrate the estimation of water discharge, calculated according to Eq 8 [49]. The methodology followed for calibration was a one-at-a-time procedure that minimizes the RMSE between predicted and observed values. The parameters K , Δt , and dz were adjusted to ensure that the model-derived discharge matched the observed data. Calibration was performed under both symmetric (November 2022) and asymmetric (December 2022) tidal conditions to ensure the robustness of the discharge estimation law. Once calibrated, the parameters are kept constant. In addition, these ADCP campaigns were employed to determine the river's cross-section characteristics and compute A_w and R_h as functions of water level. Considering adverse conditions, ADCP measurement errors were assessed at 10%, with a minimum error threshold set at $100 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ [51]. The optimal results were obtained with a Manning-Strickler coefficient of $K = 25 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$, a time step of $\Delta t = -75$ minutes, and a vertical resolution of $dz = 0.05$ meters. Results are depicted in Fig 4. The November 2022 campaign exhibited notably accurate outcomes. In contrast, the December 2022 campaign yielded slightly less precise results but remained in good agreement with the data. The discernible influence of the asymmetric semi-diurnal tidal signal accounted for some of the discrepancies [30]. The discharge time-series for the full period under scope is presented in S1 Fig. The combined RMSE for both campaigns was $450 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, equivalent to approximately 22% of the maximum observed discharge. Error sensitivity to the calibration parameters was performed and is presented in S2 Fig.

Fig 4. Comparison of river water discharge. Water discharge Q comparison between model results (dashed, green), ADCP measurements (black points), SWOT-like discharge (red) and improved SWOT-like discharge (shades of blue) at the H1 location: (A) symmetric tide during campaigns of November 2022 and (B) asymmetric tide during campaign of December 2022. The curves for SWOT-like discharge and improved SWOT-like discharge are the average of the 1000 Monte Carlo simulations of discharge. All curves were obtained using the optimal parameters namely, $K = 25 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$, $dz = 0.05$ meters and $dt = -75$ minutes.

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3.3. Discharge estimation using SWOT-like measurements

Fig 5 provides a comprehensive view of the performance and accuracy of SWOT-like discharge estimation techniques based on satellite-derived measurements. In Fig 5A SWOT-like discharge is plotted against the “True” discharge. SWOT-like discharge (red in the figure) is obtained from measurements of water level and slope as SWOT would directly provide and including its expected errors. This estimation of discharge has an R^2 value of 0.31. This signifies a weak correlation between the estimated and “true” discharge values. This discrepancy is particularly noticeable as SWOT-like discharge consistently underestimates true discharge, primarily for higher discharge values (in modulus). Notably, this underestimation is most apparent within the range of positive discharge values spanning from 0 to 1000 m^3/s .

A notable improvement in discharge estimation is introduced through the enhanced SWOT-like discharge estimation methodology, applied to a 10 km reach size (lightest blue in Fig 5A). The resulting R^2 value rises to 0.72, signifying a more robust correlation with true discharge values in comparison to the prior SWOT-like approach. The enhancement is especially evident in cases of negative discharges and positive values exceeding 1000 m^3/s . Nevertheless, we note a persisting underestimation of discharge within the range of 0 to 1000 m^3/s , highlighting ongoing challenges in accurately assessing moderate positive discharge values.

In Fig 5A the effect of varying reach sizes on SWOT-like discharge estimation can be seen with reaches ranging from 15 km to 30 km (increasing shade of blue in figure). As reach size increases, the R^2 value progressively improves, with an improvement from an R^2 of 0.88 at 15 km to 0.94 at 30 km. However, it is essential to acknowledge that this increase in reach size introduces error, leading to a deterioration in discharge estimation accuracy for values between 0 m^3/s and 1000 m^3/s , often yielding negative discharge estimates within this range. Furthermore, the figure shows that beyond a 20 km reach size the improvement in the R^2

Fig 5. R^2 and RMSE. A) comparison between model discharge taken as “True” discharge, SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes. Each particle corresponds to the one timestamp in the discharge time-series from each Monte Carlo run. B) RMSE boxplots from Monte Carlo runs between model discharge take as “True” discharge, and SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes.

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value becomes less significant. This suggests a diminishing return in accuracy associated with larger reach sizes.

Fig 5B provides a visual representation of the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values between the “True” discharge and SWOT-like discharge estimates for a range of Monte Carlo runs. The x-axis comprises six entries, denoting the different methods: SWOT-like (red), 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reaches (shown as increasingly darker shades of blue). Each entry corresponds to a boxplot in the figure, derived from the analysis of time-series from 1000 Monte Carlo runs.

The first box corresponding to SWOT-like discharge estimation exhibits substantial errors across all Monte Carlo runs. The median RMSE for SWOT-like discharge is around $1500 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (red box in Fig 5B), indicative of a significant discrepancy between the estimated values and the “True” discharge. Moreover, the presence of relatively high outlier RMSEs, reaching values around $800 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, underscores the variability and extent of errors associated with discharge estimated directly from SWOT measurements in this region. These findings emphasize the limitations of the SWOT satellite and the challenges it presents in accurately approximating “True” discharge values. Conversely, the introduction of the improved SWOT-like methodology with a 10 km reach size results in an enhancement in discharge estimation accuracy. The median RMSE decreases to approximately $700 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, signifying a considerable improvement in accuracy compared to the SWOT-like approach. Furthermore, the maximum RMSE values remain below $1200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, demonstrating a reduced spread in error magnitudes. This marked improvement suggests that the presented methodology for a 10 km reach size is critical in enhancing the precision of discharge estimation from SWOT measurements.

As the reach size increases beyond 10 km, the boxplots in Fig 5B illustrate a trend of diminishing RMSE values. The median RMSE values progressively decrease with larger reach sizes, seemingly reaching a plateau at approximately $180 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. This plateau suggests that further increases in reach size do not significantly improve the accuracy of discharge estimation, and the methodology approaches a stable level of error. However, it is noteworthy that even at reach sizes between 20 km and 30 km, certain outlier maximum RMSE values remain high at around $800 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, indicating that challenges persist in accurately estimating discharge for specific Monte Carlo runs. Consequently, a 20 km reach size appears to be an optimal choice for discharge estimation from SWOT measurements, as improvements in median RMSE are not significant with increasing reach size.

Fig 6A presents the relative Root Mean Square Error (rRMSE) values expressed as a percentage (%) between “True” discharge and SWOT-like discharge estimates. These values are shown across the different reach sizes under scope (10 km, 15 km, 20 km, 25 km, and 30 km). Each data point in the figure corresponds to the rRMSE value for a timestamp in the 1000 time-series obtained from the Monte Carlo method, capturing the variability of discharge estimation under different conditions. As can be seen for all estimation methodologies under investigation, the rRMSE values exhibit a trend of increasing error as discharge approaches zero. This trend implies that discharge estimation accuracy diminishes as discharge values approach the lower end of the spectrum.

SWOT-like discharge estimation emerges as the least accurate method, with the highest rRMSE values (red, Fig 6A). The minimum error in discharge is of 50% rRMSE observed at the highest discharge values. This suggests that the SWOT-like methodology struggles to accurately estimate discharge along the full spectrum of discharge values of the Saigon river. Even at the highest discharge values, the rRMSE remains relatively high. Conversely, when implementing the improved SWOT-like methodology with a 10 km reach size (lighter blue particles in Fig 6A), a substantial reduction in rRMSE values is observed. The minimum rRMSE drops to approximately 20% for the largest discharge values, reflecting a considerable enhancement

Fig 6. rRMSE. A) rRMSE between model discharge take as “True” discharge, and SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes. Each particle corresponds to the rRMSE value for a given timestamp in a given Monte Carlo run. The horizontal dashed line represents the 30% rRMSE threshold. B) Bar plot of percentage of Monte Carlo particles below or equal to 30% rRMSE.

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in accuracy compared to the SWOT-like approach. However, rRMSE values greater than 30% persist for discharge values ranging from $-1500 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $+1500 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, indicating that challenges in accurate estimation remain within this range.

As in previously seen, the figure demonstrates that increasing the reach size leads to a decrease in rRMSE values. For instance, at a 20 km reach size (indicated by the intermediate blue data points), the minimum rRMSE approaches 10% for the largest discharge values, representing a substantial improvement. Nevertheless, for discharge values between $-800 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $+1200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, rRMSE values exceeding 30% are still observed, highlighting the persistence of estimation challenges. Additionally, beyond the 20 km reach size, further increases in reach size do not substantially improve the minimum rRMSE at the largest discharge values. However, these larger reach sizes do result in an increase in the quantity of particles falling below the 30% error threshold. For instance, at a 30 km reach size, discharge values between $-600 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $1000 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ are still above this threshold. This suggests that while the reach size increase may not substantially enhance accuracy at the highest discharge values, it does contribute to reducing the number of instances where the error exceeds 30% rRMSE.

In Fig 6B the bar plot of the percentage of Monte Carlo particles that are below 30% is shown. As can be seen, we increase the number of particles below this threshold from 0% to 25.6% when applying the improved discharge estimation method for the same reach size. Furthermore, as reach size increases so does the number of particles below the threshold. Increasing reach size from 20 to 30 km increases the number of particles below the 30% rRMSE threshold by 9.3%. Consequently, selecting an appropriate reach size is a crucial consideration for achieving a balance between minimizing error and effectively capturing discharge variability.

In order to study the influence of lower SWOT measurement errors on our discharge estimation methodology, we conducted a sensitivity analysis. The first, publicly available observations of SWOT were remarkably promising, surpassing the SWOT mission team's expectations, and revealing the satellite's impressive ability to discern water nodes in river systems and bodies of water with widths less than 100 meters [13]. Hence, we proceeded to explore the ramifications of reduced SWOT measurement errors. Specifically, we assessed the implications of reducing errors to 30 cm (a 5 cm reduction from the original error) and 25 cm (a 10 cm reduction from the original error) at 200-meter nodes, followed by the application of our methodology under these revised error scenarios. The outcomes of this sensitivity analysis are presented in [S3 Fig](#). We provide comprehensive insights into the rRMSE and the proportion of Monte Carlo particles that fall below the critical 30% rRMSE threshold. Notably, the reduction of SWOT measurement errors to 30 cm yielded a subtle improvement. These improvements were reflected in the percentages of Monte Carlo particles associated with improved SWOT discharge estimates, which ranged from 29.4% to 82% for reaches of 10 to 30 km in length. Similarly, the further reduction to 25 cm in measurement error yielded improved results, demonstrating percentages between 33% and 83.6% of Monte Carlo particles below the 30% rRMSE threshold for various reach sizes spanning from 10 to 30 km. It is important to note that, despite the favorable outcomes observed with the reduced SWOT error scenarios, SWOT-like discharge Monte Carlo particles consistently remained above the specified threshold. However, the overall improvements, albeit notable, remained somewhat limited in magnitude. This restricted enhancement can be attributed to the inherent sensitivity of our simplified discharge estimation model, particularly concerning flow transitions during the shift from positive to negative flow regimes. Consequently, the marginal increment in the number of particles falling below the 30% rRMSE threshold underscores the inherent constraints of our methodology in capturing the intricate dynamics governing tidal flows.

4. Discussion

4.1. Validation of the spline spatial interpolation

It was found that spline interpolation generally fits well with the measured values however, it is noteworthy that the H3 gauge measurements consistently fall below the spline, while H2 gauge values consistently exceed it. This pattern is also reflected in the root mean square error (RMSE) values, which are notably higher at these two locations compared to other gauge locations. This divergence can be attributed to the fact that H3 and H2 stations are situated in an area characterized by high sinuosity (as indicated in [Table 4](#)) and an intricate artificial canal network. These two factors exert a significant influence on the propagation of the tidal wave and the hydraulic behavior of the river. Consequently, the spline interpolation encounters challenges in accurately fitting the measurement values at these locations. We also found that the behaviour between the Saigon and Dongnai rivers is not captured by the spline. The spline method is not adapted for simulating adequately discontinuities, such as the confluence between the two rivers.

In contrast, we observed that the spline interpolation aligns well with measurements when considering metrics such as Mean Higher High Water (MHHW), Mean High Water (MHW), Mean Lower Low Water (MLLW), and Mean Low Water (MLW). This consistency suggests that the spatial interpolation method simulates average high and low tides in a coherently over the studied time frame. As anticipated, these metrics, as derived from measurements, exhibit a decline as one moves upstream along the Saigon River, progressing from LG to CC. However, it's worth noting an exception with the DN2 gauge, which shows a decrease in these metrics compared to the LG gauge, even though DN2 is the most downstream measurement location.

This discrepancy arises because DN2 is situated in the Dongnai River, which is considerably wider (by a factor of 3, sometimes more in some regions) and shallower (also by a factor of two) compared to the Saigon River. The spatial interpolation method does not capture this behavior, as it is primarily a mathematical construct.

The use of wave celerity as a proxy to evaluate the spline's ability to propagate the tidal wave yielded promising results across the entire domain. This methodology proved effective in simulating wave celerity. A crucial aspect for discussion pertains to the spatial variability of wave celerity. The spline interpolation performs well in river sections characterized by lower sinuosity (below a value of 2). However, it is evident that the spline-derived wave celerity diverges from measurements within the city center area, where the river exhibits the highest sinuosity, notably between H2 and LG. In the lower reaches of tidal rivers, wave celerity is primarily influenced by friction [1]. Since the spline method represents a mathematical interpolation rather than the physical properties of the water surface, it encounters difficulties in accurately representing wave celerity in highly sinuous sections of the river, leading to either overestimation or underestimation. Moreover, these sinuous areas are often characterized by hydraulic infrastructure and frequent dredging activities, which further contribute to the discrepancies between spline-derived and measured wave celerity values. Dredging, in particular, has a significant impact on this parameter [52].

4.2. Discharge estimation using SWOT-like measurements

SWOT-like discharge obtained from measurements of water level and slope, mirroring the data SWOT satellite would directly provide, demonstrates a relatively weak correlation with "True" values. This observation holds true for both negative and positive discharge values. Notably, an immediate improvement in correlation becomes evident when we implement our new methodology to compute these variables at the same reach size. In fact, the correlation coefficient (R^2) rises to 0.95 for a reach size of 30 km. However, it is noteworthy that as the reach size is increased, the estimation of discharge values within the 0 to 1000 m^3/s range tends to be underestimated compared to SWOT-like discharge (as shown in Fig 5A). This behavior is indicative of the limitations inherent in our discharge estimation method, which relies on the Manning-Strickler law and assumes uniform flow conditions. In situations where the discharge is about to transition from positive to negative or vice versa, uniform flow conditions do not apply, leading to discrepancies. This also elucidates why larger positive and negative values of discharge exhibit a better correlation with "True" values, as flow conditions tend to be closer to uniform when the discharge sign remains constant. Furthermore, as depicted in Fig 4, the mean Monte Carlo profiles for SWOT-like and improved SWOT-like discharge exhibit no temporal discrepancy or time shift. This observation reinforces the notion that the consistent errors mentioned earlier are primarily attributed to the limitations of our discharge estimation model.

Our analysis also revealed that increasing the reach size results in a decrease in discharge RMSE values, eventually reaching as low as 180 m^3/s (as demonstrated in Fig 5B). Nevertheless, it's worth noting that even for larger reach sizes, several outliers persist, with RMSE values reaching up to 800 m^3/s . The presence of these outliers can be attributed to the challenges associated with accurately estimating discharge around zero values, as discussed previously.

Furthermore, our examination revealed that within the range of -500 to +500 m^3/s , the relative RMSE (rRMSE) values surge to more than 200 percent. This phenomenon can be attributed to the same factors discussed earlier. However, it is encouraging to note that our method substantially improves the proportion of Monte Carlo particles that fall below the 30 percent rRMSE threshold, widely considered as satisfactory [9, 53, 54]. The reduction in rRMSE values

can be achieved for discharge values outside the aforementioned range, primarily because we leverage a greater number of SWOT data points for water level. Despite their larger associated errors, the abundance of data points provides more information, which, when averaged, effectively enhances discharge estimation. This aspect is particularly relevant in the context of the Saigon River, given its tidal nature where slope values are of the same order of magnitude as the slope measurement errors provided by SWOT [26].

5. Conclusion

SWOT satellite-based river discharge estimates are poised to offer global discharge information for rivers with widths exceeding 100 meters, encompassing some of the world's largest unmonitored basins. These discharge datasets hold the promise of catalyzing a transformative shift in global hydrological research, contingent on the acceptance of their space-time sampling and associated uncertainties by the global scientific community. The computation of SWOT discharge estimates will rely on relatively straightforward flow laws, which involve the amalgamation of SWOT measurements encompassing water surface elevation (WSE), river width, slope, and parameter estimates related to flow laws.

This study aimed to explore the potential role of the upcoming SWOT satellite data in estimating discharge, a vital variable in various hydraulic and hydrology-related applications. In particular, tidal rivers and their associated floodplains represent critical yet understudied environments that serve as focal points for various human activities and provide habitats for diverse ecosystems. Managing flood risk in these areas is of paramount importance, necessitating comprehensive monitoring and a profound understanding of their hydrological dynamics. In this context, we employed a stage-fall-discharge rating curve derived from the widely recognized Manning-Strickler law [49] to evaluate the potential of SWOT satellite measurements to estimate in real-time water discharge levels in the Saigon-Dongnai River system.

Our analysis focused on a 86-kilometer segment of the Saigon-Dongnai River system in Southern Vietnam, leveraging in-situ water level measurements to obtain a second-degree spline spatial interpolation of the river mimicking that of SWOT (every 200 meters). As the main purpose of this study was to evaluate SWOT-error propagation to discharge estimations as a function of reach size we did not consider the temporal resolution of SWOT data. Furthermore, for low latitude regions the greatest advantage of SWOT is its spatial resolution (river variables at the scale of 10-km reaches or 200-m nodes) rather than its temporal resolution (2 to 3 measurements per month). These simulated measurements were intentionally corrupted with random errors adhering to mission requirements [25]. Especially interesting are the effect of SWOT-derived slope errors on discharge estimates as these are within the same order of magnitude as the Saigon river's slope variations. Subsequently, we estimated discharge values by employing five different river stretch resolutions (equal to 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km), following the methodology of [35, 36].

The comparison between synthetic true and SWOT-based discharge at the gauging stations underscores the satellite's potential. The discharge records anticipated from the satellite mission appear capable of providing reliable assessments of the flow regime at various locations. Among the tested discretizations, 20 km stretches exhibited the best performance to computation time ratio, with mean root mean square error (RMSE) values lower than $200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and 70.6% of Monte Carlo particles below 30% relative Root Mean Square Error (rRMSE). However, it's imperative to acknowledge that the proposed methodology encounters challenges when estimating discharge values during the transitions between high and low tides, given the non-uniform flow conditions in these situations. Consequently, the estimates are most reliable for high, consistently uniform discharges, whether positive or negative.

Future applications of this research will delve into the potential of spatio-temporal interpolation criteria, such as data assimilation or statistical approaches, which are expected to enhance spatial and temporal coverage of the river network within the mission's constraints (i.e., low revisit time). It's crucial to note that the reliability and completeness of the acquired hydrological information will also hinge on the specific characteristics of the rivers, including discharge variability, seasonality, and more. Rivers with relatively stable discharge patterns are likely to yield more accurate discharge estimations through satellite monitoring. In contrast, rivers characterized by rapid flood waves and high discharge variability may pose challenges for capturing all hydraulic conditions through satellite observation. Subsequent analyses will further investigate these aspects, emphasizing discharge sensitivity to the satellite overpass period and the significance of the river's hydrologic regime. Additionally, since the proposed methodology is independent of the discharge estimation model it can be applied using any other approach for discharge estimation, such as hydraulic numerical models. An effort towards an accurate modelling of the Saigon-Dongnai system is already under way [44].

In conclusion, the methodology put forth to enhance SWOT output and, consequently, improve discharge estimation can be extended to other regions facing data scarcity, hindering continuous monitoring of hydraulic variables. It is crucial to emphasize that in the case of the suggested discharge estimation law the availability of at least one ADCP campaign at the specific location of interest, and adherence to the assumptions outlined in the proposed model is required.

Supporting information

S1 Appendix. Study at the H3 location.

(PDF)

S1 Fig. Full time-series of discharge at H1 location. Water discharge time-series (green) at the H1 location, residual water discharge time-series obtained from a moving average with a 15 day window size (black) and ADCP campaign (black dots with error bars).

(TIFF)

S2 Fig. Sensitivity analysis of discharge model at the H1 location. Sensitivity analysis of parameters K , dz and dt of the discharge estimation model used in this study at the H1 location.

(TIFF)

S3 Fig. Sensitivity to SWOT error at H1 location. SWOT error of 30 cm (A and B) and 25 cm (C and D) at the 200 meter node level. A) and C): rRMSE between model discharge take as "True" discharge, and SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes. Each particle corresponds to the rRMSE value for a given timestamp in a given Monte Carlo run. The horizontal dashed line represents the 30% rRMSE threshold. B) and D): Bar plot of percentage of Monte Carlo particles below or equal to 30% rRMSE.

(TIFF)

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5.2 S1 Appendix: Figures of study at the H3 location

Fig A in S1 Appendix: Sensitivity analysis of parameters K , dz and dt of the discharge estimation model used in this study at the H3 location.

Fig B in S1 Appendix: Water discharge Q comparison between model results (dashed, green), ADCP measurements (black points), SWOT-like discharge (red) and improved SWOT-like discharge (shades of blue) at the H3 location during the campaign of November/December 2022. The curves for SWOT-like discharge and improved SWOT-like discharge are the average of the 1000 Monte Carlo simulations of discharge.

Fig C in S1 Appendix: Left: comparison between model discharge taken as "True" discharge, SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes. Each particle corresponds to the one timestamp in the discharge timeseries from each Monte Carlo run. Right: RMSE boxplots from Monte Carlo runs between model discharge take as "True" discharge, and SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes. Both plots refer to the H3 location results.

Fig D in S1 Appendix: Left: rRMSE between model discharge take as "True" discharge, and SWOT-like discharge at 10 km reach size and improved SWOT-like discharge at 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 km reach sizes. Each particle corresponds to the rRMSE value for a given timestamp in a given Monte Carlo run. Right: Bar plot of percentage of Monte Carlo particles below or equal to 30% rRMSE. H3 location.

5.3 CONCLUSION

This chapter presents a methodology to improve discharge estimation in tidally-influenced rivers using SWOT data. The results show that this methodology reduces estimation errors but also increases the reliability of discharge measurements in complex hydrodynamic environments. This approach has broad applicability, providing a valuable tool for water resource management, flood control, and environmental conservation in vulnerable low-elevation coastal zones. The findings highlight the transformative potential of the SWOT mission in improving our understanding and monitoring of river discharge on a global scale, particularly in regions that are difficult to monitor using conventional methods.

While this chapter provides valuable statistical insights into the future potential of SWOT data, it does not account for the satellite's temporal resolution. Our primary objective was to assess the impact of SWOT water level and slope errors on discharge estimation, particularly in a scenario where the slope error is comparable to the Saigon River's actual slope. This study is novel within the scientific community as it is the first to simulate SWOT data using a dense array of in-situ measurements in a tidal river environment as previous simulations using pressure sensor arrays have been limited to the ocean.

Chapter 7 presents a first look at real SWOT water level and slope and compares it to in-situ gauges. However, the methodology of this chapter has not been applied as SWOT data over this region was only made available to public at the end of April, 2024 (less than 2 months prior to the writing of this manuscript).

6

Challenging SWOT: early assessment of level 2 high-rate river products in an urbanized, low elevation coastal zone

SUMMARY

This chapter explores real SWOT data for the particularly challenging area under study. This region's flat topography, dense urban development, and tidally influenced river system pose significant obstacles for remote sensing technologies. We focus on validating SWOT Level 2 high-rate river reach products, specifically water surface elevation (WSE, also referred to as water level) and water surface slope (WSS, also referred to as river slope), against in-situ measurements. These in-situ measurements extend the field campaign from Chapter 3 thanks to the continued efforts of Mr. Tin Nguyen Trung from the CARE laboratory. Our primary goal is to assess the accuracy and reliability of real-world SWOT WSE and WSS in such complex conditions.

KEY FINDINGS

- Approximately 50% of SWOT's WSE measurements are deemed valid when compared against in-situ data. Their accuracy is promising despite the challenges posed by the region.
- SWOT's WSS measurements lack accuracy and are unreliable without prior validation against in-situ data. The variability in the tidal influences and the flat topography significantly affect the precision of WSS measurements.
- Despite limitations, SWOT provides high-spatial resolution observations that can offer new insights into dynamic hydrological phenomena.
- The study highlights the difficulties in using radar interferometry in tropical, heavily urbanized areas with smooth water surface slopes.
- There is potential for SWOT data to contribute to a better understanding of the LECZ when used alongside in-situ data, other remote sensing data and models.

Challenging SWOT: early assessment of level 2 high-rate river products in an urbanized, low elevation coastal zone

Francisco Rodrigues do Amaral, Tin Nguyen Trung, Thierry Pellarin, Nicolas Gratiot

Abstract—The Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission offers groundbreaking opportunities to observe fine-scale spatial changes in low elevation coastal zones. This study explores the first SWOT data in one of the mission’s most challenging environments: a data-scarce, tropical region with flat topography, heavy urbanization, and a river with a weak, tidally influenced slope. We focus on SWOT’s water surface elevation (WSE) and water surface slope (WSS) products at the reach level, comparing the measurements to in situ data. Our analysis shows that about half of SWOT’s WSE and WSS measurements fall within the desired error budgets, though WSS lacks linear correlation with in situ data. At this early stage, both SWOT’s WSE and WSS require validation in such complex areas. However, as SWOT’s high-resolution observations improve over time and are integrated with other data, they are expected to provide valuable insights into dynamic river and estuarine processes.

Index Terms—SWOT, tidal river, water surface elevation, water surface slope, estuary, low elevation coastal zone

I. INTRODUCTION

Geophysical processes in low elevation coastal zones (LECZ) are primarily governed by the interaction between river discharge and coastal ocean dynamics [1]. The southern region of Vietnam, particularly Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC), is a densely populated LECZ with up to 30,000 inhabitants per square kilometer in its urban center [2]. HCMC is characterized by its extensive water system, including the tidal Saigon River and around 800 km of canals. With 90% of its urban area impermeable, the city experiences significant hydrological impacts [3], leading to frequent flooding from both river overflow and rainfall runoff [4]. This issue is exacerbated by increasing extreme rainfall events, making HCMC one of the most vulnerable coastal regions globally [5]. Despite these challenges, the Saigon basin remains largely under monitored, hindering effective water resource management and extreme event prevention efforts in HCMC.

Launched in December 2022, the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission aims to transform our understanding of Earth’s surface waters with high-resolution altimetric measurements of rivers, coastal regions, and oceans [6]. We hypothesize that SWOT data could enhance our knowledge of

tidal river-estuary systems. This study explores the application of SWOT data for characterizing the Saigon River, a crucial waterway in HCMC’s urban landscape. Despite its strategic importance, the Saigon River presents significant challenges for in-situ monitoring due to its complex tidal regime and dense urbanization. SWOT data offers a promising approach to overcome these challenges, though radar interferometry faces difficulties due to flat topography, dense urbanization, and a river with a gentle water surface slope influenced by strong coastal tidal forcing.

Here, we present an early assessment of SWOT level 2 high-rate river reach products namely, of water surface elevation (WSE) and water surface slope (WSS), over this region. We examine the accuracy and reliability of WSE and WSS, shedding light on their utility for future hydrological studies. Furthermore, we discuss the implications of our findings for leveraging SWOT data in data-scarce, tropical LECZs and enhancing our understanding of riverine processes in complex environmental settings.

II. DATA AND METHODS

A. In situ measurements

Three measurement locations for water surface elevation (WSE) along the Saigon River are used: Hobo 2 (H2), Hobo 3 (H3), and La Garden (LG) (black crosses in Fig. 1c). The location selection was constrained by on-site factors such as inaccessibility to the riverbank and challenges in sensor installation, with two main criteria: i. comprehensive coverage of key sections of the Saigon River within the center of Ho Chi Minh City, and ii. maintaining a distance of approximately 10 km between sensors to match the spatial resolution of SWOT reach products.

Measurements were obtained using Onset HOBO U20L-01 water level loggers, measuring absolute pressure every 15 minutes. These devices have a typical error of 1 cm, a maximum error of 2 cm, and a resolution of 0.2 cm. To ensure accuracy, measurements were barometrically compensated using air pressure data. Since the vertical reference points of the pressure sensors were different and unknown, all signals were normalized for comparison [7]. Given that tidal fluctuations dominate the WSE signals throughout the river, normalization allowed for direct comparison between sensors by having all signals fluctuate around zero. Additionally, to compare the normalized in situ measurements with SWOT data, the former were adjusted by 1.5 meters to match SWOT’s reference geoid (EGM2008) corrected for tide effects [8].

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Fig. 1. (a) Overview of the region. The green box highlights the study area depicted in (b). (b) Map of the study area. The area within the green box corresponds to the city center area depicted in (c). (c) City center area, displaying water surface elevation gauges used to validate SWOT measurements: Hobo 2 (H2), Hobo 3 (H3), and La Garden (LG) marked as black crosses. The SWOT reaches are illustrated in color, with the center of each reach indicated by a colored dot.

From the WSE measurements the water surface slope (WSS) between two sensors is computed as the difference between two measurement locations divided by the along-river distance between them.

B. Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission and river reach products

SWOT provides observations for 10 km river reaches (see colored Saigon river reaches in Fig. 1c) and nodes spaced about 200 m apart. These measurement locations, predetermined before launch, are cataloged in the SWOT river database (SWORD) [9]. For most rivers, SWOT is expected to achieve a minimum error of 10 cm in WSE and 1.7 cm/km in WSS [10].

The Saigon River is observed by two SWOT orbits: 90 and 271 (Fig. 1a red and blue, respectively), receiving observations on day 4 (orbit 90) and day 10 (orbit 271) within each 21-day cycle. These orbits collectively cover the entire river (Fig. 1b) at least once per cycle. SWOT observations are spatially heterogeneous due to nadir gaps in both orbits. From the upstream Dau Tieng reservoir (Fig. 1b, upper left corner), the first 56 km are observed on day 10 (blue orbit 271 in Fig. 1b); the section from km 56 to 94 is observed on day 4 (red orbit 90 in Fig. 1b); and the remaining section from km 94 to the confluence with the Dongnai River is monitored on both day 4 and day 10. In this study we evaluate three of the SWOT reaches that overlap with our in situ locations (presented in orange, green and aquamarine in Fig. 1c).

Only data from SWOT's cycle 10 onwards is available for analysis as previous cycles did not include measurements over this region. In this letter, we present the SWOT Level 2 River Single-Pass Vector Reach Data Product (Version 2.0). This dataset provides measurements of water surface elevation and slope derived from the high rate data stream from the

KaRIn instrument. The associated uncertainty is automatically computed by the SWOT mission team. SWOT uncertainty estimation is a function of the quality of the measured pixels from the KaRIn instrument. Pixel-cloud information is aggregated into node level data which in turn is averaged over a reach to provide the reach data product [11]. Pixel quality flags are provided by the SWOT team and take the values of good, suspect, degraded or bad. The data is sourced from the Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PODAAC) [12] and is freely accessible to the community.

III. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows water surface elevation (WSE) time-series for three in situ locations across different SWOT cycles. Each plot features SWOT measurements and estimated uncertainty for pass 90 and pass 271, except cycle 15 which only includes pass 271. SWOT measurements are depicted as dots with uncertainty bars: blue for those within the 10 cm error budget [10], and red for those exceeding it. Measurements exceeding the error budget show errors ranging from 0.12 m to 7.99 m, as detailed in Table I.

To investigate the causes of these errors, we analyze the dark water fraction (DWF) and the ratio of valid nodes to total nodes (RVN) within a SWOT reach. Table I presents the absolute error, DWF, and RVN for each cycle-pass pair and location. Of the 33 SWOT measurements, 14 fall within the 10 cm error budget (highlighted in blue). For these measurements, RVN ranges from 66% to 96%. However, even measurements exceeding the error budget can show high RVN values. For example, cycle 12, pass 271 has an error of 37 cm despite an RVN of 100%. This suggests that a high RVN may not always reflect measurement accuracy, as the overall error can still exceed the budget even when all nodes are valid.

Fig. 2. Timeseries of water surface elevation at the 3 in-situ locations H2, H3 and LG. The signals are displaced by 3.5 m. The two SWOT measurements per cycle (pass 90 and pass 271) are presented as dots with uncertainty bar. SWOT measurements within and outside of the error budget of 10 cm are presented in blue and red, respectively. Note that some inaccurate SWOT data fall outside of the area of the plot.

TABLE I

SWOT WATER SURFACE ELEVATION ERROR (IN M, LEFT COLUMN), DARK WATER FRACTION (IN %, MIDDLE COLUMN) AND RATIO OF VALID NODES (IN %, RIGHT COLUMN) FOR EACH IN SITU LOCATION (H2, H3 AND LG IN FIG. 1C). SWOT MEASUREMENTS THAT MEET THE ERROR BUDGET ARE HIGHLIGHTED IN BLUE.

Cycle	Pass	H2			H3			LG		
		Error (m)	Dark Water (%)	Valid Nodes (%)	Error (m)	Dark Water (%)	Valid Nodes (%)	Error (m)	Dark Water (%)	Valid Nodes (%)
10	90	0.01	0	87	0.01	1	79	0.06	3	68
10	271	0.01	0	72	0.08	5	79	0.17	1	87
11	90	0.05	11	96	0.25	18	92	0.21	37	98
11	271	7.95	0	37	0.16	0	79	0.04	1	89
12	90	0.48	63	55	0.08	47	66	0.14	14	91
12	271	7.99	0	38	0.96	0	77	0.37	0	100
13	90	0.06	6	85	0.12	19	62	0.14	12	94
13	271	0.07	0	76	0.01	0	91	0.33	0	87
14	90	0.13	1	69	0.28	4	98	0.05	1	89
14	271	0.49	0	73	0.21	0	79	0.01	4	98
15	271	0.14	4	52	0.13	7	79	0.08	14	92

In Table I, the middle column shows the fraction of dark water pixels within a reach. We find that few SWOT measurements have a high fraction of dark water pixels. The two

Fig. 3. Comparison between in situ and SWOT water surface elevation (WSE).

largest errors (Cycle 11, pass 271, and Cycle 12, pass 271) have no dark water pixels detected by SWOT, indicating that measurement quality is not significantly impacted by dark water-related issues in these cases.

In Figure 3, in situ WSE measurements are plotted against SWOT WSE measurements at 3 locations with a linear regression. Although only 14 out of 33 SWOT measurements fall within the error budget, we see a strong linear correlation between SWOT and in situ WSE, with an R^2 of 0.92 and a near-zero p-value. The RMSE of 0.26 m, though over the budget, is still acceptable, which is promising for the region as SWOT measurements are likely to improve over time.

A similar analysis was done for WSS products (from Bayesian reconstruction algorithm, see supplemental material). Half of the 24 SWOT WSS measurements fall within the error budget, with RVN values ranging from 52% to 98%. For those outside the budget, errors range from 1.97 cm/km to 64 cm/km. There was no linear correlation between SWOT WSS and in situ, with an RMSE of 19.8 cm/km — about an order of magnitude higher than Saigon’s WSS.

In order to explore possible causes of SWOT errors, the raised pixel-cloud quality flags can offer valuable insights. In this study, the most commonly occurring pixel-cloud quality flags [13] are i. Classification suspect flag: Land/water classification information from the pixel-cloud is marked suspicious; ii. Geolocation suspect flag: Pixel-cloud geolocation information is marked suspect; iii. Water fraction suspect flag: Water-fraction information from the pixel-cloud is suspiciously large; iv. Geolocation degraded flag: Pixel-cloud geolocation information is marked degraded. These are discussed in the next section.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this letter, we analyze SWOT Level 2 high-rate river products in a tidal river, focusing on water surface elevation (WSE) and water surface slope (WSS). Our findings indicate that both data require ground truth validation as estimated uncertainties can be misleading (see error bars in Fig. 2). This highlights the critical role of in situ data for effectively using SWOT measurements in challenging environments. We observe that uncertainty bars for pass 271 are often larger

than those for pass 90. These uncertainty estimates depend on various factors, including proximity to the nadir point [14]. Since pass 271 intersects the Saigon River along the nadir track, locations like H2 are closer to the nadir gap than during pass 90 (see blue nadir track in Fig. 1c). This proximity accounts for the high estimated uncertainty in measurements that still meet the error budget.

Less than half (14 out of 33) of the analyzed SWOT WSE data met the error budget of 10 cm. Similarly, for WSS retrieved by SWOT, only half were within the error budget of 1.7 cm/km. We found that the ratio of valid nodes (RVN) for a given reach is not a reliable proxy for trusting a SWOT measurement; while good measurements often have RVN values above 66%, poor measurements can also arise from reaches with high RVN values.

SWOT errors depend on the quality of the pixels measured by the KaRIn instrument and used for WSE and WSS computations. The classification information from the pixel-cloud captured by SWOT distinguishes water pixels from land pixels [13]. This data is used to aggregate high-resolution pixel-cloud data to known river features from the prior river database [9]. Once the pixels are assigned, ensemble measurement quantities for each river feature are computed from the assigned pixels. The pixel-cloud data are first aggregated to the node locations, and then the node attributes are further aggregated to generate the reach attributes [13]. The reach attributes, which are the data used in this study, are expected to meet the 10 cm error budget. However, as discussed in Section III, SWOT presents errors above this budget of which 3 main quality flags were raised: classification, geolocation and water fraction flags.

The classification flag relates to the number of pixels classified as water versus land. This flag could be attributed to the Saigon River's role as a major commercial navigation route, accommodating ships with drafts up to 9 meters [15]. Constant large container ship traffic, along with boat habitation [16], may contribute to the difficulties SWOT faces in obtaining WSE measurements. Additionally, the river is heavily populated with water hyacinths that are visible from space [17] and cover large areas of the water surface. Furthermore, slums, particularly those on stilts over the river and canals in the urban center [18], [19], could further complicate SWOT's ability to distinguish between water and land pixels.

The classification flag is related to the dark water fraction within a reach (Table I). Dark water can cause errors in SWOT measurements due to lower radar backscatter, which weakens the signal-to-noise ratio needed for accurate detection. This often occurs when the water surface is very smooth under low wind conditions [20], leading to specular reflection that causes radar signals to bounce away from the instrument, making the water appear dark. As a result, SWOT may misclassify or entirely miss the water, leading to measurement errors. However, only a small portion of measurements exhibit a high dark water fraction and significant errors are not necessarily linked to high dark water fractions, as shown in Table I.

The geolocation flag pertains to the geolocation accuracy of the pixels identified as water. Geolocation problems can arise from phase unwrapping which is the process of resolving

ambiguities in radar phase measurements, allowing for the accurate retrieval of continuous WSEs from the radar signals [21]. We found evidence of phase unwrapping errors impacting SWOT measurements, particularly at the H2 location for pass 271 (see supplemental material for an illustration of this problem). The proximity of the H2 location to the nadir, combined with the urban environment, increases the likelihood of phase unwrapping issues.

Upon examining the 100 m raster and pixel cloud products from SWOT, we found that in the H2 area, the river is sometimes displaced by approximately 700 meters at the boundary between two pixel-cloud tiles. This displacement likely accounts for the large errors observed, particularly in pass 271. Additionally, this issue may be related to the over-detection of water, which raises the water fraction flag. This flag is raised when the fraction of water within a pixel exceeds acceptable limits. The urban surroundings of the Saigon river are highly impermeable, and rainwater can remain for extended periods, potentially causing flooding [4]. Additionally, human-made canals around it are ubiquitous. These static and ephemeral water surfaces can reduce the quality of the measurements and trigger this type of problem.

Another possible reason for the displacement of the river at the H2 location is the layover effect between land and water pixels. The example given in [6] illustrates rather well the layover effect: suppose that a hill located a few kilometers away from a river might have a distance to the satellite similar to that of the river's center, and thus appear close to the river center in a SWOT image. In contrast, the river banks, being at a different distance from the satellite, could appear several pixels away from the river center pixel. As a result, the top of the hill could be closer to the river center than the river banks. The layover phenomenon is well-known and has been extensively studied [10].

The region under study is part of an extremely flat, low elevation coastal zone, with 65% of Ho Chi Minh City located at less than 1.5 meters above sea level [4]. Indeed, SWOT uncertainty is greatest in flatter areas rather than in regions with complex topography [22]. This is primarily due to layover from topographic features, such as skyscrapers and vegetation around and in the river [6]. Additionally, the layover effect has a greater impact on river slope measurements than on river height, partly explaining the poorer results for SWOT WSS found in this study. The Saigon River's slope fluctuates between -6 cm/km and +6 cm/km due to coastal tidal forces. As a result, the magnitude of the SWOT WSS uncertainty is comparable to the measured slope, increasing the potential for large errors illustrating the need of validation against in situ in such environments.

WSE and WSS are two hydraulic variables essential for river discharge computation and are crucial for assessing a river system. As presented in this letter, SWOT's capability to observe these variables in a very flat, tropical, urbanized coastal area is overall positive, as this environment may be the most challenging for any satellite altimetry mission. However, to fully use SWOT data, it is also important to consider how sampling frequency impacts the derived hydraulic variables at a given site [23]. In the Saigon River, SWOT's temporal

frequency is about 3 measurements per month due to its low latitude and North-South extent, presenting a further challenge to the usability of SWOT data for hydrological studies in the area. Nonetheless, SWOT's unprecedented spatial resolution can still provide valuable insights into the river's behavior. This advantage can potentially be used to better calibrate and validate hydraulic models once more SWOT data is available [24].

In data-scarce regions like this one, in situ data remains crucial despite SWOT's capabilities. SWOT's temporal resolution constraints make it an additional tool rather than a replacement, providing valuable data to complement in situ data and hydraulic models. As the SWOT mission progresses and more data become available, the quality of SWOT products will improve and are thus, posed to become an increasingly valuable resource for enhancing discharge estimates for the Saigon River [7].

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we analyze SWOT water surface elevation (WSE) and water surface slope (WSS) products in a challenging region characterized by flat topography, a tropical urban environment, and a river with a weak slope influenced by strong coastal tidal forces. Our analysis reveals that only about half of the WSE and WSS measurements meet the error budget and both require in situ validation for reliability. Additionally, we identified phase unwrapping and layover as significant sources of error at river locations near the nadir gap.

This letter provides an early assessment of SWOT's potential in such coastal environments. We expect that SWOT's high-resolution 2D observations will improve over time, and together with field data, other satellite data, and modelling efforts, will yield new insights into dynamic phenomena in this and similar coastal zones.

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6.2 Plots and tables for Water Surface Slope

Figure 6.1: Timeseries of water surface slope at the 3 measurement locations H2, H3 and LG in increasingly darker shades of grey. For the sake of readability, the signals are displaced by 11 cm/km. The two SWOT measurements per cycle (pass 90 and pass 271) are presented as dots with error bar. SWOT measurements within the error budget of 10 cm are presented in blue. SWOT measurements with error larger than 10 cm are presented in red.

Table 6.1: Estimated water surface slope error (cm/km) and ratio of valid nodes (%) for each cycle-pass pair and for each in situ location namely between H2-H3 and H3-LG where slope is computed from in situ water surface elevation measurements. SWOT measurements that meet the error budget are highlighted in blue. False positives (which meet error budget but are incorrect) are highlighted in red.

Cycle	Pass	H2-H3		H3-LG	
10	90	0.71	87	1.33	79
10	271	36.7	72	3.79	79
11	90	0.65	96	0.59	92
11	271	49.2	37	3.87	79
12	90	1.69	55	0.99	66
12	271	47.3	38	3.7	77
13	90	0.62	85	0.63	62
13	271	37.27	76	0.76	91
14	90	30.7	69	0.64	98
14	271	38.8	73	3.8	79
15	271	55.8	52	3.8	79

Figure 6.2: Comparison between the SWOT water surface slope product, WSS, and WSS computed from in situ water surface elevation (reference level: EGM2008 Geoid). Data points are shown as green crosses and the $x=y$ line as a black, dashed line. The linear regression equation, number of data points, n , R^2 and p -value values are shown on the upper left corner.

6.3 CONCLUSION

This chapter demonstrates that while the SWOT mission offers promising new capabilities for monitoring hydrological changes in challenging environments like HCMC, there are significant limitations that need to be addressed. The validation of WSE measurements is a positive outcome, but the unreliable

WSS measurements underscore the necessity for in-situ validation.

7

Conclusion and Perspectives

The inherent vulnerabilities of Low-Elevation Coastal Zones (LECZs) due to climate change are profound and multifaceted, impacting both natural environments and human settlements. LECZs, often home to densely populated megacities and crucial ecosystems, face threats from sea level rise, tropical cyclones, subsidence, and human-induced pressures such as pollution and the destruction of natural barriers. These challenges are exacerbated in underdeveloped and developing economies where resources for robust mitigation and adaptation strategies are limited. Understanding the hydrodynamic behaviour of these areas is essential for developing effective early warning systems and flood management plans, making comprehensive and continuous monitoring critical.

To address these monitoring needs, integrating in-situ measurements with satellite observations presents a promising approach. While traditional in-situ methods provide high accuracy and temporal frequency, they are often logistically and financially challenging to maintain, especially in dynamic and hard-to-access coastal environments. Satellite altimetry, despite its lower temporal resolution, offers valuable long-term data and can complement in-situ measurements by providing broader spatial coverage. Missions like the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) satellite are poised to revolutionize the monitoring of LECZs by delivering high-resolution, two-dimensional hydrological variables. By combining the strengths of both monitoring methods, we can enhance our understanding and management of LECZs, thereby better protecting these vulnerable areas against the increasing threats posed by climate change.

In this thesis, we have focused on the data-scarce low-elevation coastal zone surrounding the megacity of Ho Chi Minh. The primary scientific objective was to provide scientific output that could take the research community a

step closer towards understanding this complex system. This was the primary objective of the study of Chapter 2 where we assess the effect of a tropical cyclone on the hydrosystem with a specific focus on the compound flooding associated with it. The two most surprising findings were that i. typhoon Usagi did not make a significant storm surge due to making landfall during a very low spring tide and by producing offshore and shore-parallel winds rather than onshore ones; ii. we found that water levels in the Saigon river are controlled by the seasonal storm surges caused by the East Asian summer monsoon rather than by continental factors like rainfall-runoff, which makes it behave in unison with the coastal tide almost as a dead arm of the sea. The main contribution of Chapter 2 to the scientific community is to add a case study based on observations that can help validate future statistical and physical flood modelling efforts in HCMC and address the growing demand for understanding the combined impacts of different flood drivers in the region.

In order to fulfil the general objective of this thesis, several research sub-goals were identified. These research sub-goals were successfully completed and are summarized below:

1. **Contribute to the body of data on the hydrological system surrounding the Ho Chi Minh megacity.**

In Chapter 2, the assessment of precipitation products over Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC) revealed that datasets like the GPCC, CMORPH, IMERG, and particularly MSWEP, demonstrate a good performance in capturing precipitation patterns around HCMC. This was the first instance of a validation effort of this kind over this region. This provides the research community with a baseline to which choose precipitation datasets for other studies over the region. Additionally, we demonstrate that a comprehensive study can be achieved by leveraging international cooperation to gather data in a data poor region such as this one.

In Chapter 3, we present the 2-month field campaign effort to obtain high-resolution water level and discharge data from the Saigon and Dongnai rivers. This data is unprecedented in the region and was made available in open-access to the community. Similarly, in Chapter 4, we present a modelling effort of the Saigon and Dongnai system of which output is also made publicly available to the community.

2. **Implement, calibrate and validate a 1D hydrodynamic model of the Saigon and Dongnai river system traversing the Ho Chi Minh megacity.**

In Chapter 4, we explore different calibration strategies for a 1D hydrodynamic model over the Saigon and Dongnai rivers. This study puts

forward the challenges of obtaining a reliable model of such highly dynamical rivers that are in poorly gauged or ungauged regions. Even though, and thanks to the fact that discharge in these rivers is mainly controlled by the coastal tide, we achieve a reasonably good model with only an approximation of the upstream boundary conditions. Additionally, we are able to improve the 1D model discharge output by coupling it with a simpler modified Manning-Strickler flow law. This modelling effort offers valuable implications for water resource management and decision-making, with all model outputs provided in an open-access format to support further research and application.

3. Provide a thorough assessment of the potential of SWOT satellite products to improve discharge estimation in the Saigon river (prior to having access to real SWOT data)

In Chapter 5 we achieve this objective by using synthetic SWOT data, applying a stage-fall-discharge rating curve, and performing a Monte Carlo analysis to account for measurement errors. We tested various river reach sizes, finding that a 20 km reach size optimally balanced discharge estimation accuracy and computation time. By comparing synthetic true discharge values with SWOT-based estimates, the study demonstrated that SWOT measurements could reliably capture the flow regime of the Saigon River, especially for high and consistent discharges. This comprehensive approach, despite the absence of real SWOT data, underscored SWOT's potential to enhance hydrological monitoring and water resource management in tidal river environments.

4. Evaluate SWOT river products against in-situ measurements in the Saigon river (once SWOT data available)

In Chapter 6, we thoroughly evaluated the SWOT river products against in-situ measurements in the Saigon River. The comparison revealed that while the SWOT water surface elevation (WSE) measurements were generally accurate, the water surface slope (WSS) measurements often lacked accuracy and required validation against in-situ data. The study highlighted that only about half of the WSE measurements were within the acceptable error range, and there was no reliable correlation for WSS measurements. This evaluation underscores the necessity of combining SWOT data with in-situ measurements to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the hydrological models and discharge estimates derived from SWOT products .

The advent of the SWOT mission alone cannot fully address the complexities of the low elevation coastal zone (LECZ) of the Saigon-Dong Nai

river system. The primary advantage SWOT offers is insights into the spatial variability of water levels, owing to its unprecedented two-dimensional spatial coverage. However, as discussed in Chapter 6, this does not extend to other hydraulic variables such as river slope and discharge. Over time, as the SWOT mission generates a more extensive dataset (currently only three measurements per month in this river system), its data will become increasingly valuable.

The SWOT satellite represents a significant addition to the existing body of knowledge but needs to be complemented by in-situ probes and numerical modelling. However, achieving a comprehensive understanding of hydrodynamics and developing effective early warning systems for extreme events necessitates a robust monitoring program. Key locations in the Saigon and Dongnai rivers must be monitored for hydraulic variables, and both hydraulic and flood numerical models thoroughly implemented, calibrated and validated. This effort also requires other high-quality data such as river bathymetry, topography, land cover and precipitation data.

Furthermore, an effective monitoring system must be supported by the local government, as most accessible riverbanks are government-owned and not open to the public. Government involvement can help mitigate issues such as vandalism and theft of sensors. Ideally, this monitoring program should be established through international cooperation, with local and foreign researchers and experts sharing their expertise with Vietnamese authorities. Developing countries that actively engage in international scientific collaboration tend to have higher scientific productivity and produce more impactful research (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2016). A notable example of long-term international collaboration is the CARE laboratory, a Franco-Vietnamese institution that has focused on water resource research for over 10 years. Despite such successful examples, international cooperation remains challenging between Western and underdeveloped or developing nations for the following reasons:

Firstly, hydraulic variables are valuable and sensitive sovereign information that governments are careful about sharing. It is possible that the region under study is already extensively monitored, with data not accessible to foreign entities, a scenario known as a "politically ungauged region". Currently, there is a 48h per month monitoring effort led at several locations along the Saigon-Dongnai river system. This effort is conducted by the Sub-Institute of Hydrometeorology and Climate Change (SIHYMECC), a local Vietnamese agency. This is already a high monitoring effort that proved useful for the modelling carried on in Chapter 4. Nonetheless, a constant monitoring of hydraulic variables is required to achieve a more reliable hydrodynamic modelling of this system. However, questions arise about funding for monitoring infrastructure, staff, maintenance, and data acquisition and processing. Such efforts require long-term commitment, which may not be prioritized over other

adaptation and mitigation infrastructures such as levees and sea barriers. Additionally, the willingness of international institutions to fund and support the development of this monitoring system is uncertain.

Secondly, in under-developed and developing countries there often exists a gap between the local and international research institutions. Local researchers collaborate with international partners only to a limited extent. A significant portion of local literature is not published in internationally recognized scientific journals. This is partly due to the international scientific community's reluctance to accept local journals, often published in the local language, as more than grey literature (Matthews et al. 2020). This reluctance is tied to language barriers and a lack of trust in the scientific rigour of local institutions, even though this might not hold true. Moreover, local institutions may be unable to afford the absurdly high article processing charges, demanded by western journals, or simply not prioritize these costs in their budgets (Borrego 2023). This creates a significant gap between the local and international scientific knowledge as well as between scientific communities of developing and developed countries. Hence, impeding international cooperation for large-scale national monitoring projects.

Thirdly, scientific practices vary significantly across different countries and cultural contexts, leading to potential conflicting views on data-sharing norms. In some regions, scientific data is treated as a commodity, creating a market where the selling of hydrological data, for example, is common. This practice, while understandable given the underpayment of researchers worldwide, hinders the implementation of an open monitoring system. The integrity of purchased data can be questionable, and economic interests restrict accessibility. There is a disincentive to share data publicly and openly, undermining the potential for a transparent and effective monitoring system. Although this is speculative, it highlights significant challenges related to data accessibility in underdeveloped and developing countries.

Looking forward, the integration of the SWOT satellite data with existing and prospective in-situ monitoring efforts holds significant promise for advancing hydrodynamic modelling and water resource management around Ho Chi Minh City. As the SWOT mission continues to collect data, its comprehensive spatial coverage might improve our understanding of water level variability. However, the true potential of SWOT can only be realized through a robust, monitoring infrastructure that encompasses key hydraulic variables and high-quality bathymetric data. Such an infrastructure would not only improve our hydrodynamic models but also provide critical early warning systems for extreme events.

An additional exciting perspective that could bring a crucial monitoring tool to the region is the Spatial Altimetry Mission for Surface Hydrology

(SMASH) mission under consideration by the CNES (Becker et al. 2018). The primary objective of SMASH is to observe continental water bodies with a very high temporal revisit rate, specifically providing daily observations. This mission is designed to address the limitations of current satellite altimetry missions by offering more frequent data, which is crucial for understanding and managing continental water resources. SMASH aims to achieve this with a simplified payload and reduced satellite resource demands, making it a cost-effective alternative to previous proposals. However, the mission’s high-frequency temporal data will be invaluable for a wide range of scientific applications, including oceanography, estuarine and coastal studies, snow cover monitoring, and operational water management. The daily measurements of water elevations from SMASH could complement the spatial data provided by SWOT, opening new avenues for research and applications in the Saigon-Dongnai estuary.

Finally, international cooperation could play a pivotal role in this development, bringing in expertise and financial resources. However, addressing the political and economic challenges associated with data sharing and accessibility will be essential. Bridging the gap between local and international scientific communities through open-access publications and reduced article processing charges could foster greater collaboration and data transparency. Ultimately, a well-coordinated monitoring program, supported either by national, international or both stakeholders, will be crucial for sustainable water resource management and disaster mitigation in this vulnerable coastal zone.

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A

Studying the Manning-Strickler Equation for tidal rivers

In this appendix we will perform a thorough analysis of the modified Manning-Strickler (MS) equation for tidal rivers that has been used to estimate discharge. The MS equation, traditionally employed for open-channel flow, has been adapted to accommodate the dynamic conditions of tidal rivers, providing a vital tool throughout this work.

Firstly, we address the calibration of key parameters within the modified MS equation. Traditional manual calibration methods, while useful, are time-consuming and often suboptimal. By implementing a Non-linear Least-Squares (NLLS) curve fitting technique, we aim to improve the precision of parameter calibration, thereby enhancing the model's accuracy in predicting water discharge under varying tidal conditions. The results from this calibration have been used in Chapter 2 to compute the Saigon river discharge during Typhoon Usagi.

Secondly, we conduct a Variance-based Sensitivity Analysis (VBSA) to ascertain the influence of different parameters on the model's output. This analysis not only helps in understanding the relative importance of each parameter but also in identifying potential areas for model improvement. The VBSA is performed using Monte Carlo sampling with Sobol sequences.

The results and discussions presented in this appendix underscore the complexities of tidal river systems and the necessity for sophisticated modelling approaches. By refining the Manning-Strickler equation and applying advanced calibration and sensitivity analysis techniques, we aim to contribute to a better understanding and quantifying the weaknesses of this flow law when applied to tidal rivers.

A.1 Water Discharge Estimation

Throughout this thesis, instantaneous water discharge was estimated by applying a stage-fall-discharge (SFD) rating curve adapted from the general Manning-Strickler law (Equation A.1), previously tested and validated by Camenen et al. 2017 and used to predict the total discharge of the Saigon river in Camenen et al. 2021:

$$Q(t) = \text{sign}(S) \cdot K \cdot A_w(t) \cdot R_h(t)^{2/3} \cdot \sqrt{|S(t + \Delta t)|}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with Q the water discharge [m^3s^{-1}], $K = 27.06 m^{1/3}s^{-1}$ the Manning-Strickler coefficient, $R_h = A_w/P_w$ the hydraulic radius [m], A_w the wet section [m^2], P_w the wet perimeter [m]. Note that A_w and P_w are both a function of the water level and thus, of time. The term $\text{sign}(S)$ is equal to the sign of the slope, S , taking the values of +1 or -1. The energy slope, S [-], is assumed equal to the water slope and is computed as:

$$S = \frac{H_{up} - H_{dn} + dH}{L}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

with the water level H_{up} and H_{dn} measured at Phu Cuong (PC) and Thao Dien (TD), respectively, and L the distance between the two locations. Two additional terms are used in this model: dH and Δt . The former is used to compensate the fact that the reference points of each location are different and unknown. The latter is a time lag required to account for the propagation of the tidal wave between one location to the other. The values used in this study were $dH = -0.149$ m and $\Delta t = -2$ h. The full observed water levels at Phu Cuong and Thao Dien were used to compute the total discharge of the Saigon river (see Chapter 2).

A.2 Improving the calibration of parameters using Non-linear Least-Squares curve fitting

For the asymmetric tide of March 2017, the study conducted by Camenen et al. 2021 reported the best results with a root mean square error (RMSE) of approximately $350 m^3/s$. This outcome was achieved using a Manning-Strickler coefficient (K) of $26 m^{1/3}/s$ and a time lag (dt) of -2 hours. Although the paper did not specify the dz value, it was found to be -0.15 meters based on the code provided by Dr. Benoit Camenen. Calibration results from Camenen et al. 2021 are shown in Figure A.1.

Fig. A.11. Sensitivity of the Strickler coefficient K (a) and time shift Δt (b) on the error calculation compared to ADCP campaigns

Figure A.1: ADCP campaign and calibration curve for PC-TD experiment as in Camenen et al. 2021.

In Camenen et al. 2021, the model calibration is done using two campaigns: i. March 2017 during an asymmetric tide and ii. September 2016 during a symmetric tide. During the asymmetric tide the model has much more difficulty following the discharge measurements than during the symmetric tide (Figure A.1). The parameters K , dt and dH are calibrated by hand. This is one common way of calibrating models, where you start by visualizing the time-series and intuitively try some parameter values and change them over and over until you achieve a good enough fit to the measurements. In Camenen et al. 2021 the parameters are tweaked one at a time to optimize the RMSE. This provided good results (see Figure A.1), however it is time consuming and I believed that it could be improved by using a simple non-linear least squares (NLLS) fitting technique: where I fit equation A.1 to the ADCP measurements by adjusting the 3 parameters mentioned above.

Applying the Non-linear Least Squares (NLLS) technique, the calibration results were significantly improved. The NLLS method yielded an RMSE of approximately 185 m³/s using a Manning-Strickler coefficient (K) of 27 m^{1/3}/s, a time lag (dt) of -2.0 hours, and a dz value of -0.149 meters. These findings are illustrated in Figure A.2.

For the symmetric tide of September 2016, Camenen et al. (2021) reported the best results with an RMSE of 195 m³/s, using a Manning-Strickler coefficient (K) of 25 m^{1/3}/s and a time lag (dt) of -1.9 hours. Due to abnormal behavior in the data, the NLLS technique could not be verified for this campaign. However, given the superior results obtained for the March 2017 asymmetric tide, it was concluded that the parameters identified in the second point were adequate.

Figure A.2: ADCP campaign and calibration curve for PC-TD experiment using NLLS curve fitting.

A.3 Variance-based Sensitivity Analysis (VBSA)

Variance-based sensitivity analysis (often referred to as the Sobol method or Sobol indices) is a form of global sensitivity analysis (Sobol 2001; Saltelli et al. 2007). Working within a probabilistic framework, it decomposes the variance of the output of the model into fractions which can be attributed to inputs or sets of inputs. For example, given a model with two inputs and one output, one might find that 70% of the output variance is caused by the variance in the first input, 20% by the variance in the second, and 10% due to interactions between the two. These percentages are directly interpreted as measures of sensitivity. Variance-based measures of sensitivity are attractive because they measure sensitivity across the whole input space, they can deal with nonlinear responses, and they can measure the effect of interactions in non-additive systems.

Decomposition of Variance:

From a black box perspective, any model may be viewed as a function $Y = f(X)$, where X is a vector of d uncertain model inputs X_1, X_2, \dots, X_d , and Y is a chosen univariate model output. Furthermore, it will be assumed that the inputs are independently and uniformly distributed within the unit hypercube, i.e. $X_i \in [0, 1]$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, d$. This incurs no loss of generality because any input space can be transformed onto this unit hypercube. $f(X)$ may be decomposed in the following way (Sobol 1993),

$$Y = f_0 + \sum_{i=1}^d f_i(X_i) + \sum_{i<j}^d f_{ij}(X_i, X_j) + \dots + f_{1,2,\dots,d}(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_d), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where f_0 is a constant and f_i is a function of X_i , f_{ij} a function of X_i and X_j , etc. A condition of this decomposition is that all the terms in the functional decomposition are orthogonal (i.e. Y is decomposed in functions that are not

a linear combination of each other and thus, can be used to form a basis of a function space), namely:

$$\int_0^1 f_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_s}(X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}, \dots, X_{i_s}) dX_k = 0, \text{ for } k = i_1, \dots, i_s. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

We can then define the conditional expected values for each of the terms of the functional decomposition:

$$f_0 = E(Y), \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$f_i(X_i) = E(Y|X_i) - f_0, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$f_{ij}(X_i, X_j) = E(Y|X_i, X_j) - f_0 - f_i - f_j. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

From which it can be seen that f_i is the effect of varying X_i alone (known as the main effect of X_i), and f_{ij} is the effect of varying X_i and X_j simultaneously, additional to the effect of their individual variations. This is known as a second-order interaction. Higher-order terms have analogous definitions.

Further assuming that the $f(X)$ is square-integrable, the functional decomposition may be squared and integrated to give,

$$\int f^2(\mathbf{X}) d\mathbf{X} - f_0^2 = \sum_{s=1}^d \sum_{i_1 < \dots < i_s} \int f_{i_1 \dots i_s}^2 dX_{i_1} \dots dX_{i_s}, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Notice that the left hand side is equal to the variance of Y , and the terms of the right hand side are variance terms, now decomposed with respect to sets of the X_i . This finally leads to the decomposition of variance expression,

$$\text{Var}(Y) = \sum_{i=1}^d V_i + \sum_{i < j} V_{ij} + \dots + V_{12\dots d}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where

$$V_i = \text{Var}_{X_i}(E_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(Y | X_i)), \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$V_{ij} = \text{Var}_{X_{ij}}(E_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim ij}}(Y | X_i, X_j)) - V_i - V_j, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

and so on. The $X_{\sim i}$ notation indicates the set of all variables except X_i . The above variance decomposition shows how the variance of the model output can be decomposed into terms attributable to each input, as well as the interaction effects between them. Together, all terms sum to the total variance of the model output.

First-order Indices:

A direct variance-based measure of sensitivity S_i , called the "first-order sensitivity index", is stated as follows (Sobol 1993),

$$S_i = \frac{V_i}{\text{Var}(Y)} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

This is the contribution to the output variance of the main effect of X_i , therefore it measures the effect of varying X_i alone, but averaged over variations in other input parameters. It is standardised by the total variance to provide a fractional contribution. Higher-order interaction indices S_{ij} , S_{ijk} and so on can be formed by dividing other terms in the variance decomposition by $\text{Var}(Y)$. Note that this has the implication that,

$$\sum_{i=1}^d S_i + \sum_{i<j}^d S_{ij} + \dots + S_{1,2,\dots,d} = 1. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Total-effect index:

Using the S_i , S_{ij} and higher-order indices given above, one can build a picture of the importance of each variable in determining the output variance. However, when the number of variables is large, this requires the evaluation of $2d - 1$ indices, which can be too computationally demanding. For this reason, a measure known as the "Total-effect index", ST_i , is used (Homma et al. 1996). This measures the contribution to the output variance of X_i , including all variance caused by its interactions, of any order, with any other input variables. It is given as,

$$S_{Ti} = \frac{E_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y | \mathbf{X}_{\sim i}))}{\text{Var}(Y)} = 1 - \frac{\text{Var}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(E_{X_i}(Y | \mathbf{X}_{\sim i}))}{\text{Var}(Y)}. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Note that unlike the S_i ,

$$\sum_{i=1}^d S_{Ti} \geq 1, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

due to the fact that the interaction effect between e.g. X_i and X_j is counted in both S_{Ti} and S_{Tj} . In fact, the sum of the S_{Ti} will only be equal to 1 when the model is purely additive.

A.3.1 Monte Carlo Sampling to perform the VBSA

In order for a variance to be computed, several instances of the model output must be generated using different combinations of values for the parameters. In order to do this the Sobol quasi-random (QR) sequences proposed in (Saltelli et al. 2010). QR sequences are specifically designed to generate samples of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k as uniformly as possible over the unit hypercube. Unlike random numbers, successive quasi-random points know about the position of previously sampled points and fill the gaps between them. For this reason they are also called quasi-random numbers although they are not random. Using

this sampling technique I obtained several sequences of values for each parameter (K , dt and dz) and performed the VBSA. For more information on this sampling technique see Saltelli et al. 2010.

The 95% confidence interval was obtained via a bootstrap method. The upper and lower limits being equal to the 98.5th and 2.5th percentiles of the samples.

A.4 Results and Discussion

The methodology presented in the above sections has been implemented for the Modified Manning-Strickler equation using the open-source Python library SALib (Herman et al. 2017; Iwanaga et al. 2022). The results are discussed below.

The first-order sensitivity of the equation differs between symmetric and asymmetric tides, influencing its behavior and the factors that affect its output.

For symmetric tides, three main modes are observed: "classic" river behavior (positive discharge), "inverse" river behavior (negative discharge), and a transition mode between the two (see Figure A.3). During the "classic" mode, the equation computes discharge as if the river is unaffected by tides, and the output is not influenced by the time lag (dt). However, the sensitivity to the Manning-Strickler coefficient (K) and the vertical offset (dz) is similar. In the transition mode, there is a rapid change in discharge, switching from positive to negative (and vice-versa) within an hour. This mode includes the high slack water when discharge shifts from negative to positive ("inverse" to "classic" river), where the tide reaches its peak and starts flowing out again. Here, the equation is equally sensitive to dt and dz . Conversely, during low slack water when discharge transitions from positive to negative ("classic" to "inverse" river), the equation is almost solely sensitive to dt . This indicates that the transition from "classic" to "inverse" river is driven by the time lag between downstream and upstream water height, meaning the propagation of the water level signal controls this mode. In the "inverse" river mode, both K and dz are significant, but the equation appears more sensitive to dz .

For asymmetric tides, the behavior is primarily divided into two modes: "classic" and "inverse" river behavior (see Figure A.4). However, the "classic" behavior exhibits oscillation by slowing down and then increasing again before reaching low slack water, a phenomenon attributed to non-linear shallow-water dynamics that modulate the tidal wave and create double tides. In this scenario, dz predominantly influences the equation's output. This is evident when examining the ADCP campaign during an asymmetric tide (Figure A.2). The second local minimum of the discharge curve is negative but significantly weaker ($1/2$) than the other two minima. The calibrated model's asymmetric

Figure A.3: Symmetric tide and sensitivity analysis to parameters dz , dt and K .

discharge (blue curve in Figure A.4) fails to accurately capture this second minimum, resulting in higher uncertainty around this point compared to symmetric tides (Figure A.3).

The equation struggles to predict discharge accurately around the periods of slack water (both high and low slack water), resulting in high uncertainty in the discharge values. This challenge is also present in asymmetric tides, where despite high and positive discharge, the uncertainty increases substantially.

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Figure A.4: Asymmetric tide and sensitivity analysis to parameters dz , dt and K . Shaded areas are the 95% confidence interval. As can be seen, the 2nd-order indices are negligible when compared to the 1st order ones, which hints that there is little pairwise interaction between parameters. Additionally, the Total-effect index is similar to the first order index which further justifies that each parameter is independent in the way it affects the output of the model.

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B

Modelling the Saigon river using C-GEM

In this appendix, we appropriate the work of our colleague Dr. An Nguyen Truong from the IGE that implemented and calibrated the C-GEM estuarine model to the Saigon river. This model is not as accurate as the MAGE model since its main focus is carbon transport. However, at the time of writing the MAGE model was not available. Previous applications of this model to the Saigon River estuary have facilitated studies on biogeochemistry, demonstrating the model's capability after necessary calibration and validation. However, applying C-GEM to the Saigon River poses specific challenges due to its unique characteristics and interactions with the Dongnai River, which significantly influences its hydrodynamics.

The C-GEM model accurately represents tidal range but it struggles with accurately simulating water levels. Therefore, this study focuses on analysing percentage differences between various model scenarios in relation to a reference model run. The insights gained from this approach aim to enhance our understanding of the Saigon River system's response to different hydrodynamic scenarios: changes in dam water discharge, changes in the Dongnai river discharge and sudden and seasonal coastal surges.

B.1 C-GEM Hydrodynamics module

Estuaries are subject to two main forcings: tidal variations of water level at the mouth and freshwater inflow upstream. The first induces a tidal wave that travels upstream and is progressively distorted due to the combined effects of river geometry and discharge. The amplitude of the tide along the estuary is determined by the balance between energy gain due to channel convergence

and energy loss through bed friction. Therefore, fundamental hydrodynamic characteristics such as tidal range, tidal excursion and the phase lag of the tidal wave can be related to the estuary's geometric characteristics. Although alluvial estuaries display a variety of shapes, they have common geometric characteristics that are compatible with an idealized representation of an estuary (Savenije 2005). For tidally averaged conditions, their width \bar{B} can be described by an exponential function decreasing with distance, x , from the mouth:

$$\bar{B}(x) = B_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{x}{b}\right) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where x is the distance from estuary mouth [m], B_0 is the width at estuary mouth [m], b is the width convergence length [m]. For weakly stratified or well-mixed estuaries whose depth is much smaller than width, the hydrodynamics can be described by the one-dimensional barotropic, cross-sectionally integrated mass and momentum conservation equations for a channel with arbitrary geometry (Nihoul et al. 1976; Regnier, Mouchet, et al. 1998; Regnier and Steefel 1999):

$$r_s \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} = -g \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} - g \frac{U|U|}{C^2 H} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where $t = \text{time}$ (in s), $A = \text{cross-sectional area}$ ($A = H \cdot \bar{B}$) (in m^2), $Q = \text{cross-sectional discharge}$ ($Q = A \cdot U$) (in $m^3 s^{-1}$), $U = \text{flow velocity}$ (in $m^2 s^{-1}$), $r_s = \text{storage ratio}$ ($r_s = B_s / \bar{B}$)(-), $B_s = \text{storage width}$ (in m), $C = \text{Chézy coefficient}$ (in $m^{1/2} s^{-1}$), and $H = \text{water depth}$ ($H = h + \xi(x, t)$) (in m).

The C-GEM (Carbon-Generic Estuary Model) developed by Volta et al. 2014 reduces data requirements by using the generic, theoretical framework presented above. This yields a computationally efficient model which is still able to provide an accurate description of estuarine hydrodynamics (Volta et al. 2014), salt transport and biogeochemistry on the appropriate spatio-temporal scales. The coupled partial differential equations (Eqs. B.2 and B.3) are solved by specifying the elevation ξ_0 at the estuarine mouth and the river discharge $Q_r(t)$ at the upstream limit of the model domain. Bed friction exerted on the moving water is described by means of a roughness formulation following Manning–Strickler (Savenije 2012):

$$C = \frac{1}{n} H^{1/6}, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where C is the Chézy coefficient, n is the dimensionless Manning number and H is the water depth.

B.1.1 C-GEM applied to the Saigon river system

In order to gain further insights into the hydrodynamics of the Saigon river system the hydrodynamics module of C-GEM was used. This model has been successfully applied to the Saigon river estuary for studies dealing with biogeochemistry (A. Nguyen et al. 2020; A. T. Nguyen et al. 2021). Hence, the required calibration and validation of the model for this estuary has been already performed. This provides a ready-to-use tool for a broader study of the dynamics of the Saigon as described by C-GEM. However, the limitations of applying this model to the Saigon river must be taken into account. First, the Saigon river is a tributary of the Dongnai river which is a much wider river with a much larger discharge, both quantities larger by 1 order of magnitude. However, in the model the Dongnai is artificially used as a tributary of the Saigon river (note the model's domain in figure B.1). This creates an abrupt decrease in width and input of discharge at the confluence of these two rivers (km 142 in the domain) which in turn gives rise to hydrodynamic behaviour that might not be realistic. As can be seen in figure B.2, the model behaves strangely around the confluence and provides results that might be affected by numerical errors or instabilities. Henceforth, we will distinguish three parts of the domain of C-GEM: 1. the Saigon part from km 0 to km 125, 2. an adjustment part from km 125 to km 142 and 3. the Dongnai part from km 142 to km 200. The second part of the domain, will be left out of the discussion. Thus, the results related to the impact of the Dongnai BC must be carefully interpreted.

The second limitation of this C-GEM application is that even though tidal range and salinity are well represented by the model (A. T. Nguyen et al. 2021), it does not accurately represent water level. Thus, the absolute values of water level and other variables derived from it (such as slope) are not relevant. In order to obtain insights using C-GEM we study the percentage difference between several model scenarios rather than the absolute values of its outputs. However, we also present the absolute error for each variable to have an idea of the magnitude of the values under scope. This methodology should provide an overview of how the Saigon system reacts to different scenarios.

On the previous sections we used a modified Manning-Strickler law where the slope between the stations of PC and BD allowed the computation of a discharge. Further, it was seen that the discharge was de-coupled from extreme precipitation at the end of 2018. We entertained the hypothesis that this is due to the fact that the slope of the Saigon is partly controlled by downstream dynamics (coastal, perhaps) and thus, so is the discharge. In the next subsections, we want to complement this analysis by studying the outputs of C-GEM. Firstly, we look into a direct output of the model: the velocity, U , which is directly related to discharge. Secondly, we compute the slope, S , at

each domain point as,

$$S = \frac{z_{up} - z_{dn}}{2000}, \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where z_{up} and z_{dn} are the direct output of water level for an upstream and a downstream point, respectively, which are separated by a distance of 2 km. Finally, we look into the daily tidal range, Tr , since it is the variable that has been used for the model's validation in A. T. Nguyen et al. 2021. This variable is computed as the difference between the maximum and minimum water levels in a given day. The average over a season of each of these variables will be studied.

Modelling the Saigon system with C-GEM requires the definition of three boundary conditions (BCs):

1. The water elevation at the estuary mouth (km 200). Hereafter, referred to as the *Coastal BC*.
2. The freshwater discharge at the upstream limit (km 0). Hereafter, referred to as the *Dam BC*.
3. The Dongnai river discharge at the confluence (km 142). Hereafter, referred to as the *DN BC*.

Figure B.1: The domain of C-GEM (left, in pink). Figure taken from A. T. Nguyen et al. 2021. The three BCs used for the B experiment (right). Units are m³/s for the discharge and m for water level.

In this work we refer to the experiment validated and used in A. T. Nguyen et al. 2021 as the base experiment. The BCs used in this experiment can be seen in figure B.1. The Dam and Dongnai BCs are artificially constructed using step signals and respect the wet/dry seasonal variations. The absolute values of discharge for the Dam BC that are used are much larger than in reality (maximum of $30m^3/s$). On the other hand, the Dongnai discharge values are constructed based on T. T. N. Nguyen et al. 2019 which presents data on mean monthly discharge (period 2012–2016) of the Dongnai River from the Department Of Natural Resources and Environment of HCMC (DONRE). The Coastal BC is based on hourly observations (Caldwell et al. 2015) at the Vung Tau station located about 200 km away from the mouth of the estuary. These observations are de-trended by subtraction of the mean. Then, the measured mean depth at the estuary mouth (period 2008-2009) is added to this time series, which finally results in the BC found in plot 3 of figure B.1. It can be seen that there is a seasonal variation where average water levels are lower during the wet season.

In figure B.2, along river profiles of width and cross-sectional area can be found. Additionally, locations of interest are highlighted by vertical lines namely, the water quality stations at Phu Cuong (PC), Bach Dang (BD) and Binh Khanh (BK) and the confluence with the Dongnai river. As can be seen, the jump in width and cross-sectional area is evident at the confluence with the Dongnai river.

In figure B.2, plots of the along river average profiles of U , S and Tr can be found. It can be seen that C-GEM gives an average negative velocity over the period of 1 season for both dry and wet seasons. Thus, there is an average discharge towards the coast for each point on the domain for both seasons. Additionally, two areas show an interesting behaviour: downstream of the dam and around the Dongnai confluence. At the dam, the discharge is stronger in the wet season as given by the BC and thus, we see a faster average U . Near the dam, one can outline two behaviours: Firstly, the negative average velocity tends to zero as we move downstream and it reaches a near constant value (-0.015 m/s for the dry season and -0.025 m/s for the wet season) at about 60 km away from the dam. Given that the average velocity value is close to zero one can state that at this location the dam’s discharge is no longer driving the velocity and hence, the discharge of the river. Secondly, a gradual increase in the envelope around the average can be seen as we move away from the dam. The larger this envelope is, the larger is the fluctuation of the velocity over time. Thus, as we move away from the dam there is a gradual increase of the tidal forcing. Given these two behaviours one can state that:

1. the dam’s discharge is the main driver of the river’s discharge up to a given downstream location;

Figure B.2: Along x mean profiles for the geometry of the Saigon river in the model C-GEM (left). The blue values are the average for the corresponding 25 km section. Along x mean profiles for the base experiment (right). The shaded area are 1 standard deviation from the mean.

2. At that location the tidal fluctuations at the coast seem to take over as the main driver.

Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning that the DN BC presents the same seasonality as the dam's discharge and thus, the Dongnai discharge has a potential effect that needs to be disentangled from the dam's effect.

Around the confluence with the Dongnai river one can see a negative average velocity that continues up to 18 km upstream, around the BD station (figure B.2). During the wet season the average U is larger than for the dry season which is in accordance with the seasonality of the dam BC. However, the DN BC and the coastal BC present the same seasonality and once again, the characterization of this behaviour requires the separation of these BCs. One can see that C-GEM presents the Saigon river has having average negative velocity. This velocity is increased at its boundaries such that at the dam upstream there is an input of water and downstream at the confluence there is an output of water. Thus, at these boundaries it seems as though the tidal effects on velocity and hence, discharge are overshadowed by the other BCs.

We found that there are seasonal differences near the dam and near the DN confluence. The question is which BC or combination of BCs is responsible for this variation. All three BCs present a seasonality (wet vs dry season) which will have an impact on the behaviour of the Saigon system. In order to

understand which seasonal effects are attributed to which BC, the seasonality of the BCs must be disentangled. To do so one must isolate or remove each BC’s seasonality and study their impact on the model’s output at the locations of interest. The behaviour of the Saigon system will be studied by leveraging different combinations of BCs. Each combination provides a new instance of the model and will be referred to as an *experiment*. Several experiments are carried out for the duration of 1 year and compared. The objective is to understand how each BC affects hydrodynamic variables given the two other BCs. In table B.1, the experiments that will be detailed in the following sub-sections are summarized.

Table B.1: Boundary conditions (BCs) used for the experiments with the model C-GEM. The ID is the name to which each experiment is referred to in the text. The upstream boundary condition is referred to as "Dam", the Dongnai BC is referred to as "Dongnai" and the coastal BC as "Coastal". "Real" refers to the realistic BCs used in the calibrated model of (A. T. Nguyen et al. 2021).

ID	Dam	Dongnai	Coast
Base	Real	Real	Real
1	Constant	Real	Real
2	Real	Constant	Real
3	Real	Real	Tidal cycle
4	Real	Real	Tidal cycle+Step
5	Constant + Step	Real	Real
Storm	Real	Real	Tidal cycle+Surges

B.2 Metrics for comparison between experiments

In order to compare two experiments we compute the percentage difference, PD , for the seasonal average of each variable. The percentage difference between two experiments is computed as

$$PD^i = \frac{x_2^i - x_1^i}{x_1^i} \cdot 100, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where x_1^i and x_2^i are the average value of a variable at km i for experiment 1 and 2, respectively. For a section from km a to km b , the average value is computed as

$$\overline{PD} = \frac{\sum_{i=a}^b PD^i}{b - a}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Additionally, we use the absolute error to compare two experiments namely,

$$AE^i = |x_2^i - x_1^i|, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where x_1^i and x_2^i are the average value of a variable at km i for experiment 1 and 2, respectively.

B.3 Analysis of Dam and Dongnai boundary conditions

In this section, two experiments will be compared to the base experiment. Experiment 1 will have the value of the dam BC set to a constant. This constant value is of 30 m³/s which is representative of dry season discharge values in the base experiment. Similarly, experiment 2 will see the Dongnai BC set to a constant representative of the dry season namely, 450 m³/s. Turning each of these BCs to constants removes their seasonality when compared to the base experiment. The base experiment has discharge values for the dam and Dongnai that are larger during the wet season. For a given experiment, the model will be mainly affected during the wet season where the BC value has decreased. Therefore, comparing the wet season of an experiment to the wet season of the base experiment will provide insights into the model's reaction to the BC change.

Figure B.3: Along x profiles for velocity, slope and tidal range for experiment 1 (constant dam) and experiment 2 (constant Dongnai). The shaded area are 1 standard deviation from the mean.

Figure B.3 shows the along river profiles of the variables under scope (velocity, slope and tidal range) for both experiments as presented for the base experiment in figure B.2. When comparing experiment 1 (constant dam) with the base experiment it can be seen that removing the seasonality of the dam, i.e. decreasing the discharge during the wet season, has a clear impact on the Saigon part of the domain. In fact, there is no distinction between the two seasons in this section which implies that the dam's discharge is controlling the velocity and slope along the Saigon. The plots for PD and AE are shown in figure B.4 where a velocity reduction by around 60% (AE up to 0.125 m/s) can be seen between the dam and the PC station. The slope shows a decrease between 60 and 80% (AE up to $4e-5$ m) on the same section. However, this decrease might be due to the large values of discharge constructed for this BC in the base experiment leading to a stronger effect on hydrodynamic variables than in reality.

- Halving the discharge of the dam results in a reduction of the velocity by 60% along the Saigon river.
- Halving the discharge of the dam results in a reduction of the slope between 60-80% along the Saigon river.

The Dongnai part of the domain felt the impact of the BC change to a lower extent (PD ↓ 4%) given the much stronger Dongnai discharge at km 142 and the effect of the coastal BC downstream. Additionally, one can see that the reduction in dam discharge led to a gradual reduction in tidal range. This reduction starts at km 25 and reduces Tr by 60% ($AE = 0.4$ m) at km 0. This indicates that there is an inverse relationship between discharge and tidal range where larger dam discharge reduces the tidal range near the dam.

- Halving the discharge of the dam results in a augmentation by 60% of tidal range near the dam.

The percentage difference and absolute error between experiment 2 (constant Dongnai, right plot on figure B.3) and the base experiment (figure B.2) can be found in figure B.5. Removing the seasonality of the Dongnai, i.e. decreasing the discharge during the wet season, impacts both Saigon and Dongnai river. The velocity and the slope are reduced along the Dongnai by around 60% (AE between 0.03 and 0.08 m/s for velocity and between $1e-6$ to $6e-6$ m for slope). As expected velocity and slope are tightly coupled together and the Dongnai discharge is controlling these variables - lower discharge implies lower velocities and slope at the Dongnai. Additionally, the slope of the Saigon river is affected by the discharge of the Dongnai. We see an increase of up to 20% in slope that gradually decreases from km 120 towards upstream. Additionally, the velocity also increases but to a lower extent ($< 1.5\%$). However, these

Figure B.4: Percentage difference, PD , (left) and absolute error, AE , (right) between the base experiment and experiment 1 for velocity, slope and tidal range.

values are very close to the transition zone of the domain and thus, might be affected by numerical problems.

- Halving the discharge of the Dongnai results in a reduction of both velocity and slope along the Dongnai river.
- Halving the discharge of the Dongnai results in an increase of both velocity and slope at the Saigon river, specially near the confluence.

The lower discharge of the Dongnai slightly affects the tidal range with a downstream increase of less than 3% ($AE < 0.1$ m). Therefore, in the Dongnai, tidal range is less affected by discharge than in the Saigon. This is possibly due to the fact that the coastal dynamics are predominant in this section of the system since the tidal wave seems to be almost unaffected. However, this phenomena is extended upstream where the tidal range also increased by 3% almost along the whole length of the Saigon river. Thus, the Dongnai discharge is capable of modulating the tidal wave propagation not only downstream but also upstream. It seems that the Dongnai's discharge is coupled to the Saigon's hydrodynamics mainly via attenuation of tidal range.

- Halving the discharge of the Dongnai results in small increase ($\approx 3\%$) in tidal range all along the system.
- The Dongnai's discharge affects the dynamics upstream of the confluence.

Figure B.5: Percentage difference, PD , (left) and absolute error, AE , (right) between the base experiment and experiment 1 for velocity, slope and tidal range.

B.4 Analysis of the Coastal Boundary Condition

B.4.1 Seasonality experiments

The coastal boundary condition for the base experiment (plot 3 of figure B.1) presents an average water level of -0.0013 m during the dry season and of -0.3 m during the wet season which amounts to an average decrease in water levels of almost 30 cm during the wet season. This marked seasonality can be attributed to the wind-driven ocean circulation due to the northeast monsoon (September-April) and southwest monsoon (May-August) (Marchesiello et al. 2019).

In this sub-section, an experiment without the seasonality of the coastal BC (experiment 3) will be compared to an experiment with a fictitious decrease of average water level during the wet season (experiment 4). For experiment 3, the BC at the coast is constructed with a single spring-neap cycle (duration of 30 days) which is repeated for the duration of one year. For experiment 4, the same coastal BC is used but with an added step signal during the wet season (June - November) such that the average water level is decreased by 30 cm. The BCs used for these experiments can be found in figure B.6. Comparing these two experiments provides insights on the effect of the coastal dynamics along the river. Experiment 3 presents no seasonality due to the coastal BC

whereas experiment 4 will have a marked difference in water level during the wet season. This simulates the seasonality of the coastal water level as seen in the base experiment but allows to remove all other effects due to anomalies in the coastal signal.

Figure B.6: The three BCs used for the coastal experiments. Units are m^3/s for the discharge and m for water level. The BC of the coast was changed to a single spring-neap cycle repeated over the duration of one year for experiment 3 (left). For experiment 4 (right), a step signal was added to the coastal BC during wet season.

Two metrics were computed for this experiment: the percentage difference, PD , and the absolute error, AE . Plots for the PD and AE for the velocity, U , the slope, S , and the tidal range, Tr , are given in figures B.7 and B.8, respectively. The results in these figures show that a decrease of 30 cm on average water level at the coast has an impact on U and S nearly all over the domain. On the other hand, the tidal range remains practically unchanged up to km 50 where it decreased from a near 0% difference to a -15% difference at the dam (km 0). This translates to a 10 cm difference in Tr at the dam.

- A decrease of **30 cm** on average water level at the coast leads to a decrease of up to -15% ($AE = 10 \text{ cm}$) of tidal range near the dam.

For the velocity, we find a decrease of around 12% ($AE \approx 0.005$ to 0.02 m/s) all the way past the DN confluence and a sudden jump upstream of the BD station. This shows a clear discontinuation between the two rivers which can be attributed to the sudden change of geometry (figure B.2) together with

Figure B.7: Percentage difference between experiments 3 and 4 for velocity, slope and tidal range.

the Dongnai discharge. It seems as though there is an area of adjustment between the confluence (km 142) and immediately upstream of the BD station (km 125). This indicates that the Dongnai confluence has a strong effect on the first 20 km of the Saigon river. However, the results in this area are hard to interpret and might not be physical but rather numerical in nature.

- A decrease of **30 cm** on average water level at the coast leads to a decrease in velocity of around 12% up to km 125.
- There is an adjustment to the sudden change of geometry in the area between the Saigon-Dongnai confluence at km 142 and km 125. This area produces behaviour that is hard to interpret and might be an artifact of numerical, rather than physical, phenomena.
- We can split the domain in three parts: 1. the Saigon part from km 0 to km 125, 2. an adjustment part from km 125 to km 142 and 3. the Dongnai part from km 142 to km 200.
- The second part is hard to interpret and corresponds to the Dongnai confluence effect.

In part 1 of the domain, the difference between experiments remains negligible but starts increasing at km 50 towards the dam. At the dam we see an increase of up to 5% in the velocity ($AE \approx 0.01$ m/s).

The percentage difference and absolute error for the slope follow the same dynamics discussed for the velocity. This indicates that the local slope of

the river and the velocity are tightly coupled together in the model. In part 1, the slope PD remains around 5% and increases near the dam up to 18% ($AE \approx 7.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m). For part 3, the slope PD is on average -13% ($AE \approx 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m).

Figure B.8: Absolute difference between experiments 3 and 4 for velocity, slope and tidal range.

A decrease of **30 cm** on average water level at the coast leads to a decrease in slope and velocity in the Dongnai and an increase in slope and velocity in the Saigon. This means that the Saigon experiences a higher discharge especially near the dam where both the velocity and slope increase the most. This increase is connected to the decrease of tidal range at this location which implies a weaker effect of tides and allows the dam's discharge to better control the river. In the Dongnai the tidal range PD stays within 2%, yet both velocity and slope decrease which indicates a decrease of discharge.

- A decrease of **30 cm** on average water level at the coast leads to a decrease in slope in the Dongnai and an increase in slope in the Saigon. For the Saigon, this is due to the decrease in tidal range which allows the dam to control the dynamics.

B.4.2 Storm surge experiments

In recent years, many cyclones have had severe impacts on coastal regions of Vietnam and through climate change it is expected that the severity and frequency of these events will increase (Trinh et al. 2020). Southern Vietnam ($14^\circ - 9.5^\circ$) is vulnerable to coastal disasters, especially storm surges caused by tropical cyclones. For the period 1950-2010, 25% of cyclones that made

landfall in Vietnam were in this area (Takagi et al. 2014). In order to study the consequences of storm surge on the Saigon river system an ephemeral increase in the coastal BC is required. This was achieved by modifying the coastal BC of experiment 3 (using the repeated tidal cycle). We increase the water level by 0.2, 0.5 and 0.8 m for the period of 3 days as shown in figure B.9. The first surge happens in the beginning of May, the second in the beginning of July and the last one in the beginning of October. This experiment will be referred to as the "storm" experiment.

Figure B.9: The three BCs used for the storm surge experiment. Units are m³/s for the discharge and m for water level. The coastal BC has peaks in the beginning of May (0.2m), July (0.5m) and October (0.8m).

In figure B.10, one can find the percentage difference for velocity, slope and tidal range between the experiment with repeated tidal cycles and the storm experiment. It can be seen that for all surges the effects along the domain seem

to vary between -20 and +20%. This might be due to numerical re-adjustment of the model and it seems to lack a physical explanation. Additionally, some results seem to be paradoxical as the two smallest surges decrease the velocity near the coast (up to -20% PD) whereas the largest surge (in October, 0.8 m) increased the velocity by 20%. The same can be said about the slope PD that oscillates between -20 and +20% along X. Finally, the tidal range seems to be affected by this sudden increase in water level for the given 3 days. It increases near the dam by 20% while remaining nearly unchanged elsewhere.

In conclusion, it seems difficult to obtain any meaningful physical interpretation of the storm experiment. This implies that the model is too sensitive to short lived variations at the coastal BC and thus, the difference between experiments is too erratic to offer meaningful interpretation.

Figure B.10: Plots of percentage difference between experiment 3 (repeated tidal cycles) and storm experiment with punctual storm surges of 3 day duration. The first plot shows the velocity, the second the slope and the third the Tidal range.

B.5 Experiment seasonality due to Dam

In this section, we follow a similar methodology as for experiments 3 and 4 where the impacts of the coastal BC were studied. The dam boundary condition for the base experiment (plot 1 of figure B.1) presents an average discharge of 30 m/s during the dry season and an increased discharge (up to 3 times larger) during the wet season. Based on these values another experiment is conducted with a dam discharge of 30 m/s plus a step signal that doubles the discharge during the wet season to 60 m /s (experiment 5, figure B.11).

All other BCs are left as in the base experiment.

Figure B.11: The three BCs used for the dam experiments. Units are m^3/s for the discharge and m for water level. The BC of the dam was kept constant for the first experiment (left) and then a step signal was added in the wet season for the second experiment (right).

Comparing these two experiments provides insights on the effect of doubling the discharge of the dam. Experiment 1 has a constant discharge and thus, presents no seasonality. Experiment 5 simulates a doubling of the discharge during the wet season. The percentage difference and absolute error between these two experiments are presented in figures B.12 and B.13, respectively. These results show that the dam affects only part 1 of the domain namely, the Saigon river. Tidal range remains unaffected throughout the domain except for the first 25 km downstream of the dam. A twice larger dam discharge reduces the tidal range up to 25% ($AE = 0.24 \text{ m}$) at the dam (plot 3 in figure B.13). This means that tidal forcing is little affected by the dam's discharge throughout the river.

- A doubling of the dam's discharge only influences the Saigon river part of the domain.
- Tidal range remains unaffected everywhere in the domain except for the 25 km downstream of the dam which see a Tr reduction of up to 25%.

Velocity in the Saigon river is increased by around 80% (AE between 0.01 and 0.08 m/s) in the first 75 km after the dam. Then, between km 75 and the

Figure B.12: Percentage difference between dam experiments 1 and 5 for velocity, slope and tidal range.

transition part of the domain (km 125) velocity is increased by around 40% ($AE < 0.01$ m/s). This is expected as a higher discharge implies a higher water velocity. The slope of the river is also increased along the Saigon. It reaches a PD of 200% in some parts which corresponds to a tripling of the slope due to a doubling of the dam's discharge. There is a parabolic profile in slope PD for the first 75 km that remains unexplained. Note that the values of slope are very small and thus, PD values can be large but with small differences between values as can be seen by the slope AE in plot 2 of figure B.13.

- A doubling of the dam's discharge increases the velocity at the first 75 km after the dam by 80% and by around 40% for the remainder of the river Saigon (km 75 to km 125).
- A doubling of the dam's discharge increases the slope along the Saigon river between 50 to 200% depending on location.

The increase in discharge explains the velocity and slope increase at the Saigon part of the domain. Furthermore, at km 125 where the transition zone between the Saigon and Dongnai starts the effect of the dam's discharge is muted. In fact, the Dongnai branch of the domain is very little affected by the dam BC. This is mainly due to the geometry change and input discharge from the Dongnai BC which together mitigate the dam effect.

Figure B.13: Absolute error between dam experiments 1 and 5 for velocity, slope and tidal range.

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